

Larp Festivals as Democratic Spaces

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About the project - Larpocracy

Larpocracy researches spaces for deliberation and democratic skill building through live-action role-playing (larp). Funded by Horizon Europe, seven leading partners will study the use of larp as a method for creating inclusive and democratic social spaces, both online and offline.

Our mission is to investigate the potential of live-action role-playing (larp) as a method to foster democratic skill building and political engagement. Our research aims to leverage this innovative form of co-creative embodied play to address declining engagement in traditional democracy and the limitations of social media in fostering civic discourse.

The project will produce:

- Studies and experiments chartering capacities of larp in supporting democratic engagement and fostering democratic skill-building.
- Public events in collaboration with designers and organizers from marginalized and vulnerable communities.
- Design exemplars of larp and larp spaces capable of supporting inclusivity and democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Democracy by Design Toolkit.
- A widespread community of Experts understanding the capacities of larp and larp-like spaces in fostering democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Policy Recommendations supporting policymakers in multiple domains.

Executive summary

This report is the first deliverable from Work Package 5: Design of Spaces for Human Encounter in the Horizon Europe funded research project Larpocracy. It lays the foundations for our research on larp festivals and larp conventions as democratic spaces and describes the first stages in the development of a forthcoming toolbox supporting the experience design of participatory cultural events. In this first report, we map out the context and form of larp festivals and conventions, consider how “democracy” in the context of in-person events can be understood and modelled, and discuss the design of participatory experiences – including the design of participation itself – as it is understood within the design movement known as *Nordic larp*.

The goal of our research project, of which this report covers the first year of work, is twofold. We seek evidence-based tools for strengthening democratic culture at larp-cultural events, and to give guidance for how these can be applied in other co-creative and/or participatory contexts. In line with the wider Larpocracy project, this could include e.g. participatory democracy, civic participation, or civil-society organisations in and beyond the cultural sector.

This report does not present results, any completed theoretical model, nor indeed practical recommendations, although our preliminary analyses, when taken all together, suggest interesting directions. Larp (live-action role-playing) as an expression is relatively young and while the form itself is relatively well understood, phenomena and cultures connected to it have not been systematically studied or in most cases even properly documented. This is also the case for larp festivals and conventions, the connected and partly overlapping event types that we study.

This report discusses how to understand *larp festivals* (showcases of multiple short-form larps) as arts festivals and why drawing a line between them and conference-style *larp conventions* is not straightforward. Our academic research is focused on larp festivals and conventions in the Nordics, situated here in a wider international context, but always focusing volunteer-run non-profit events. We trace the history of larp conventions and the closely related role-playing conventions back to the literary science fiction fandom convention that originated in the United States in the 1930s and describe their variety today.

Analysing their functions, we suggest that larp festivals and conventions – and their co-creating participant communities – be understood as sites both of play and cultural co-creation, and of processes both developing and legitimising the cultural forms they centre. We argue that larp festivals and conventions are sometimes cultural institutions, and always part of a cultural public sphere. They commission new works and support their circulation; are loci for artistic work, criticism, academic study, and publication activities; and offer models for cultural production and centre formation with no or limited public investment, yet outside the commercial marketplace. Larp festivals and conventions are places for being and thinking different: for experimentation with, transformation through, and participation in alternative models, identities, communities, and ways of being.

We review a range of theoretical approaches to democratic spaces, arriving at a multi-perspectival understanding of democratic space as a site of communication, contestation, power, capital, and the social production of spaces and subjectivities, while also foregrounding networks of care, embodied play, and alternative temporalities. Larp festivals and conventions are described as actors in society, as volunteer productions, as experienced by their participants, as arenas of democratic imagination,

and as conduits of democratic imaginaries into the public sphere. For each of these approaches, relevant research directions are suggested as wider context for our own ongoing work, which is also sketched out.

The final section of the report discusses the practice of experience design; how it is understood in the Nordic larp design community; how we hypothesise that these design practices may be shaping the larp-cultural events we study; and briefly our ongoing work to both document design practices and evaluate their outcomes. Core concepts from participation-focused experience design illustrate how every aspect of an experience can enable or hamper the participant's sense of agency, ownership, and belonging.

Looking ahead, fieldwork results will help us iterate on models of democratic participatory spaces as well as of their design. Conceptual tools from Nordic larp are at minimum pedagogically useful for understanding of how physical and social environments interact. At best, they may provide a basic framework for a design language for human participation.

1. Introduction

1.1. Goal and audience of this document

The goal of this report is to explicate how larp festivals and conventions can function as democratic spaces. Based on expert knowledge, existing literature, and preliminary observations from fieldwork, this document explains how we understand "larp festivals and conventions", how we approach "democratic spaces", and how larp festivals function as such democratic spaces.

This report is the first deliverable output from *Work Package 5: Design of Spaces for Human Encounter* of the Horizon Europe-funded Larpocracy project. The overall goal of WP5 is to develop and test design recommendations for democratic larp spaces. Specifically, we seek to create recommendations for the design of events and social interactions that increase participation, enhance experiences of agency and belonging, build collaborative, caring, and inclusive cultures, as well as teaching skills and reflexivity related to democratic engagement. While the work draws from larp festivals and primarily seeks to impact future larp events, it has implications for event design and experience design more broadly. The work is rooted in the understanding that social encounters between humans are *addressable through design* – that through conscious design of rules, practices, mechanics, and environments, it is possible to impact the experiences that participants in an event construct for themselves and each other.

The beginning stages of any interdisciplinary research project require significant time to be spent on mapping knowledge, investigating different knowledge-constitutive interests, and aligning (or at least discussing) the various ontological, epistemological, and methodological foundations. That has also been our experience in this first year of our research.

The primary goal of this document is to formalise the outcomes of our foundational work in these areas and share it with our colleagues across the Larpocracy project, as well as with our external evaluators, who need to gain the same understanding of key concepts and theoretical frameworks in the ongoing WP5 research.

The secondary audience is industry practitioners, public sector representatives, students, other researchers, or anyone else coming upon this public document. We have tried to be comprehensible, and in the case of previously understudied aspects of the work also suitably comprehensive, for preliminary observations to exist in a public record even when academic publications might be years away.

It is important to note that while this report reflects our current understand, the work is ongoing and unfinished. Thus, this document should be approached as a baseline for ongoing and forthcoming empirical and theoretical work.

1.2. Work Package Goals and Progress

According to the project proposal, the goal of the overall Larpocracy project is to "understand and enhance the capacities of larp to support civic participation and democratic skill-building and explore how these capacities can inform the design of spaces for deliberation and political engagement both online and offline."

Within Larpocracy, the goal of WP5 is to understand *how larp festivals and conventions can function as democratic spaces*. The stated purposes of this exploration are:

- 1) to support existing communities in making game-cultural events more and intentionally democratic
- 2) to evaluate whether learning from them might support forms of democratic engagement elsewhere in society – whether civic participation, democratic skill-building, political organising, or building better spaces for deliberation.

This work is focused through the systematic study of contemporary larp-cultural events employing specific design and production practices with a high degree of relevance for democratic innovation – namely, *the tradition with Nordic Larp discourse to view participation itself as the object of holistic event design*.

For any lessons from this approach to become usefully transferable and applicable to other contexts, not only must these practices be studied in situ, but *their originating contexts* must be well understood, and both *the design practices themselves* and the *conceptualisations of democratic space* employed in this work must be thoroughly theorised.

As per our project plan, we have in the first year of this work:

- Mapped out existing larp festivals (see 2.1, Appendix A)
- Are in the process of producing foundational research on larp festivals and conventions and their histories (see 2.2-2.5)
- Conducted fieldwork at and made study visits to larp festivals and conventions to chart existing practices (see Appendix B)
- Evaluated theoretical models for conceptualising of democratic space in the larp festival context (see 3.1-3.3.)
- Began outlining a theoretical model for the design of human participation as understood within the studied design communities (see 4.2-4.3)
- Initiated work on all 2026 events and activities.

1.3. Key concepts

This report discusses larp festivals as democratic spaces. It maps the emergence of larp festivals; reviews literature on democratic spaces as aligning with different theoretical concepts of democracy; explores the democratic potential of larp festivals; and finally looks into how design can be consciously used create them. To provide a groundwork for the discussion, let us look at key concepts underlying the project.

Larp is a form of expression, like theatre or literature, in the form of social role-playing, where, guided by rules, participants portray fictional characters in a shared imaginary world. Larps are created by larp designers, who craft the fictional setting, set the theme, structure the event, oversee the character creation, and provide the rules for interaction and safety. The participating players are co-creators of the work who have significant autonomy and agency within boundaries set by the characters they portray, the setting, and the rules.

Larp can be divided into three stages. First there is preparation for the larp. During this time larp designers, larpwriters, and producers design the fictional world and interaction dynamics, writers write game materials and characters (the distributed *larp script*) and produce the event. The player-participants familiarising themselves with the fiction, the rules, and their character, and often also prepare their costumes and props. The preparation culminates on-site in a shared workshop. Second, there is the time the larp is being played, when participants inhabit a fictional setting in character. This is also called the *runtime*. Finally, there is the post-larp phase of deroling (getting out of character), debrief, and decompression, usually including a reflective discussion amongst participants on what they together. (For more discussion on defining and conceptualizing the key aspects of larp, see e.g. Montola 2012; Zagal & Deterding 2018; Koljonen et al. 2019.)

Most larp traditions originally developed out of tabletop role-playing games, like *Dungeons & Dragons*. Over the decades they have been influenced, among other things, by various traditions of theatre and performance, non-digital and digital games, scouting and pioneer movements, visual arts, martial arts, youth work pedagogies, science fiction and fantasy fandoms, BDSM, political activism, and popular cultures (see also Harviainen et al. 2018).

Their formal qualities and production practices have also been shaped by their national and local contexts. In addition to cultural norms and practices this includes structural aspects like public policies (e.g. *the freedom to roam*) and civic society organizational structures (Johansson et al, 2025). This has resulted in numerous different larp cultures, all with their own specific histories. For example, larp is used for recreational purposes and for artistic expression, but also for goal-oriented purposes such as education and therapy (e.g. Bowman, Diakolambrianou, & Brind 2024). The larp festivals that we study present larps as a hobby, as recreation, or as art. However, they do at times feature larps that have also been used for specific purposes, including political activism and civic education (Johansson et al 2025). While recreational and artistic larps are most relevant to WP5 research, such explicitly telic larps, are important to the Larpocracy project as a whole.

The design tradition we focus on, often referred to as *Nordic larp*, is hard to characterise because it views larps as bespoke works – a single medium, whose every formal or artistic aspect can change across works. Its designers and players view larp as a valid form of cultural expression, which similarly to literary fiction or contemporary art is capable of tackling any topic. The tradition currently tends to favour larps that are either short-form (approximately 4 hours, for up to about 15 participants) or long-form (typically 1-4 days, for up to about 150 participants). They are typically stand-alone “one-shot” events (while many other larp traditions favour continuous, open-ended *campaigns*). (For an introduction to the Nordic larp traditions, see Stenros & Montola 2010; Saitta, Holm-Andersen, & Back 2014; Koljonen et al. 2019)

These larps are usually run non-profit, and some receive cultural or arts funding. While this tradition originated in Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland, it has for about two decades not been limited in influence or inspirations to the Nordic countries. Larps that are similar in content, form, and production culture can be found all over Europe, and even beyond. Nordic larp design discourse and its institutions, such as conferences and books, remain influential, and no agreed-upon name has emerged for the wider category of larp whose designers or players engage with it. In addition, distinct styles that have grown out of the experimental Nordic community now have their own international trajectories of influence. Among these are *blackbox larp*, shortform works in theatre

black boxes often exploring embodied or somatic approaches; *larp in fine arts contexts*, where larp design tools or the medium itself is employed as a method in relational works; and *international larp*, high-concept events targeting an international player base, staged and played in English, commonly at interesting destinations.

We are using the term *larp festivals and conventions* as shorthand for larp-cultural events with scheduled programming where designers and players gather to play a selection of larps, develop and share larp-related knowledge, or to celebrate the traditions and practices of their larp communities. The difficulties of delineating the boundaries for the larp festivals, conventions, and conferences on which we focus will be discussed in depth in chapter 2. It excludes everything from the wider category of *larp-cultural events* that can be clearly identified as another type of event, such as a larp design *masterclass*, a *film festival* devoted to documentaries about larp, or a *crafting get-together* where outfits for a larp are created.

A *larp festival* is usually taken to mean events where people come together to a venue where at least two larps are staged. A typical larp festival lasts two days and has three to five scheduled slots where one can play larps that take four hours to run (including workshop, runtime, and debrief). This type of event was the starting point of our work, but as it has progressed, we have discovered the plurality of larp-cultural events. Most important for our purpose is the *larp conventions*, at which it is common that some larp are played, but the focus is more on lectures, workshops, and discussions on and around larp (or even role-playing games, games more broadly, or even genre media of all kinds, with larp representing only one strand of the programming). Larp conventions and larp festivals have varying backgrounds, cultural contexts, and histories, but can serve very similar functions in their local communities. For our later recommendations to have the widest possible application across European play cultures, we have opted for an inclusive definition. This will also serve our continuing research, which is engaging specifically with design choices, i.e. possible ways of organising events, and with participant agency, which is shaped by such choices as well as the participants' preconceptions of the events. For a significantly more detailed discussion, see the next chapter.

Democracy has meant many things over the centuries, but at its core it is a form of governance where the will of the people is the basis of power. How this is implemented, for example if it direct or if it is there representation, and who counts as people, has varied over history. For our conceptualization of democracy, it is central that everyone has not only the right, but access to participation, and that it is safe to do so. Participation includes not only the possibility to participate in free and fair election, but also to have access to deliberative public discourse, to receive care, and be protected. This means that democracy is rooted in human rights and civil liberties, including protection from the state. Democracies also need to be effective, meaning that a government need to be able to act on the citizen's behalf. Furthermore, we understand democracy as a process – as an ongoing practice that requires work and vigilance. (For more, see e.g. Economist Intelligence Unit 2024.)

Democratic space, then, is a site where processes relating to democracy can take place. This term also has multiple overlapping and conflicting meanings. For us, *democratic space* as a concept means a social space where practices relating to democratic work take place. These practices can be formal and legible to the national or international democratic governance, such as meetings or election, but they can also be informal or sites where practices are contested or re-envisioned, such as protests.

Democratic spaces are sites of communication where norms and structures are made, upheld, shaped, questioned, taught, learned, unlearned, resisted – in a word, recreated. Thus, access to such spaces, the language and culture of the spaces, and their design and organization are central to the project of democracy. As these sites are not natural but created by humans, there is a clear connection to conscious design of events, experiences, and processes.

We conceive larps as socio-cultural technologies, consciously designed events where brief encounters or longer interactions between humans take place, where participation itself is the material being shaped. There is a connection between larp design and *experience design*, yet our work emerged from a specific tradition on larp design: Nordic larp.

We take it as given that it is possible to design human encounters, and that every possible element in that encounter from lighting and room temperature to etiquette and lines of sight can be consciously designed. This is what it means when we say that everything is a *designable surface*. Obviously, it is never possible to design everything for a specific case: choices need to be made. Even so, theoretically everything can be designed even if practically it is not possible to do so simultaneously.

1.4. Methodological approaches

This deliverable document aims to carve out a new space between event and festival studies, game studies, larp studies, design studies, and democracy studies. To do so, we need to construct a coherent basis: a theoretical framework rooted in existing scholarly work.

That is to say: this report is not a double blind peer-reviewed academic publication and the research sketched out in this document is preliminary. Parts of the work presented here will be further developed and published in academic venues. All results are subject to updates, clarifications, and corrections as our work progresses.

Approaching this document, note that, first, there is a strong literature review element, as we triangulate existing work on, for example, "democratic space" and "festival". Our reviews have not been systematic, but opportunistic, as the aim is not to be comprehensive but practical.

Second, our work has an expert quality to it. The academic partners and practitioner partners in this project all have deep and situated knowledge about larp, larp design, and larp festivals, as participants, designers, organizers, critics, or evaluators. This embodied expertise and designerly knowledge also informs and guides our work. This makes many of us 'insiders' or 'aca-fans' (see Burr 2005; Hills 2002; Jenkins 1992), requiring ethical reflection on participation, observation, and influence.

Thirdly, during the first ten months of the project Larpocracy, we have started fieldwork at numerous larp festivals. While both data collection and analysis are far from finished, this field work has informed our approach, by expanding our horizons and by prompting new questions.

The creation of this document has been preceded by numerous discussions and workshops on specific topics, and the discussion has continued while crafting this document. This deliverable is a report on where we are today, having processed these three inputs in our joint hermeneutic spiral. Work on these topics will continue, and parts of this report will be further developed for publication.

1.5. How to read this document

This document comprises of this introduction and three additional chapters. The argumentation flows from *what* to *why* to *how*. Chapter 2 discusses what larp festivals and larp conventions are, as well as sketching out their development and formal variety. It gives an overview of the phenomenon we study, and the primary field where we are expecting to make an impact. While we maintain an open approach in relation to what counts as a "larp-cultural event", our research is tied to specific traditions and contexts, which it is important to delineate.

In Chapter 3, we move on to the *why*. To investigate larp festivals as democratic spaces, we must first define what that means and why it matters. This chapter gives an overview of how "democratic spaces" can be understood, what different paths to democratic participation and political engagement can be found, and how democratic cultures and skills relate to this. This overview lays the foundations for studying how larp festivals and conventions can support democratic participation, directly or indirectly.

Finally, the *how* chapter outlines how the organisers of larp festivals and conventions use intentional experience design, in ways directly influenced by the subject matter of these festivals, larps. Larp is, at its core, a participatory practice. As socio-cultural technology, larps can operate as sites fostering co-creation and community-building, and as such can support, build, re-imagine, and strengthen democracy. Although the design of larps and larp festivals is a wider field, key aspects of it include designing for participation, inclusion, agency, belonging, co-creative culture, and shared ownership. These are central to the values and praxis of larp (and to those of larp festivals and conventions) in Northern European contexts. Especially in the Nordics, where a strong civic society is valued, larp cultures has been particularly shaped by participatory civic practices such as democratically organised non-profit volunteering. Larp design, larp festival design, and design for democratic participation have significant overlap. The report's final chapter sketches out next steps toward developing a design language for democratic spaces.

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1.5.2 Distribution of Labour

Everyone mentioned as author of the document has participated in writing of the document, or in the underlying thinking and research. Chapter 1 is mostly written by Jaakko Stenros. Chapter 2 is mostly written by Johanna Koljonen, Jaakko Stenros, and Piotrek Warzyszynski. Section 3 is mostly

written by Hanne Grasmø, Johanna Koljonen, and Jaakko Stenros. Section 4 is mostly written by Johanna Koljonen and Jaakko Stenros. Appendix A is based on work mostly done by Piotrek Warzyszynski. Appendix B is mostly written by Hanne Grasmø, Marcin Słowikowski, Jaakko Stenros, and Piotrek Warzyszynski. Additional work and participation by Elektra Diakolambrianou, Alessandro Giovannucci, and Mafalda Morganti.

1.5.3 Statement on the use of AI/LLM

Artificial intelligence or large language models were used in the background work of this report to create overviews of some of the topics discussed, to find material to read, and to identify gaps in our knowledge. Artificial intelligence or large language models have not been used in the production of the text, aside from the proofreading provided by Microsoft Word.

2. Emergence and Form of Larp Festivals and Conventions

2.1 Introduction to larp festivals and conventions in Europe today

2.1.1. What are we studying?

This work package explores how larp festivals and conventions function as democratic spaces, and how design elements and the intentional design practices commonly used in the communities we study to create such events may strengthen participation and provide space for community co-creation. Our assumption is that these tools could also be applied in non-larp contexts where participation matters, such as spaces related to democratic participation.

Isolating design practices and charting their underlying assumptions about how human encounters can be designed requires us to understand the studied events deeply: to situate them in the wider field of similar events across Europe and the world, to understand how the events themselves and their participatory outcomes are shaped by their production circumstances and local contexts, and to explore how actual participant experiences may connect to designerly intentions. Our work builds on existing academic research and theoretical concepts and expands it with empirical observation and fieldwork by researchers who are also larp experts.

The fieldwork within the academic research project is concentrated on Nordic larp festivals, explicitly to explore whether and how their organisers consciously use the specialised experience-design discourse of Nordic larp cultures in the creation of the events. *Nordic larp design discourse* is a relatively systematic language for the analysis and creation of interaction and experiences. We hypothesise it is particularly well-suited as a basis for the toolkit for design of democratic participation that we are ultimately aiming to produce. Reasons for this include its holistic view of events and the participant journey: particular attention paid to participant agency, shared norms, and temporary cultures; and a grounding in non-profit civil-sector volunteer cultures.

In our preparatory work during the first six months of the Larpocracy project we visited many of these events, trying to understand their differences but also looking for connections and patterns. Systematic field work started in the seventh month of the project and is currently ongoing. Contextualising the Nordic larp-related observations and getting a feel for contemporary event cultures and organising practices across Europe necessitated study visits similar types of events in other play cultures, regions, or countries (see Appendix B for a full list of events we have studied or visited).

2.1.2. What kinds of events have we considered?

Starting our work by informally listing relevant larp festivals, we immediately realised that events viewed by their community participants as belonging to the same category, or as obviously related, differ from each other on several parameters. This was the case even within the single artistic subculture of Nordic larp. As the first output of the Work Package would be a list of contemporary larp festivals across Europe, defining the term to limit the selection rapidly became quite complicated.

For example, **Knutepunkt** (1997-; styled Knudepunkt in Danish, Solmukohta in Finnish, and Knutpunkt in Swedish) is a four-day event organised annually in the Nordic countries, entirely focused on the larp medium.¹ Its programme features talks, discussions, and workshops, but only few larps are played. **Stoori: Helsinki Freeform Festival** (2023-) does not include any talks or workshops but offers sixteen larps in a single day. **Blackbox CPH** (2012-) is mainly a showcase of new or work-in-progress larps, with social programme reduced to a minimum, **Grenselandet** (2010 -) has a socio-political approach, mixing larps and larp designers from authoritarian regimes (e.g. Palestine, Belarus) with the European chamber larp scene, often including larps with political content, while **Spillerom** (2014 -) primarily focuses on community building and strengthening the local and regional larp scenes across language and national boundaries. In Denmark, **Fastaval** (1986-) is a long-standing festival focused on original freeform scenarios (which have influenced larps significantly) and original board games, with other role-playing and tabletop game activities also represented. Fastaval offers coaching and support structures for designers contributing original work.

Some events, like Knutepunkt, gather hundreds of participants, while others, like **Portal** (2013-), are aimed at a smaller community specific to its European region. There are also significantly larger events, like the now 10.000-participant **Ropecon** (1994-) in Finland. This can be harder still to categorise. As larp is not the event's sole focus, only a section of its programme features larps, larp-related talks, and occasionally larp designers as Guests of Honour. Similarly, its participants are primarily Finnish. Yet, because of Ropecon's scale, participation in its larp-related programming, or the fraction of its international participants, are still numerically significant compared to smaller events.

The variety within even just the handful of "larp festivals" discussed above makes it hard to come up with a single definition that could describe them all, or a single term for the category. Each of these events is different even in terms of content, function or target group, let alone aspects such as pricing and how their production is organised. Depending on their specific format, the event's history, and the local linguistic and cultural context, these kinds of larp-cultural events could be known as for instance conventions, conferences, or festivals (either as English loan words or in the local language). Local larp cultures may have strong opinions about how events described by such different terms should be defined and may not always be aware that such uses are not consistent even within the same language area.

As one of our goals is strengthening the larp community, starting by gathering information about as many larp-related events as possible made sense. It soon became clear that a definition of a larp festival as an event where people gather to play a curated selection of larps would exclude many we considered important (like the Polish larp conference **KoLa**, at which none are played.) As this chapter will explore, larp-cultural events not immediately classifiable as "larp festivals" have significant impact on the development of the larp form and are a core context for developing, collecting, archiving, and sharing knowledge within larp communities. They cannot be omitted by this study.

For our list of contemporary events we decided to employ the most inclusive approach possible, in practice, we included every event that whose present existence we were able to confirm and that

¹ We have decided to highlight the names of festivals and conventions in bold each time they are mentioned for the first time. This practice was inspired by Jon Peterson's (2012) similar choice in *Playing at the World*.

the active larp community members or any member of our team could identify as larp festivals or larp conventions (Appendix A).

In our usage, “larp festivals and conventions” covers all events that significantly feature larps to be played, host larp-related discussions, contribute to the development of the larp community, or promote larp to new audiences. Some focus on playing new works or curated classics, others on upskilling larp practitioners or developing theoretical approaches. Some events approach larp as a tool for education or an artistic expression, others as a hobby. Some have strong institutional roots, while others are initiated by small groups of enthusiasts. Despite all their differences there are two elements all these events have in common: larps and community.

In the context of the research project, deciding how to define and label these kinds of events is not a purely linguistic curiosity. Participant behaviour at any event is necessarily shaped by the participants’ understanding of its context and nature, and such expectations naturally also affect whether they feel it is for them at all. Participant agency in specific situations can also be affected by an event’s organisational structures and by contextual or temporary cultural norms. For all these reasons, studying how larp festivals function as democratic spaces necessitates a nuanced understanding of what they are.

In the following sections, we will describe the range of these kinds of event, sketch out their cultural history as both festivals and conventions, discuss how the categories are related, and propose approaches to situating and understanding larp festivals and conventions within the wider cultural landscape.

2.1.3. What are larp festivals today?

Any event organiser or participant’s understanding of what larp festivals and conventions are commonly like will inevitably shape their design choices and the kinds of participation or democratic behaviours they can conceive of for themselves. To give an idea of the varieties of events we are studying, we have attempted a preliminary typology, based on observations made visiting events and their websites.

Varieties within the existing larp festivals and conventions were mapped out across four axes of classification: *purpose and content*, *community and structure*, *outreach*, and *origins*.

Purpose and content

The purpose of the event and the kind of programme elements it includes are often related. An event can have more than one purpose. These commonly include:

- **recreation and experience** – participants are offered larps to play and social interactions outside of the larp events (e.g. Stockholm Scenario Festival) and can sometimes focus on a certain topic where larp serves as a tool to discover it (e.g. Make a Scene, Łyżkon)
- **education and skill-training** – participants can share knowledge about certain topic or a theme (e.g. Edu-larp Conference), train their skills as larpers - like improvisation and handicrafts (e.g. Polish Larp Conference KoLa), and deepen their understanding of how to create and produce larps.
- **knowledge and theory development** – participants discuss and develop common understanding of larp as serious leisure and artistic design (e.g. Interaction Unfinished). The

purpose for these events can be to expand larp design as a format or genre (e.g. Stockholm Scenario Festival) and to build analytical and critical larp theory, for instance by publishing (para)academic books in connection with the event (e.g. Knutepunkt)

- **community building and recruiting** – the event offers a program with an emphasis on social interaction, so that participants get to know like-minded people. Beyond strengthening social networks in general, building trust and connections, these events also help players find and access larps, and to play them (e.g. Prolog).

Content types at these events commonly include:

- larp-related **presentations, discussions, and workshops** for developing larp-related knowledge or skills (e.g. Knutepunkt)
- **larps** – the event is a showcase of multiple larps (e.g. Immersion, Grenselandet)
- **mixed elements** – the event features larps and diverse larp-related activities (e.g. Portal Larp Convention)
- non-larp **social programming**, such as parties, stage shows, rituals, and games to strengthen community ties are common at these events (e.g. Knutepunkt) – but can be intentionally omitted at events whose schedules prioritise experiencing new work, or where socialising is expected to emerge spontaneously in dedicated spaces or after the event (e.g. Stoori: Helsinki Freeform Festival).

Organisation and structure

How the larp festivals are organised and by whom can be considered for instance in terms of financial model, levels of centralisation or curation, and temporal cycles.

- **Economic structure** – events can be **commercial**, i.e. organised for-profit (e.g. Flamberg) or as a brand activations (Spelkongress), or **non-profit**, i.e. with any profit reinvested into the community or the next event (e.g. BEta LARP, Spillerom).
- **Compensation** – most events of interest to our research are based entirely on **voluntary work**. The production may however be paying for expert labour, for instance for transport, or for a technician, a cook, or cleaning on site. Non-profit events sometimes employ **salaried staff** in central functions, whether employed for the purpose, or working on the project within the context of for instance a position as publicly funded game-cultural developer.
- **Pricing** – participation in the events can be **free of charge** (e.g. Portal), involve a **voluntary donation** (e.g. BEta LARP) or **ticketed** either for the event in its entirety (e.g. Knutepunkt, Grenselandet), or on a larp-by-larp basis (Blackbox Copenhagen). Ticketed events can sometimes be free or discounted for core staff members, for all volunteers, or for low income and/or young participants and/or participants from low-income countries. At other events everyone pays their way regardless of how much they have worked to produce it.
- **Centralisation** – events can be **top to bottom**, i.e. have an established team of organizers responsible for the event's design and core staff functions (e.g. Stockholm Scenario Festival), or **community-based**, i.e. where the event is co-created by its participant community and everyone can contribute to its final form (e.g. Portal Larp Convention).
- **Formality of organisation** – i.e. the event has an **established organisation** or entity responsible for it (e.g. The Smoke), or **informal** – emerging from spontaneous action within the community (e.g. Larpart). Recurring conventions can sometimes become **institutions**

even without institutional infrastructure. E.g. Knutepunkt, has for almost three decades been organised by any group in that year's host country willing to volunteer. Although a local registered association or similar structure is often also brought in for legal or administrative reasons, they are not responsible for the work getting done.

- **Curation** – with either a procedure for selecting the programme items (e.g. Stockholm Scenario Festival, Make a Scene) or showcasing every submitted programme item that space can be found for at the event (e.g. Blackbox CPH, Spillerom)

Levels of centralisation and formalisation are often related to the events age and temporal cycle. In practice, every event starts as a **one-off initiative**, and its original circumstances strongly determine how it is organised. Once it is known whether it will become **recurring**, practical factors such as sustainable access to volunteer labour or a need to administer financial resources or other assets across events may affect the formality of its organisational structure.

Community and outreach

For whom are the events?

- **Language** – Some events are **international**, i.e. gathering participants from several countries and use a lingua franca such as English fully (e.g. Knutepunkt, Grenselandet) or partly (e.g. Betalarp, Ropecon). Others are **domestic**, dedicated to the community of a certain country and using a national language exclusively or primarily (e.g. KrakON). In certain countries this may mean the convention is bilingual. E.g. Ropecon has a few items in Swedish, which is Finland's second official language. Many domestic events of significant scale or impact also offer some programming in English for international and immigrant participants (e.g. Ropecon, Fastaval, BEtalarp).
- **Focused inward or reaching out** – an event **prioritising an existing larp community** is dedicated to a certain larp community or larp tradition, sometimes narrowing the focus even further, such as targeting only designers or even conventions organizers. Events doing **outreach to new audiences** are open for new target groups and participants, also outside of larp community
- **Open or private** – Some events are **open to the public**, and everyone is welcome to take part (e.g. Make a Scene Festival). Others are **limited access**; there is some selection process for participants, according to criteria set by the organisers, or even **private**, i.e. limited to a close, predefined audience.
- **Focus** – either **entirely larp-focused** – the programme and all its elements are designed around larp and all programme items are related to larp (e.g. Knutepunkt, Portal Larp Convention), or **larp is a section of a bigger programme** – the event features multiple topics and methods, larp is one of them (e.g. Ropecon, Fastaval)

2.2 What are festivals?

2.2.1. What is a festival?

Historically the term 'festival' refers to a celebration or cultural performance, that is recurring, often in accordance with the calendar cycle. Festivals were either sacred, honouring a deity; or secular, in memory of an event or a person. In modern times such community festivals evolved into cultural

events, staged to focus on some theme or activity of special meaning to a community. “Through festivals, various aspects of identity, culture, and experience are created, performed, negotiated, contested, and consumed” (Ostashewski 2019), effects achieved mainly through the participation of the community – whether in the organisation of the event, providing content for it, or as its audience. There are several key elements of this type of event: festivals have a specific theme, are based on participation of a community, and consist of multiple activities.

Arts festivals grew out of religious and community festivals. While theatre festivals are commonly traced back to classical Greece, most arts festivals are a feature of a cultural landscape where artists rely economically on reaching wider audiences than a limited patronage class. Some also centre genres, like folk music, where professional careers either hardly existed or were funded in alternative ways.

Arts festivals in the modern sense are an organisational structure for making artistic work available in places or to audiences who may otherwise not have that access; for artist-practitioners to meet and sometimes compete with their skills; for enabling critical reflection of the work; and often for enthusiasts or junior artists to sample or be trained in specific aspects of the form.

Most commonly, an arts festival today centres the work, offering opportunities to see paintings, plays, or films; to experience pop music or poetry in performance. Significantly for our project, however, not all media lend themselves to the communal consumption of several works within a limited stretch of time: e.g. literature festivals are not typically a place where complete books are read aloud. Instead, audiences gather to hear authors being interviewed or participating in panels, to discuss literature themselves, to find new books to read, and to be in community with each other and with the literature professionals. Such an event does not differ dramatically from traditional community festivals.

The festival’s function of making work accessible is often conceptualised as democratising access to culture. At different times, underlying purposes have implicitly or explicitly included for instance developing the taste and critical abilities of a broader public by exposing audiences to the “best” culture; to support nation-building projects through communal celebrations of national culture or achievements (see e.g. McGuigan 2011); or to support the arts by developing and growing sustained audience communities.

Community festivals, which also continue through to the modern day, in turn often also include a significant proportion of cultural performances. Distinguishing between a dedicated arts festival and for instance a city festival such as a local “night of the arts” is not always straightforward, nor is it typically necessary. To reflect on the nature of these categories, however, we can view arts festivals as typically curated around a specific medium or theme, and as centring the work, and often the presence, of expert practitioners, while a community festival is fundamentally a local celebration. Cultural expression is often a part of both, but at a community festival, professional performance is often interspersed with celebrations of local talent, including amateurs. Indeed, festivals are a site where the categories of amateur and professional can blur. An environment centring skill, knowledge, craft, or community can make it less relevant whether one is a devotee or has the field in question as one’s primary occupation.

2.2.2. What then is a 'larp festival'?

In line with these broad historical definitions of festivals, a larp festival would be an event where larp designers and players gather to stage, facilitate, and play multiple larps, and/or to discuss and learn about them, and/or to celebrate their practitioner communities and their specific practices. The playing of larps is typically followed by social programme, offering participants an opportunity to strengthen community bonds, whether pre-existing or established through the co-creation of the artistic work.

Community participation is central to all the events we study, even those structured along the lines of e.g. a theatre festival, in part because of the typically volunteer-based non-profit structure of the larp communities we study, in part because of the co-creative nature of the larp medium itself. Larp is a participatory medium; all participants whose interactions and emotions are "part of the performance" of a larp are also in some sense its co-creators. Whether by playing or facilitating larps, deepen their expertise about larp or larp-adjacent activities, or volunteering in the organisation of the event itself, participants of larp festivals and conventions are engaging in communal activities and developing existing communities.

The understanding of 'festival' discussed above covers a significant part of larp-cultural events, only some of which specifically use the term festival or conceptualise of themselves as arts festival. Many of the larp-cultural events within the scope of our interest would instead be considered by their participants as obviously related to *role-playing conventions* or *larp conventions*. As the discussion in the next section will demonstrate, differentiating between 'conventions' and contemporary understandings of 'festivals' can be surprisingly challenging. Tracing the respective histories of these event types is further complicated by conflicting definitions of both in different cultural contexts; as well as by the great variety at different times in whether or not a specific role-playing experience in a convention or festival context would be considered a "larp".

2.3 What is a convention?

2.3.1. Science fiction fandom conventions

A 'convention' is a meeting of people around some shared purpose. *Trade conventions* (trade fairs and expos) and *political conventions* are among the best-known categories, both gathering professionals in a specific field or active members of a specific party. In the cultural sector, the *fandom convention* is the top category for events at which experts and enthusiasts engage with each other around a medium (e.g. fanzines), artform (e.g. anime), genre (e.g. horror), or work (e.g. *Game of Thrones*). Many of the fandom conventions most visible in the media today are commercial events, but they originate in non-profit volunteer culture and flourish in it still.

Specifically, the literary science fiction convention is the source that begat or inspired fandom conventions for other media and subgenres. Understanding role-playing conventions and festivals today requires us to understand this history. Where non-profit convention history is documented at all, it tends to be in the form of community memoir, or as appearances in the margins of studies of genres, popular media formats, or fandom practices. In the following, we have constructed an overview.

Fan conventions emerge in the United States as *science fiction conventions*, an unbroken tradition since the 1930s; **Worldcon - World Science Fiction Convention**, still an annual event, is first organised in 1939. Science fiction and fantasy literature are genres in themselves emblematic for collective reading and writing practices. Intellectual and social networks between fans had for decades been built and maintained through contributions to and via correspondence in fanzines and semi-professional publications, as well as magazines and journals. As natural extension of these networks, conventions became meeting-places for readers, critics and authors of these genres. In this sense, travelling to conventions in other cities, regions, or countries was as much about deepening social relationships than as about experiencing the programming. The convention format soon spread to Europe and beyond.

The structure and elements of science fiction conventions, such as panels, lectures, meet-and-greets with authors, and masquerade parties or other dress-up activities, remain to this day. Key qualities include a playful social atmosphere, a contrastingly serious attitude toward the works of interest and the artistry of their creators, and a strong sense of community with the other participants (styled “members”) of the convention.

2.3.2. Fandom conventions as a non-profit volunteer tradition

From the start, the local chapters or clubs producing science fiction conventions were organised in regional and sometimes national organisations. This structure that would have been familiar across the US from organisations like labour unions and rotary clubs (Mendlesohn 2014), from organised religion, and from leisure activities such as sports and scouting. At this time, cultural and educational activities were often organised through clubs and non-profit associations, whether directly, or as activities within for instance one's church or the labour movement. Early science fiction fandom especially was also a hobby for enthusiasts for cutting-edge science, and science fiction clubs often emerged in university settings.

The significant presence and influence of first- and second-generation European immigrants across the US will have contributed to a rich variety of cultural practices around non-profit organising, as well as aided the rapid spread of the sci-fi convention format abroad. Another likely but unstudied vector for popularising fandom practices was the presence of US military servicemen in Europe and Asia. For instance, two of the three organisers of the first German science fiction convention in 1956 were children of a US officer stationed in the country (Hansen, n.d.).

The organised fandom of these early associations is still a vital international movement. Worldcon has most often been in North America, but at the time of this writing, bids by local fan organisations to host this convention also include e.g. Australia, Rwanda, and Germany.

In the Nordic context, Sweden became an early locus for organised science fiction fandom. Its first convention, LunCon (1956) gathered about 40 participants from ten Swedish fan clubs, featuring on its programme a presentation about continental fandom; literary talks and discussions; lectures by scientists about human mutations and anti-gravity; screenings of fan-made science fiction films; and the founding of a national science fiction union specifically to organise conventions and support fan travel to international events (Pettersson 1956, Hanes n.d.).

The main purpose of this con, however, was to create a Swedish s-f union. This had been discussed for quite some time in the fmz, and we all considered such a necessity for

Sverifandom. (...) Some of the purpose of this union is to establish a more intimate contact between Swedish fans, by means of a special fandom column in HAPNA, to prepare for the eventual participation of Swedish fandom at the '57 Worldcon in London, and to prepare and arrange at least one Swedish con per year. (Helander quoted in Hanes n.d.)

In Finland, by contrast, organised fandom did not emerge until the 1980s (via Swedish-speaking Finns visiting Swedish conventions) but immediately became very popular.

Today the Nordic region as a whole is still an outlier in the size of its organised fandom, including the number of active members participating in international events (Mendlesohn 2014). Fandom's organisational forms and communal volunteering cultures of non-profit fandom is a good cultural fit with the Nordic social democracies, in which leisure activities are often still organised in this way. Volunteering around one's hobbies remains normalised, and the global trend of decreasing participation in civil sector organisations is slower in the Nordics (Robertsson 2023). The proportional prominence of Nordic fans within organised fandom can also be understood as a higher degree of resistance against the gradual transformation of media fandom into primarily a consumer position.

Over time, fandom would expand its scope of interest from literary sci-fi and fantasy to related genres in audiovisual and other media, including games, although the literary focus of traditional science fiction fandom remains. Its communities of knowledgeable and passionate fan members have remained significant nurturers of writers, critics, academics, artists, and other professionals and would-be professionals of its key genres.

Indeed, such fan communities have been described as *knowledge economies* (Mendlesohn 2014, Fiske 1992), in which social status is connected to expertise – not just in the genre, but in any specialised subject. At such science fiction conventions, presentations and discussions on cutting-edge science or medieval history would be just as appreciated as ones on Ray Bradbury's narrative techniques, J.R.R. Tolkien's mythologies, or about recently developed subgenres such as solarpunk. This positioning of fans as passionate experts is also reflected in that the genre's most respected awards, The Hugos, are voted on by membership holders of the foremost annual convention of organised fandom, Worldcon.

2.3.3 From non-profit to for-profit convention culture

In contrast to the deep tradition of fan-as-expert stands another type of media fandom, positioned as a somewhat more empowered consumer identity. Especially since the 1990s, with its speculation-driven boom in supposedly collectible comic books, the normalisation of digital gaming, and the mainstreaming of geek cultures that fuelled e.g. superhero films, the geek consumer market has become significant. The most engaged fans increasingly viewed as influential tastemakers for a wider population (Fiske 1992, Jenkins 2006a).

From the media industry perspective, engaging with, rewarding, or manipulating fan audiences has become an important part of the marketing of IP-based content on any platform or format. This is a normalisation of what was first called "transmedia storytelling" – multi-platform works relying on exploiting or re-envisioning fandom's traditional consumption and production practices (see Jenkins, 2006a, 2006b, 2007). Even as fan engagement has become central to contemporary business models, fan creativity remains a source of tension for major IP rights-holders. Attempts to curtail it

having proved inefficient, the contemporary strategy is to direct it onto brand-controlled online platforms.

Fandom convention cultures spread and diverged from literary sci-fi fandom to a great many other popular subcultures, giving us comic book conventions, wargaming conventions, role-playing conventions, anime conventions, cosplay conventions and so on. While non-profit, volunteer-produced convention cultures exist in all these spaces, an alternative strand of commercially produced events appeared early on, initiated by for instance publishing companies, and boosted by the emergence of a business model for paid-for appearances by celebrities or cult figures with fandom appeal. This kind of commercial fandom convention also proved a natural partner for fan-oriented marketing necessitated by the industry changes referred to above.

As a result, the most visible and best-known fandom conventions in this millennium have been of the commercial kind, with San Diego Comic Con (1970-) and its offshoots in other localities the best-known examples. Although it is tens of times larger, Comic Con is not structurally dissimilar to non-profit conventions. It does however prioritise the sales floor (expo area), and the talks, panels, and shows put great emphasis on programming related to previewing, or otherwise building advance goodwill for, upcoming productions among core audience demographics.

In contrast to non-profit fandom conventions with their focus on event co-creation, knowledge and participant creativity, the commercial convention centres consumer activities like *purchasing memorabilia*, *paying to meet or be in the presence of genre celebrity*, and *gaining access to artificially scarce information* related to commercial IP. Even in a such a consumerist environment, however, convention research suggests participants experience the gathered community of fans as central to their experience (Lamerichs 2015, Terraferma et al. 2025).

The logical next step has been for brands to take control of such events themselves. Fans do understand that brand-controlled conventions like Disney's D23 (2009-) and Star Wars Celebration (1999-) are marketing events, but this does not preclude having personally meaningful participant experiences. Especially smaller brand-controlled events, like the Icelandic EVE Fanfest (2004, for committed players of EVE Online), the British Games Day (1975-2013) of British miniature war gaming giant Games Workshop, may also intentionally include community-building or co-creative elements modelled on participatory non-profit conventions.

Brand-focused events may also be position themselves as supporting game cultures of some aspect of it beyond their short-term commercial interests. For instance, Swedish game publisher Fria Ligan's Spelkongress (2023-) resurrected the name of an event hosted by dominant role-playing game publisher Äventyrsspel (at least 1986-1992). Inviting other Swedish game publishers to its trade hall, the event can support the contemporary Swedish analogue game industry while emphasising the central position of Fria Ligan within it. As commercial fandom events are designed to create visibility for IP and attract as many participants as possible, they are often covered in the media, while non-profit events may be entirely unknown outside the participant communities even in countries where they are very popular.

Academic research on conventions, very limited overall, similarly tends to be focused either on the most visible commercial type or to prioritise "media" fandoms of genre TV and film. Non-profit

conventions, especially or at a smaller scale or in fields like analogue games and literature with relatively limited economic impact, are almost invisible in the research.

In the research, conventions as producers of shared community experiences – as community festivals – are relatively well understood. Less well documented is the function especially of non-profit conventions as contexts for the production of expertise on their subject-matter, and as necessary nodes in wider fandom knowledge practices of aesthetic analysis and criticism, theory-building, para-academic publishing and documentation, the nurturing of artists and academics, and ultimately of contributing to the legitimising of their subject matter in the wider culture.

2.3.4. Early role-playing history viewed through fandom and conventions

The invention of role-playing games as a medium is understood to be a consequence of character-play gradually emerging within wargaming communities; players of these kinds of games had previously played with armies or squadrons rather than portraying individuals. Upon its release in 1974, *Dungeons & Dragons* was understood and positioned as a kind of tactical wargame. The word “role-playing”, already in contemporaneous use for activities like strategic simulation and psychodrama, was attached to the game by its players. By the next edition, the authors had also adopted the term “role-playing game”.²

The emergence of live role-playing games in the late 1970s is typically explained as a following from the popularity of tabletop role-playing. It seems that in most places tabletop role-playing games were played, larp would also be “invented” as players decided to dress up as their characters, speak their words, and physically represent their actions.

Surprisingly, our first review of histories and contemporary sources focused on fandom and conventions suggests the story may just as well be told the other way around. The introduction of character play to wargaming itself occurred in many places at approximately the same time. Who should be credited with the invention of role-playing games is a complex question; part of the reason for this may be that it occurred in a cultural context where adults playfully embodying fantasy characters was already common. Just like “role-playing” as a cultural concept predates role-playing games, it seems likely that “live role-playing” was not so much an inevitable consequence of the popularity of tabletop role-playing as an adaptation and reframing of contemporary, already subculturally acceptable adult play practices – which themselves predated *Dungeons & Dragons*.

In the mid-1960s, as a folk-culture revival was peaking and the works of J.R.R. Tolkien made an enormous impact on US counterculture, science fiction fandom begets Tolkien Societies as their own, independent fandom movement. In California, fans also experiment with text-based shared fantasy role-play and invent the Society for Creative Anachronism, at the precise moment that Renaissance Faires also emerge in Los Angeles. All of these movements will spread rapidly across the US, including to Wisconsin, where the creators of *Dungeons & Dragons* are based.

Dress-up and character-play activities such as masquerades had been part of the science fiction convention format since the 1930s. Costumes inspired by the worlds of J.R.R. Tolkien were worn at Worldcons from at least 1958, and a first Tolkien fan organisation was founded by one Ted

² A detailed pre- and early history of role-playing games, and of the emergence of the term “role-playing game”, can be found in Jon Peterson’s work (2012; 2020).

Johnstone at the 1960 event. While that one did not last, the Tolkien Society of America, constituted in 1965, would provide the international model for national Tolkien clubs with local chapters (smials). The Mythopoeic society, a rival Los Angeles association engaged with the Inklings (a fantasy-literary group of which Tolkien was part) was founded in 1967. Its first event was a Hobbit birthday celebration.

The two Tolkien fandom organisations would merge in 1972. Both were already notable for combining fan production and dress-up activities with an academic focus: the Tolkien Society organised academic conferences rather than conventions, and the Mythopoeic society's fanzine, *Mythlore* (1969-), would become a peer-reviewed academic journal in 1999. Similarly, the UK Tolkien Society (1969-) now styles itself as an educational charity and literary society.³

Ted Johnstone, the founder of the very first US Tolkien club in 1960, was at that time among his many other fannish activities also an active participant in a game-world called *Coventry*. In the late 1950s, sci-fi fans in Pasadena inherited a local game experiment, injecting the basic idea of a shared storytelling world with science fiction and fantasy elements. Coventry was a storyworld that participants could inhabit as a character; stories played out through writing and sharing them (what would today be considered a form of *text-based role-playing*). Story developments were discussed collectively, and advancing through the game required "service credits", earned through writing or other volunteer work for the project. Johnstone published one of the Coventry fanzines and became key to the game's spread through fandom in California and further afield (Coventry, n.d.); he also seems to have been involved in the undocumented social conflicts that brought about its end in early 60s. Johnstone, a science fiction writer, was also involved in wargaming and moved on to run of the first Diplomacy-by-mail-fanzines.

The Society for Creative Anachronism (SCA) was founded in 1966 in Berkeley, California. Its playful medievalism of the grew out of its roots in the backyard party of medieval studies graduate and her friends. The association was likely inspired by historical re-enactment and living history, which have independent traditions across the world, and had long been popular in the US. When Berkley hosted Worldcon two years later, a handbook for starting one's own SCA chapter was released at the event, and by the end of the 1969, the organisation had spread across the US. Today it is chartered in the US as a non-profit educational corporation and has tens of thousands of active members around the world.

Among the founders of the SCA was Steve Perrin, who would create an alternative set of combat rules for *D&D* in 1976, and eventually created the influential role-playing game *RuneQuest* (1978) (Appelcline 2014, p. 250). In 1975, SCA-members at UC San Diego developed a game system based on *D&D* but influenced by their interest in medieval history and practical experience of historical combat; it would eventually evolve into independent RPG publisher Midkemia Press (ibid p. 337-8).⁴

³ Europe's first Tolkien society was the Swedish Tolkien Society started in 1968, although it was soon superceded by the Tolkien Society Forodrim (1972-). Both grew out of the strong local fandom; the first on Sweden's west coast from the country's oldest fandom organisation Club Cosmos (1954-), the second in Stockholm, where Forodrim still offers a range of social and education activities centred on Tolkien's fantasy world and those of others. Members still often dress up and interact somewhat in character at events.

⁴ The university gaming group included Raymond Feist, who would go on to write an influential series of fantasy novels based on the Midkemia world.

Influential game designer Steve Jackson joined the SCA as research for his 1977 game *Melee*, (ibid 2014, p. 218).

California was also the birthplace in 1963 of the Renaissance Faire phenomena, with many similarities to the SCA when it comes to dressing up and educational ambitions, but open to the public and at a larger scale of up to tens of thousands of visitors. Medievalism was at the time not progressively coded. Although Renaissance Faires grew out of an educational initiative, their playful and irreverent atmosphere created a temporary refuge from the strictures of 1950s US middle class propriety, not least for women and sexual minorities. Many of the 500 volunteers who first Renaissance Faire were available because they had been affected by Hollywood blacklisting during the so-called communist witch hunts; it was organised as a fundraiser for a left-wing and pacifist local radio channel (Rubin 2012).

In the early 1960s environment, the rapidly popular and spreading Renaissance Faires offered a space of social and cultural freedoms and would attract censure from conservative action groups. They are understood to have contributed to the development of hippie culture, provided key early performance opportunities for folk and rock musicians (and later the New Vaudeville movement), and partly inspired the modern music festival that would emerge during the decade with events like Woodstock (Rubin 2012).

Renaissance Faires spread to other states in the late 1960s and early 1970, including Wisconsin where *D&D* creators Gygax and Arneson were based, and would explode in popularity during the 1980s. Today there are about 250 active Renaissance Faires in North America (Rubin 2012). Variants of the format eventually reached Europe, combining with and shaped by both fantasy fandom activities as well as local living history activations.

This brief overview shows that the emergence of wargaming variants centred on the portrayal of individual combat characters – in settings coloured by mid-century American popular culture medievalism – happened in a subcultural environment where embodying similar characters in both combat and non-combat situations was already common. While further research is clearly required, this observation challenges the narrative of live role-playing as sprung exclusively from tabletop role-playing cultures. It seems likely that the embodied character-play already present in the culture strengthened interest in similar aspects of existing wargames and inspired the development of new ones. Table-top role-playing games would then in turn have provided new approaches to structuring the embodied character dress-up play that was ambiently present in other formats.

2.4 History of the Role-Playing Convention

2.4.1 Emergence of the role-playing convention

The history of tabletop role-playing games as a medium is intertwined with the history of role-playing conventions. Gary Gygax and Dave Arneson, the creators of the first commercial table-top role-playing game, *Dungeons & Dragons* (1974), first met at Gen Con. This Lake Geneva, Wisconsin, wargaming convention had been founded by Gygax in 1968, specifically emulating the gathering places of the science fiction fans for his own community⁵. Small events for wargamers had been

⁵ Science fiction fandom and gaming communities were perhaps not entirely separate at this time. A key channel for spreading information about role-playing games were newsletters and zines published by the

organised locally before, in the style of private events (Peterson 2012, 9-10), but as Gygax recalled almost 40 years later, his idea for a club event was to do a “convention, the way that science fiction people have conventions” (Laws 2007, 10).

With the competitive playing of wargames and board games as central activities, Gen Con could have been modelled on for instance sports events or chess tournaments. Inspired by science fiction conventions, the event instead emphasised socialising and community, invited a few relevant shops to create a small trade hall, and included film exhibitions, talks, guests of honour, and performances on the programme (Laws 2007; Peterson 2012). The first Gen Con lasted only a day and had just under a hundred participants (Peterson 2012, 11). It became an annual event and is currently the largest tabletop game convention in North America with over 72,000 unique participants in 2025.

The core audience of wargamers was interested in military history, some because of personal military experience, but whether because of overlapping social circles or the familiarity of the format, GenCon soon started attracting science fiction and fantasy lovers too (see also Peterson 2012, 460-461, 487-494). After its 1974 release, *Dungeons & Dragons* fast became the most popular game at the convention. As had been the case on a much smaller scale with *Coventry* in LA fandom in the 1960s, enough sci-fi fans engaged so passionately with the new game to necessitate creating specific fanzines across the country to discuss it. One apazine founded in 1975 by Lee Gold, *Alarums and Excursions*, would continue until 2025 when the eyesight of its by then aging editor failed (Meints 2025). D&D and its followers were played at science fiction conventions, but as the emerging role-playing subculture attracted members from contexts, the need for role-playing events also increased.⁶

After Gen Con showed the way, local game conventions started popping up around the United States, as well as internationally. Another long-running and influential US game convention, **Origins International Game Expo**, was established in Baltimore, Maryland, in 1975 (Peterson 2012, 522; Origins50 n.d.). Founded by the locally based wargame company Avalon Hill, Origins from the start had a stronger commercial component than Gen Con. Origins too was started out as a wargaming and soon embraced *Dungeons & Dragons* and other games. The conventions would first travel around the United States, often produced in collaboration with local conventions (on a similar model to sci-fi fandom’s Worldcon). It settled in Ohio in the mid 1990s.

Wargaming and roleplaying conventions rapidly spread abroad. Fandom and the gaming hobby had long been print cultures, whose communities and networking were built around amateur press associations and correspondence. Joining a club for one’s hobby in person was not possible everywhere but travelling to one or a few annual conventions might be within reach – or otherwise to be inspired to organise one’s own. This dynamic was not significantly different for fans or gamers in Europe than in e.g. the rural US.

various science fiction fandom clubs and wargaming groups. At the time many zines were called APAs (standing for amateur press association) or apazines. These zines have been a key historical source in piecing together the early years of role-playing games (see Peterson 2012; 2020).

⁶ The history of character play is complicated – and again sci-fi fandom plays a part – but it clearly influenced this form of playing being identified as role-playing. For pre and early history of role-playing games, and the emergence of the term “role-playing game”, see Jon Peterson’s work (2012; 2020).

The history of the emergence and spread of larp festivals and conventions in the US (and UK) offered in this chapter is only a partial sketch, a starting point for building a more comprehensive picture of the field. We have not had the possibility to dive into such histories in specific countries in Europe even if we are aware that festivals and conventions can be found around the continent. We look forward to expanding our knowledge on the topic in the future and invite others to document their local histories in accessible manner. Here we limit ourselves to mapping the origins of larp conventions and festivals in the US, where they originate, and to the Nordic context which is most relevant to our research focus.

2.4.2 Role-playing conventions arrive in the Nordics

In the Nordic countries, both wargamers and science fiction fans read fanzines. One of the first documented role-players in Sweden was the teenage Michael Börjesson, who had ordered *Dungeons & Dragons* from the US after reading about the game in a science fiction zine *Supernova* in 1975 (Seter 2024, 17-18). He would later demonstrate *D&D* at a new wargaming convention in Gothenburg, **Konvent '77**.

This convention too became an annual event, changing its name to **GothCon** in 1980, and still attracts a few thousand participants each year. GothCon is the longest-running still extant Nordic game convention, if not by much; the Danish **Viking-Con** has run annually since 1982, still attracting about 900 full-weekend participants (Viking-con n.d.). Like most Nordic game conventions, they are non-profit events produced entirely by volunteers. While this in line with the traditions of organised fandom, it was also the obvious choice of organisational structure. As Magnus Seter (2004) observes in his history of Swedish role-playing, early role-players often had “a foot in each of these camps: war games, Tolkien enthusiasts, and a youth association.” (p.19).

The unusual impact and vitality of Nordic role-playing game cultures since the 1980s is built on these non-profit associations, events, and their participant communities. Historically, Nordic public sectors have supported civic infrastructure and specifically participation in democratically organised, registered non-profit associations. Funding has often been directly available, especially for activities for young people, incentivising them to organise as non-profit associations.

Gothenburg had had a strong gaming association culture since the 1970s, a fact that may well have been connected to GothCon. Whether GothCon created association culture or the association culture created GothCon, it was in Gothenburg that the idea of role-playing organisation was born. (Brodén 2009, p. 35)

Gaming clubs in western Sweden organised in 1985. Southern Sweden followed in 1987, on the initiative of Christer “Chrip” Pettersson, who was active in Unga Forskare, a national federation for youth clubs engaged in STEM education. When a national gaming organisation, was founded late that same year, the constituting meeting was held at the Stockholm offices of Unga Forskare (Brodén 2009, p. 35). It was named Sverok, short for “Sveriges Roll- och konfliktspelsförbund” – the Swedish role-playing and wargaming association; in other words, “the kinds of games that were played at conventions.” (Brodén 2009).

Sverok would go on to become one of the biggest youth organisations (comparable to football and scouting), and the only one run entirely by the under-26-year-olds themselves. A central federation was useful for receiving and distributing state funding but also gave Sverok a significant public voice

in speaking for the movement, and the capacity to for instance offer training programmes in managing non-profits, and extra support for projects such as conventions (Brodén 2009).

Finland came to convention culture later than its Scandinavian neighbours, but here too, fandom culture played a part in the spread of role-playing games. The country's first commercial distributor of role-playing games, Lauri Tudeer – who had come across the medium as an exchange student in the US – resorted to marketing his wares in science fiction magazines (Mäyrä 2003).

2.4.3. Larp conventions and larp festivals appear

At Gen Con, larp-like live gaming activities, such as *Killer the Game of Assassination*, had a presence early on, but would soon become discouraged. As well as putting complex and sensitive boardgame setups at risk, and disturbing or annoying non-participants, running around with gun props was a legal liability. At the end of the decade, it also became a reputational liability.

The much-publicised 1980 death of James Dallas Egbert, erroneously attributed to playing role-playing games, triggered in the US a moral panic that would also spread internationally (see Laycock 2015). Concern narratives explicitly connected risk behaviours to dressing up in a costume and physically performing character actions, such as casting spells. When it became politically expedient to underline that role-playing games were not like that, embodied and dressed-up role-play was outlawed at Gen Con. The policy would stay in place until the breakthrough and huge popularity of Vampire larp in the 1990s (Laws 2007).

The early history of larp cultures is poorly documented in general; cultural practices beyond the gameplay itself especially so. In the US Northeast, some of the earliest larps are known to have been multi-day or even week-long events. They were organized by still-extant groups associated with universities, such as the MIT Assassins' Guild and the Society for Interactive Literature (SIL) at Harvard. Nat Budin (2012) identifies the staging of *Rekon-1* at science fiction convention **Boskone XX** in 1983 as a turning point for larps in the convention setting. *Rekon-1* has been described as the first “theatre style” larp⁷. It also spanned sequels and SIL ultimately moved from running larp at the sci-fi conventions to launching **SILicon**, their own convention dedicated to larp (Harviainen et al 2018).

SILicon launched in Massachusetts in 1986 and was structured from the start in the style of an arts festival, celebrating original work. Although shorter form larps with a runtime of some 4-5 hours intended for convention play had emerged, the festival originally programmed several weekend-long larps in parallel. During the 1990s, shorter theatre-style larps would gradually come to predominate at the festival, which under its later name **Intercon** remains an influential stage for short-form work (Budin 2012).⁸

⁷ In the US context, ‘theatre style’ larp is typically understood as limited in size (a room rather than e.g. an outdoor site) and duration (hours rather than a multi-day event), with players playing a single character (rather than also taking shifts playing e.g. antagonist characters), and focused on conversation (rather than combat). When theatre style larps are played at conventions, sets and costumes can be symbolic or even entirely optional.

⁸ With “live-roleplaying” as a concept spreading much faster than information about specific play practices, numerous local, regional, and national styles emerged. Although most used the same word for the activity, they had significant differences in format, play cultures, and fundamental assumptions. There are very few contemporary descriptions of the specifics of early larp. Understanding one’s own culture or design tradition from within is very difficult, especially if there are no clear points of comparison, and many early larp

With earlier controversies largely forgotten, larps also returned to many game and fan conventions, of which they are still an expected and unremarkable part. The standardized duration of short form convention larps had made scheduling them simpler. As more larps were specifically designed to be played in hotel rooms or conference rooms, it also meant the gameplay was contained and would not affect or even be visible to rest of the convention.

A complete history of larp festivals in the United States is far beyond our scope but would make for interesting reading. Impactful US-based larp festivals and conventions worth studying include at least **Be-Con**, **Dreamation**, **DEXCON**, **Metatopia**, **Living Games**, **Big Bad Con**, and **OwlCon**, as well as **Wyrd Con**, a west coast convention whose documentation and publications we have partially relied on for this overview (e.g. Budin 2015, 2021).

Where we have been able to find sources, it appears larp conventions in general emerge later in Europe than in the United States. In the United Kingdom, larp festivals go back to at least 1992, when two still-operating festivals first started: **Dropzone**, specializing in laser-tag larp, and **Convulsion** (using the name **Continuum** since 2003). Several others of the approximately ten other UK larp festivals that have appeared since then also remain active. (Holkar 2025⁹.¹⁰)

As festival-style larp conventions often become centres for specific formats or aesthetics – whether of larps or of convention-making itself – they may attract participants interested in that specific style from far afield. As is typical for convention cultures, some percentage of particularly engaged community members will also travel internationally to significant events. Many of them are convention makers, who in addition to the participant experience are looking to learn from each other, network, or even volunteer on each other's teams. As just one example, one of the newer UK festivals, **Consequence** (2007-) draws heavily on the model of Intercon, to the point of using the same larp-participation booking management software (M. Holkar, personal communication).

2.4.4. Larp conventions and larp festivals reach the Nordics

As larping typically emerged in social contexts where tabletop role-playing was already present, the style was often represented or practiced at gaming conventions in general. In Denmark, larps were run at Fastaval from the very beginning (see discussion in 2.5.5), as well as being a centre for an emerging, arguably very larp-like role-playing style (see section 2.4.5).

In Finland, the very first email about organizing the gaming convention Ropecon did mention including larp in the event, although it did not happen until the second Ropecon in 1995. In the

communities also assumed others were doing the same kind of thing. What is considered a “normal larp” still varies hugely around the globe and even within individual countries or US states. For example, larps based on published rulebooks of *Vampire: The Masquerade* and *Mind's Eye Theatre* form one set of normative traditions in US larp; campaign-style boffer events in different genres another; while the so-called “Secrets and Powers” style has been highlighted as central to Intercon communities (see Budin 2015). Each of these traditional styles obviously include a lot of variety in turn.

¹⁰ There is also a genre of larp called “festival larps”. This form, popular in at least UK and Germany, refers to larps that are exceptionally large, accommodating possibly over a thousand players, with competing factions of players (Brind et al. 2018, 193). Festival larps have plots that can be sought out, feature politicking and trade, and tend to be set in fantasy worlds (Harviainen et al. 2018, 96). These larps are not included in our conceptualization of larp festivals and conventions and fall outside the scope of the research project.

meantime, an event called **Larpcon** (1994) had been organized in Hämeenlinna in conjunction with a fantasy larp, *Nordarak X* (Talvitie 2009; Koponen 2015).

The event brought together two hundred larpers, and the national association of live action role-players (SuoLi) was founded at the event, marking the beginning of a rapid growth period for larp in Finland. Larpcon itself did not continue, likely because of the growth of Ropecon, and an abundance both of games and non-game social activities for the player communities in question.

In Sweden, a national larp convention called **Prolog**, featuring short form larps as well as presentations, workshops, and discussions, started in 2009. Norway's **Spillerom**, a similar event, started in 2014.

In Denmark, a national larp association, Landsforeningen for Levende Rollespil (LLR), was founded in 2003. Forum, a national conference for its member organisations, started in 2008. Over time however, LLR – now Landsforeningen Bifrost – has expanded into an umbrella organisation for a range of creative and participatory youth hobbies. In addition to larp, Bifrost member associations cover tabletop role-playing, board gaming and wargaming, cosplay and anime/manga fandom, and to some degree re-enactors and military simulation hobby, which is also reflected in the Forum programme.

2.4.5. Specialised festivals for short form larp

The Nordic short form larp in its current format – and the larp festivals where they are showcased – emerged in around 2005-2010, influenced in part by international convention larps, but also drawing significant inspiration from the freeform role-playing format (a hybrid between tabletop role-playing games and larp with strong use of metatechniques).

This development is complicated, as it is tied to a shift in the meaning of the label 'larp' in the Nordics. The term was long understood to mostly include a kind of complex, immersive, day-long or even multi-day role-playing event that it is not practical to produce in a festival context. In for instance the United States, fully embodied role-playing in which one moved around often seem to have been understood as a kind of larp even when no costuming was involved and the physical environment was not directly representing that of the fiction (e.g. using a classroom or conference room, without set dressing, to represent a spaceship or castle). In Europe, the same formats were often viewed as variants of tabletop role-playing instead (see discussion in 2.5.5).

In the Nordics, the definition of larp expanded only gradually, and did not include this kind of free form role-playing until around 2010. This happened in part thanks to increasing overlap and exchange between designer communities such as traditional larp makers and the Danish "scenario designers" centred on the Fastaval (1986-) convention, and in part because of increasing interaction with play cultures, such as those in the US and the Czech, with strong chamber larp traditions.

The emergence of blackbox larp, not least through the inspiration provided by the Danish film *Dogville* (2003) which featured minimalist staging, and the enormous influence of larp makers like Nina Runa Essendrop on a new generation of designers, was another significant turning point (see Nielsen 2015).

The week-long international Larpwriter Summer School programme (2012-2016) was a particularly strong vector for the influence of both. The design approaches taught in the programme were

applicable to any kind of larp, but by logistical necessity, only shorter larps could fit on the curriculum as examples. Many of the students who sought the programme out did so because they had no local larp community from which to learn. For this new generation of designers, internationally oriented from the start, short form larps were what was it possible to produce, and blackbox larp an aesthetic gold standard.

Larp showcases more reminiscent of art festivals were created to accommodate this shorter format can be traced back to the Swedish **Höjdpunkt** (2008) a one-time event intended to raise awareness locally of international freeform and chamber larp scenario culture (Huss, 2008). The many chamber larp and blackbox festivals that followed had international audiences and in effect became a kind of circuit for designers to tour influential work. They included Norway's Grenselandet (2010-), the German It's Full of Larps (2011-), the Danish Blackbox CPH (2012-), and the Stockholm Scenario Festival in Sweden (2012-). Numerous other festivals joined later, produced in different styles, but typically structured around two 4–5-hour larp slots a day. Where one had previously often had to travel for a larp, often to a secluded site, larp festivals staged in large cities made lower-threshold participation possible¹¹.

All of this contributed to an emergence of a new larp format and a flourishing in Northern and Central Europe of larp festivals with the form and feel of arts festivals (typically at venues with at least one theatre blackbox) at which multiple larps are staged and played.

2.5. Rethinking festivals and conventions

2.5.1. Conventions as cultural festivals

The previous section traced role-playing and larp conventions in relation to the fandom conventions, which are their precursor, remain an influence, and which sometimes overlap (e.g. when fandom conventions include role-playing sections or larps).

The many interesting implications of this glancing historical discussion cannot be fully covered here. Even as a form of stand-alone event, the convention has not been theorised, and we hope to contribute to the foundations of such work in future academic publications. Although a full exploration of the convention's functions and wider financial and cultural context is out of scope for the research project, a welcome if unexpected outcome of this Work Package will be a formal exploration of themes and perspectives preliminarily sketched out below.

Within the communities we study, usage of the term "larp festival" tends to be limited to e.g. blackbox festivals, which have clear, formal similarities to theatre festivals and other specialised art showcases. Likely, these events are also influenced by them: we have preliminarily observed that many organisers of such events are specifically also parts of artist communities. In the previous section, we also showed that short-form larp festivals are connected to role-playing conventions through their histories as well as direct lines of influence. Below, the point at which any convention turns into a festival is discussed.

¹¹ Larp festivals started very late in Finland. While larps had appeared as parts of other festivals (Ropecon, some art festivals, and even the 2017 Worldcon in Helsinki), a festival fully devoted to showcasing larps did not appear until 2023, when Stoori launched in the capital region. Immersion started the following year in 2024 in Turku.

On a general level, all gaming conventions at which playing games is a central activity are arts and culture festivals in the sense that they centre and celebrate the work. Since underground and nonprofessional arts festivals are organised through similar volunteer and nonprofit communities to those of role-playing, makes it difficult to draw any specific boundary beyond which a 'convention' would turn into a 'festival'.

One meaningful distinction to consider could be about the thresholds for participation. Even though showcases targeted exclusively at practitioners exist, art festivals in general do tend to be directed towards audiences, whether consisting of knowledgeable enthusiasts, casual consumers, or curious passers-by. Whatever the position of the audience member to begin with, one implicit aim of any curated festival or participatory convention will be to deepen their engagement with the cultural expression at hand. Becoming more engaged may involve e.g. becoming better oriented about current artists, works, or trends; learning about local opportunities for consuming works or for participating in their making or promotion; or developing one's skills, whether through dropping in on a beginner-friendly workshop, or attending a masterclass with a visiting expert.

In this sense, even festivals that are non-commercial represent marketing opportunities for media, artforms, or movements. Even blackbox and chamber larp festivals, whose audience size is limited by the number of players in each programmed larp, often position themselves as beginner-friendly or try to appeal to specific new target audiences. As an example, the Finnish larp festival Immersion, while appealing to existing audiences for serious or experimental short form larp, also attempts to expand interest within the theatre community to the larp medium.

Sorting conventions and festivals based on their appeal to the general audience reveals that the very largest non-profit conventions can turn into cultural festivals. The Finnish cultural context, in which subcultural expressions are relatively normalised, provides two particularly interesting examples.

The role-playing convention Ropecon (1994-), started by a technical university role-play club, was originally inspired by gaming conventions abroad and by the local science fiction conference Finncon (1986-). The first Ropecon gathered 700 participants, welcoming players of tabletop role-playing games, miniature wargames, board games, and collectible card games (Talvela 2018). It has since grown into the largest non-profit gaming convention in Northern Europe. In 2025, it had 10,400 participants (E. Maeda, personal communication 6 Jan 2026). Of these, 1613 were volunteers, whether on the organising committee or doing at least one 8-hour volunteer staff shift during the event (Ropecon 2025). Regardless of its name ("Rope" from Finnish 'roolipeli', role-playing game, and "con" for convention), its history, and its typical gaming convention programming, Ropecon also increasingly functions as a cultural festival.

Thanks to decades of systematic media outreach, Ropecon has long been covered by national news media similarly to any major subcultural festival, which in the Finnish context means that it is covered seriously. General-interest reporting, e.g. on national news broadcasts, may still take a (largely benevolent) human-interest perspective on sub-cultural expression. On the other hand, culture coverage of major news media can be expected to report on significant game releases coinciding with the convention or to interview particularly interesting guests of honour or award winners.

Over time, awareness of the event has grown, and people with even a passing interest in any of the many genres and expressions the event engages with may consider a visit to the convention centre. Special family tickets are also available. No matter how casual the visitor's intentions, the convention offers endless ways of engaging deeper, whether in activities on site, or later through in any of countless clubs, associations, public libraries and other stakeholders presenting their activities connected to games and game-cultural creativity.

A similar role to Ropecon in the non-gaming fandom context is played by the comics convention **Tampere Kuplii** (2007-), a nonprofit "feelgood comics festival for everyone interested in comics and graphic novels". Produced entirely by volunteers, the event is free of charge and attracted 24,782 visitors in 2025 (Tampere kuplii, 2025).¹² This makes it a significant event in the comics space even at the European scale, demonstrating the vital role non-profit conventions and their communities play in supporting fields of cultural production that the commercial marketplace cannot or will not support.

2.5.2. Convention cultures in the cultural ecosystem

Understanding conventions as cultural festivals permits us to read them comparatively with other cultural fields. As their role in the cultural ecosystems have not been directly studied, we are limited to conjecture about the dynamics of these limited markets. It does however seem reasonable to think of their role as similar to that played by arthouse film festivals within the grand ecosystems of cinema and filmed entertainment.

Film as a medium, including the billion-dollar grossers of commercial entertainment, relies for its sustainability on artistic innovation and the emergence of new voices. With the commercial marketplace unable or unwilling to support niche or experimental development, work to that end occurs elsewhere in the ecosystem. One key role is played by the global system of film festivals, a focal point for the engagement of professionals, experts, and enthusiasts. It seems likely, although at this stage of the research this necessarily conjecture, that networks of non-profit conventions are a similar linchpin for the artistic development of fields like role-playing games, comic books, board games, and genre literature – and therefore also for the continuing survival of independent publishing in these fields.

The most prestigious film festivals – Cannes, Venice, Berlin, Toronto, and Sundance – are focused on the development and celebration of the artform¹³. Some of these "A-festivals" are indeed open only or mainly for film professionals rather than public audiences. In the role-playing space, certain conventions and their communities play a similar role in the development of aesthetic theories and canons, even though their attendance may be relatively small. In both cases, the work of developing and understanding an artform can only have meaning as part of a wider network of events showcasing or promoting work to wider audiences. In the case of film festivals and fan conventions alike, this involves balancing niche and specialised interests with wide appeal and making space for both artistic and commercial concerns.

¹² Note that there is significant variance in how different festivals calculate the number of their participants. Comparisons are tricky.

¹³ While the same festivals often coincide with or contain distributions rights markets for commercial film, this aspect of them is typically only reported on in trade media, while the artistic competitions receive mainstream media attention.

At the very least we must consider the possibility that even though non-profit conventions of this kind are largely illegible to society, invisible in cultural discourse, and overlooked in academic study, this may not reflect their actual cultural importance. The situation is a product of the low cultural status of these media and genres, of their subcultural history, and of their relatively small financial footprint (which, as with arthouse cinema, is negligible only if there is no creative relationship between the avant-garde and the commercial mainstream in film, games, and other media).

2.5.3. Non-profit conventions as cultural institutions

Some non-profit conventions have reached a scale where their impacts – cultural and sometimes economic – are legible to wider society. For instance, the significance of Worldcon and its influential Hugo awards has become legible when the process around their selection has been tampered with or challenged (e.g. Schaub 2015; Gennis & Polo 2024).

In the light of the discussion in this chapter, we increasingly lean towards the view that many established non-profit conventions, including the volunteering communities that sustain them, should be viewed not as arenas for leisure activities but as a distinct type of cultural institution. They do not just offer social meeting places for the shared enjoyment for some media type or artform, but work for the preservation, promotion, and advancement of culture, offering sites for learning, reflection, identity building, and artistic co-creation.

A subset of them, such as the larp convention Knutepunkt or the literary science fiction fandom centred around Worldcon, are additionally nodes for discourse communities engage in systematic knowledge work, which over time has played a significant role in legitimising their sub-culturally coded subject areas within mainstream and elite cultures. Over time, cultural interest and even cachet attaches itself to this type of event, resulting on the one hand in increased stability as participating or event volunteering is viewed as legitimate and valuable for professional careers in related fields. On the other, any institutional role brings with it related challenges of maintaining relevance in a developing field; the difficulty of continuing to attract younger or non-expert groups of participants; and a risk of perceived or actual power concentration to the organisations or to high-status individuals within it.

None of this necessarily implies that convention organisers themselves necessarily view their events as institutions or reflect on their work in terms of cultural or social power. Our preliminary work on larp festival organisers suggests they primarily focus on the quality of the programme, the experience of the participants, the accessibility of the event, on creating a space for fun and community, as well as for learning and reflection. Even so there seems to be some awareness that the effects of these events extend beyond integrating the participant community and presenting new larps. Larp festivals specifically have an impact on their participants and organizers, and through them on larp cultures and traditions, as well as on related fields from which practitioners or experts are pulled to larp events through their cachet or some personal connection. To a lesser extent, or at least on one more difficult to document, the events may also affect culture and society more widely.

To support this analysis, the next section provides an overview of what is created, enabled, or produced through the existence of these primarily non-profit and volunteer-produced conventions and related types of events. This analysis is followed by two case studies of individual festivals.

2.5.4. What larp festivals and conventions produce

Creating, presenting, and curating works. Larp festivals are a site where larps are staged (or “run” as a larp’s production, facilitation, and play is often called). Larps run at festivals are often facilitated by the designer or design team themselves. They can include world premieres or current selections but also catalogue titles or retrospective selections, or even playtests of unfinished larps. Many festivals curate their selection from interesting new larps that have premiered during the previous year, making available to a local audience work that may have been created in other countries. Most festivals also feature new works from the local community, creating motivation and sometimes support structures for creating new scenarios, as there is an opportunity to share the work with an audience at a specific date. Tickets and travel for larpmakers presenting works can be covered or subsidised, in effect making it possible to tour a participatory artwork internationally within this largely non-profit environment.

Some festivals invite works based on specific themes or guidelines (Make a Scene Festival) while others can provide coaching in scenario creation by seasoned designers (Fastaval). There are also festivals who actively bring back older works, giving players opportunities to experience classic works that may not have been available to play in years or decades (Immersion, Fastaval). These structures of staging, inviting, and especially touring and reviving larps contribute over time to the *development of a canon* and to *growing the artistic influence and audience of individual larp designers*.

Acquiring, disseminating, and reflecting on skills and knowledge. Larp festivals are a site where people teach each other about designing, running, playing, and understanding larps. Such program can take the form, for example, of a lecture or a workshop, a panel discussion or a crafting session, but festivals also provide opportunities for informal discussions and reflection. Interestingly, while most programme relates to larp, since larp can be about anything, festivals can engage participant on almost any subject matter. For example, lectures on medieval clothing, the hypothetical biology of fictional species, or best practices in social media marketing can easily fit at a larp festival, as can workshops on dances of a specific period, confident public speaking, or light and sound design. The wide range of suitable topics is another feature shared with science fiction conventions.

Artistic development and analytic expertise. Continuing from spreading skills and knowledge, larp festivals and conventions also produce new understanding of the medium. They are the place where the creators, players, critics, and scholars of larp come to push their thinking and practice, to see where the community is, and hear about cutting-edge artistic development and theory. At the leading larp festivals, the current state of a larp tradition is present, and its future can be glimpsed. Knowledge-producing conventions and their communities also incentivise or directly produce e.g. books, journals, magazines, web fora, and archives relating to their field.

Festival production and participation. Any larp festival also offers a site to practice and transfer skills in related to event organisation and related fields. The teaching of event production or convention- or festival-specific skills can be explicit, with lectures or workshops for participants, or through formal training, apprenticeship structures, or shadowing within the organising team or staff. But it can also be tacit, with participants picking up skills as they observe work being done action or choices made or are volunteering themselves. It is common at larp festivals for all participants to take on some small organizer responsibilities, such as moving chairs, picking up after themselves,

spreading information, keeping time, or welcoming newcomers. This is primarily a consequence of larp festivals being produced by volunteers for communities feeling some sense of responsibility for and ownership of the event. In addition, larp as a form is itself co-creative, and often produced in a manner where participant labour is engaged to keep participant fees as low as possible. This way of engaging with larp likely seeps into organizational structures in the surrounding cultures, with larp festivals, like larps, made by all the people who are there. As most larps outside the festival and convention context are in fact standalone events, and a great proportion of the event participants have themselves produced either larps or larp-cultural events, the average skills and event production literacy of the participants is high. As at science fiction conventions (MacCallum-Stewart, 2023), the minutiae and overall quality of the festival or convention's production is also a common topic of conversation among their visitors.

Community and identity formation. Festivals consolidate communities around them, as individuals build relationships, and groups of people share experiences, create norms, and generate meaning. This is tied to belonging, feeling as part of a group, and that group membership acquiring meanings that become a building block of one's identity. Playing together is a fast way to build "a secret society" of shared experience (see Huizinga 1955): playing together creates a feeling that only those people who were there can fully understand. Internal jargon often emerges, concepts are further defined, and best practices emerge. A tightly knit community can however become harder to enter, requiring intentional effort to make new participants in the community feel welcome.

Space for play and thinking/being differently. Larp festivals are a place where participants can engage in play without fear of judgement or embarrassment. Thus, they offer an alibi (Deterding 2018) for adults to play, through creating a safe framework necessary to overcome fears of looking foolish. Often festivals also attempt to bring in first-timers, inviting new people to participate in the playing. Furthermore, play is connected to creativity and insight, meaning that while participants engage in acts of encountering each other and the world "as if", such pretend play can provide a place where thinking and even being and doing differently are possible. Of course, the benefits of having a space for play applies not just to players, but also to designers. Larp festivals lower the barrier of entry for first-time creators, providing context, production structure, organisational support, and visibility for new work.

Cultural legitimacy and legibility. Larp festivals, especially as they become established, raise the wider societal understanding and recognition of larp as a form of expression. This institutionalization process makes larps and larp festivals worthy of journalistic interest, artistic merit, scholarly attention, and public funding. In addition, conventions and festivals producing, publishing or maintaining e.g. books, journals, or online archives turns tacit, practical or verbal knowledge, as well as ephemeral event- or performance-based artforms, into written text. In this way, their areas of interest literally become legible, as well as searchable within digital information systems and possible to reference in research. As larps and larp festivals have become more established, they have attracted people from other artistic fields both not just through word of mouth, but also the spread of document resources. Practitioners from other fields come looking for inspiration or to harness larp methods for e.g. other arts or for education; commercial game and experience designers seeking inspiration and insight, or sometimes specifically seeking access to fans of the larp medium itself in order to promote their larp-based brand activations, or related products and services.

Transformational and transferrable experiences. Finally, larp festivals produce people who can take the experiences, skills, and insights gained to other cultural and societal contexts. In a general sense, this is of course a feature of all events and experiences. Larp festivals specifically may for example be able to shift one's way of viewing cultural or societal events as something in which one can pitch in and participate and offer a space where insights about societal issues may emerge as a result of playful and critical engagement.

2.5.5. Case Study: Fastaval as a cultural institution

In 1985, twenty early role-players "mostly aged 16-22" were gathered – through an announcement posted on a notice board in an Aarhus comic-book shop – to the founding meeting of a club for the hobby. As the group was big enough for the new club to need a space of its own, but too small and young to afford the rent, it was decided they would apply for the public funding as a youth club. Municipal support was proportional to membership, which therefore needed a boost, and a modestly successful "game day" was hosted to attract new members (Fastaval n.d).

The event, now known as "Fastaval 0" turned into an annual convention from the following year.¹⁴ It is still ongoing under the auspices of a separate non-profit association, Alea, specifically dedicated to the purpose. While Fastaval remains firmly grounded in the Danish role-playing community, it has over the past twenty years attracted an increasing proportion of international guests, primarily drawn by the renown of the convention's competitions for original role-playing scenarios and boardgames.

Larp culture influenced the community from the very first beginnings at Fastaval 0, where the Odense-based role-playing club FBO demonstrated *boffer fighting*¹⁵. In 1987, however, a first larp was created for Fastaval players by Malik Hyltoft. Unusually for the time, the theme was a 1926 mining strike. and many larps at the convention in the following years would have political themes. A 1991 larp portrayed an Orwellian dystopia; in 1992, civilians in a bomb shelter; in 1993, a hostage negotiation between civil rights activists and the authorities (Andresen 2011, p. 33). In parallel to convention larps typically played in a single room, a tradition emerges to also run a "convention-wide" larp that could accommodate up to 100 players, specifically to create a specific, shared experience for a greater part of the community (ibid p.34).

In the 1990s, larp and tabletop role-playing in Denmark and at Fastaval developed in different directions, with larp understood to be primarily for entertainment, while serious tabletop role-playing had the potential of an artform. This was especially true at Fastaval, which developed a specific style now known as the scenario tradition: artistically ambitious, rules-light and non-system one-shots often played in an embodied style reminiscent of improvised theatre, often engaging with

¹⁴ It is common to encounter these kinds of "zero events" in conventions histories. It seems that many annual events that turned out to be long lasting started with a smaller "proof of concept" events. In addition to Fastaval, this has also happened with Gen Con (the so-called Gen Con Zero was hosted in Gary Gygax's basement) and **Game Developers Conference** (originally Computer Game Developers Conference, hosted in designer Chris Crawford's living room).

¹⁵ Boffer fighting is a form of combat simulation using padded or "foam" weapons, such as swords. The activity is so central to many cultures, that the term 'boffer' is often used as the category name for combat-oriented styles of larp. These kinds of larps remain popular in the Nordic region, Denmark in particular. Foam weapons are however rarely used within the so-called Nordic Larp tradition, as combat is not typically a central activity or arena in this style of role-play.

existential or political themes, or exploring psychologically searing human dynamics, often in a realistic style.

In the local context, "scenario role-playing" was not considered to be larp, while from e.g. a US perspective, it clearly was. Game scholar Evan Torner, who visited in 2010, would describe the experience as life-changing for the seriousness with which the medium was treated. To him typical Fastaval game as a "literary larp scenario", impressed with the event's ability to "encourage experimentation, foster creativity and maintain a more formal artistic environment in which role-play takes place. (...) Fastaval is a gaming convention that elevates live-action gaming to a literary/performative art form, evaluating it as such as well". (Torner 2011, p. 37).

By the early 00s, Danish larp had matured artistically as well, and original larps compete in the Fastaval scenario competition although the scenario style still predominates. Fastaval's renown attracted Nordic role-play designers to participate, transmitting influences between the scenario tradition and the Nordic Larp movement. One significant conduit was the Swedish-Danish free-form collective Vi åker Jeep and its *jeepform* style of embodied role-play (Vi åker Jeep, 2007). Experimental game design elements spread to larp; Jeep member Anna Westerling founded Stockholm Scenario Festival to make scenario role-playing internationally available (A. Westerling, personal communication 2022), and the Jeep collective significantly participated in organising the Knutepunkt convention in 2011. The Fastaval scenario tradition's spread in Denmark and internationally would also be central to the development of Blackbox larp.

The Fastaval convention has never received public funding directly, and at current is also restricted from doing so because the Alea association (whose membership of Fastaval-goers is geographically dispersed) holds its annual meeting¹⁶ (current convention chair M. Bistrup Andersen, personal communication, 13 Jan 2025). The event has occasionally received support from private foundations, as well as from the national gaming culture organisation, Landsforeningen Bifrost, of which Alea is a member, as well as from Danish Youth Council (DUF), of which Bifrost is a member (M. Bistrup Andersen, personal communication, 15 Jan 2025).

The Danish Youth Council is an umbrella organisation "purpose-driven and socially engaged children's and youth organizations that work to promote democratic communities for children and young people in organizational life." Its 78 member organisations organise 600.000 members of which 100.000 are volunteers (DUF, n.d.).

DUF distributes lottery funds. In Sweden, by contrast, funding for democratically organised youth associations comes from the state, through the same public agency for civil society issues that coordinates e.g. the EU Erasmus programme and issues related to faith organisations.¹⁷ In an entirely public structure, the role of the national organisations for each sector of youth activities becomes emphasised. Although the precise structures and funding sources vary, there has been broad agreement across the Nordic countries that financial support for non-profit associations is an

¹⁶ This is permitted under Danish law but disqualifies the organisation from direct funding.

¹⁷ The closest Swedish equivalent to DUF, is its government agency for youth and civil society, MUCF, which in addition to the youth associations is "the coordinating authority for young people, civil society, faith communities, and national minorities". (MUCF, n.d.)

investment in practical citizenship skills, democratic culture, and shared responsibility¹⁸. Youth activities are particularly important in this regard.

Fastaval is still a non-profit event and produced by volunteers. Some of the founders still join in, many middle-aged participants have been going since their tweens, and a continued influx of young people is guaranteed by the contemporary popularity of tabletop role-playing games and the strong presence in Denmark of role-playing in after-school programmes and even as a specialised pedagogy. Of the 2025 participants, 19% were 10-20 years old, and 29% were 20-30 years old. Just under 3% of participants were children under 10; the event now offers a one-day track of children's programming for second-generation participants attending with their parents. Families are housed at a nearby boarding school, and a lucky few will nab nearby hostel and hotel rooms, but most of the convention's 1000 participants still sleep in neat rows on a gym floor.

The production model of Fastaval, where original scenarios are facilitated in parallel runs by several game masters, necessitates the existence of a script from which it can be played without the presence of the original designer. As these scenarios are, in the non-profit environment in which they are produced, typically not commercially published, creating a permanent repository for them became a concern. The website Alexandria.dk, created by Peter Brodersen in 2003, soon expanded into an archive of role-play activities in Denmark (P. Brodersen, personal communication 2022).

Today Alexandria.dk offers larp scripts, freeform scenarios, tabletop role-playing games, board games, gaming-related fanzines, and more. There are more than 1500 international larp entries and more than 500 larp scripts in Alexandria – ready to play and free to use (Grasmo 2025). Brodersen, who runs it still, is supported by over 50 volunteers helping with archiving. This archive has helped make other larp festivals like Stockholm scenario festival possible (A. Westerling, personal communication 2022), and it has also been a key repository used repeatedly in the writing of this chapter. The spread of Fastaval scenarios across the Nordics and the world via Alexandria.dk helped create shared frames of reference for designers and players and demonstrated the utility of the replayable larp script, which eventually became a feature of Nordic larp culture more broadly (Grasmo 2025).

Within event studies research, the importance of events such as conventions or conferences is often evaluated in terms of economic impact on the host city, and such a calculation would likely be possible here as well. Local business should see some limited impact. There is catering for the hundreds of participants who select to purchase it (at cost); hospitality sees a boost with the local hostel, nearest hotel, and convenient apartment rentals selling out; and the nearest supermarket should see a small bump. The sleepy municipality of Hobro, where the convention is now based, benefits from the venue rentals – a local high school and its neighbouring sports facility, both of which would otherwise close for Easter. In terms of tourism development, the effects are probably negligible. Although most of the participants travel from elsewhere in Denmark, the Nordics, or further afield (including other continents), businesses closed for much of Easter weekend, and the participants rarely leave the venue anyway. As for product sales to the participants themselves, the

¹⁸ Colloquially speaking, volunteering in the Nordic context appears to be understood as creating and caring for something together, when it seems in other cultures to be conceptualised more in terms of public service or even a moral obligation.

convention has a small vendor area, but even compared to other non-profit fandom conventions, the sums involved are marginal.

Given this small footprint, it would be easy to dismiss Fastaval and this entire category of event as charming but ultimately trivial curiosities. Within the academic convention research, such a tone is often present even in the most well-meaning fandom research by academics from outside the communities themselves. Ethnographic research about participant behaviours, their experiences belonging, and their processes of meaning-making is certainly valuable, but its individual focus obscures the event type as a medium as well as its societal and cultural impacts.

Fastaval likely provides both a good return on historical investment of public and lottery money and continues to be societally productive. The convention certainly offers a constructive environment for young people, including dedicated hangout areas for minors. From a democracy research perspective however, its civic training aspects are the most interesting.

Formally, the convention is organised by a registered association, Alea, which participants tend to join at sign-up (this is voluntary, but members pay a discounted price, making the total price including the membership fee lower than the one without). Alea is run on the standard democratic system familiar from most Nordic non-profit associations: the association is legally and financially liable for the event, and its annual meeting makes high-level decisions about bylaws and rules, finance, and strategy. All members can participate in the annual meeting (in person or online) and stand for election to the board.

In this case the real civic training, however, is operative. Every aspect of convention production is organised by that year's volunteer committee. Additionally, about a quarter of the participants each year take on specific organising responsibilities or practical production tasks. On top of this, every participant of the event not already volunteering for a specific task is obliged at signup to also select "DIY shifts", such as setting up and restocking the breakfast buffet, or striking and packing up the event after it closes. The cleaning of the venue, including its bathrooms, is handled by a special group of volunteers styled "Dirtbusters", whose special costumes and narrative design transforms their culturally low-status task into a visible and exclusive experience (Helfer 2011).

In this very practical sense, civic responsibility is built into the structure of the event. The visitor is not a consumer, they are a participant with shared responsibility in making the event happen and the experience positive, regardless of whether they are formally a staff member or currently on duty in some way. Advancing to positions of higher responsibility is mostly a question of showing up and building trust through working together, while affecting the overall rules of the event is possible to everyone through the democratic structure of the Alea association. Although Fastaval's culture is unusually clear and intentional, this type of organising is typical for non-profit association culture in much of the world – including for non-profit science fiction conventions, who for this very reason do not sell tickets but "memberships" even to their largest events.

The volunteering culture offers training in a range of skills unrelated to games. Every year, a shifting group of Fastaval volunteers spends the event – and a great deal of time before it – writing, performing in, producing, and video editing a convention-themed sketch comedy show screened nightly to the other participants. Other groups design and run a check-in process for a thousand people, or decorate, budget for, stock, and man the cafés and the cocktail bar. The context may be

playful and the communal framing enjoyable, but the tasks are treated seriously provide real work experience, often in mixed-age groups with significant organising and professional experience to draw on.

As for evaluating the cultural worth of a convention like Fastaval, structures of cultural status can get in the way. Independent analogue role-playing is not a big business anywhere, especially not in small language areas where the gaming hobbies are produced non-profit. Nor are analogue games, for all their current popularity, particularly visible in the public or cultural discourse. Some histories make a case for strong analogue game cultures being conducive to national success in the lucrative digital games sphere (Trammel 2019), but role-playing games and board games are rarely viewed as inherently valuable. If a thousand people showed up, annually and multi-generationally, to play new jazz music together, sing original choral works, or even do amateur theatrics, such an event would probably be viewed as culturally valuable even though it had no element of public performance. We propose that considering games in the same way is necessary, regardless of their historically lower status as a cultural form.

Fastaval's Otto awards, one of very few competitions for analogue indie one-shot role-playing scenarios, are internationally renowned. Participants play and evaluate competition titles. Similarly to many film festivals, there is an overall audience award, and specialised award categories decided by an expert jury. All games premiered at the convention enter competition. Anyone can pitch such a game, a curatorial team selects pitches, and convention volunteers offer an ambitious months-long coaching and editorial support structure to help all selected titles be completed, tested, and honed on time. The original boardgame competition, organised similarly around collaborative learning, attracts submissions from all around the world and has developed a specialised community of its own. Role-playing scenarios premiered in competition at Fastaval go on to tour other conventions and blackbox larp festivals, end up in classroom use or facilitated in museum settings, and are taught in game design programmes. Award-winning Fastaval boardgames are sometimes picked up by publishers.

In effect, this structure provides an environment for peer learning and apprenticeship within niche game design disciplines in which little formal education is available and trains the participant community in reflecting on and critiquing games as works of art and entertainment. These practices of communal reading and writing, fan production, and knowledge-making align precisely with the production of aesthetic theory, professional practice, and gradual cultural legitimacy within literary science fiction fandom.

For the individual participant, who may only be motivated by the enjoyment of leisure activities or shared experiences with like-minded people, convention volunteering can additionally offer skills training, artistic development, confidence, and a resilient community. The skills are inevitably also brought into professional life far beyond the non-profit environment. While documenting such skill-transfer effects is only possible through asking people individually, anecdotal evidence suggests it is common. Designers and organisers from the Fastaval community have also gone on to develop businesses combining their knowledge of games and their understanding of organisations and communities, including a successful chain of board-game cafés, and a strategic consultancy whose otherwise predictable-looking offices are adorned by long shelves of Ottos.

2.5.6 Case Study: Knutepunkt – Nordic Larp discourse as a convention culture

Pan-Nordic larp culture started in 1997, when Knutepunkt was organized in Norway. Originally conceived of as a meeting place for larp creators seeking to develop larp as an artform with cultural and societal impact, the event brought together participants from Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland (Strand & Grasmø 2017). It would come to circulate annually between these four countries, although thanks to the event language being English its participant base would rapidly expand. It now attracts larp designers from everywhere larp is played, with aesthetically and politically progressive European larp traditions predominating.

As an event, Knutepunkt has been difficult to formally categorise even for its participant community; it is most often referred to as a conference. By its nature and structure, it is however very similar to a literary fandom convention, with a focus on knowledge-making through talks, panels, workshops, and strong presence of academic larp researchers. The community's influence on games studies, as well as its international appeal, have both grown out of its publishing activities.

Starting in 2001, an average of has at least one Knutepunkt conference book a year have been produced and published both in print and online as a free pdf. The books are in English and represented one of the globally very few contexts where larp design was discussed and larp theorised as art, the larp discourse centred on the Knutepunkt convention would go on to have an outsize international impact. In this sense, its position remains similar to that once held by online forum The Forge for indie tabletop role-playing.

At Knutepunkt's birth, multi-day larps predominated in the community and playing them at the event itself was not possible. Gradually, Knutepunkt embraced aspects of the larp festival, with some short larps often played during the conference itself, and the addition of the community festival **A Week In...** (2003-) to precede the main event. *A Week In* features short and longer larps as well as events and socialising. It is intended to create or deepen connections between the international conference visitors and the larp community of the host city, not all of whom will participate at the convention.

In its third decade, the Knutepunkt discourse community remains the focal point for the design tradition referred to as Nordic larp and its offshoots, such as "*international larp*", marquee events produced in English specifically for international audiences, and *blackbox larp*, a minimalist style of convention-length larps designed for theatre blackboxes.

3. Understanding Democratic Spaces

To engage in study of 'democratic spaces', we first need to address what that term entails and place our understanding within the many models of democracy and democratic participation. In the following, we review existing literature on democratic spaces and democratic models to clarify key concepts and to situate our work in relationship to existing scholarship. This chapter is an opportunistic literature review, pulling together works informing our critical, constructionist, and care-informed approach to temporary and playful democratic spaces.

3.1.1 Some meanings of 'democratic space'

Even within academic research, the phrase 'democratic space(s)' is used in many different senses. Sometimes it is a technical term referring to *agency within a governance system* to participate or reform it. Such political agency can be curtailed, widened, or threatened (e.g. "Swedish Aid in the Era of Shrinking Democratic Space", Eldén & Levin, 2018). This is obviously a spatial metaphor, and we notice with interest its conceptual similarity e.g. to a Swedish term for agency, 'handlingsutrymme' ("the space available for action"). While most other uses of 'democratic space' involve a physical space in some sense, the metaphor of space for acting or thinking differently often attaches itself associatively to those uses too.

In academic contexts, the words 'democratic space' also appear as *instances of temporary situations with social and spatial aspects*, like events, processes, spaces, and actions that are democratic in some sense (e.g. "Vignettes... highlight the value of a democratic space and how art-making can support both social interaction and individual expression", Ahmed, 2025), or when such situations are *being evaluated for democratic qualities* (e.g. "Democratic Spaces: How Teachers Sustain Democracy and Education in Their Classrooms", Collins et al 2019)

Within the study of democratic innovation, the term has been used somewhat loosely in both senses as descriptions of event types such as citizen's assemblies, as well as in the context of evaluating the democratic impacts of specific instances thereof. In the context of a wider critique of the dominance of deliberative theory in shaping current understandings of democratic theory, Hans Asenbaum (2025) proposes a move from the study of *democratic innovations* to the study of *democratic spaces*. This would enable the inclusion into the field of "not just state-sponsored institutional designs" but also "social movement's participatory processes and civic initiatives" as well as the internal governance of e.g. political parties (Asenbaum 2025, p. 2).

Relevant to any discussion of democratic spaces are also *counterpublic* spaces (Fraser 1990): informal or oppositional spaces contesting hegemonic norms (e.g. feminist collectivism, street protest, some art and play events). The role of such spaces to continuing democratic development connects to the use in some traditions of 'democratic space' in reference to *spaces of resistance* or *alternatives to current systems*. Among these are theories focusing care and radical intimacy (e.g. Rosa 2023, see also Berlant 2011, Lorde 1988, Hemmings 2011, Kompridis 2011) and queer temporalities (Freeman 2010; Steele 2013, Halberstam 2005; see also Vitry 2020 on Sara Ahmed's 'queer time and space').

Particularly relevant to our area of research are descriptions of playful, ludic, spaces as *counter-publics of resistance* (e.g. Shepard 2006, Gouveia 2019, Morris 2021, see also Harper 2020; on playfulness see also Masek & Stenros 2021). This has been discussed for instance in the context of larps (Harper 2022), festivals (Jamieson and Todd 2021, Delanty et al. 2011), and humour (Masek and Prakken 2025).

Democratic spaces exist both offline and online. Digital or networked democratic spaces are sometimes called *networked publics* (e.g. online forums and social media, digital platforms for participation; digitally extended or connected media audiences and communities real or imagined; for a full discussion, see Ojala and Ripatti-Tornioinen 2023). These are sometimes studied as a specific type of democratic space, at other times viewed as analogous in their variety to the many kinds of offline democratic spaces.

3.1.2 A multiperspectival conceptualization of democratic space

Asenbaum (2025) has suggested the application of “multiple lenses within democratic theory” to the study of democratic spaces, not to hybridise them or perfect one, but to understand it in multiperspectival ways. “By immersing ourselves in various realities and looking at the same object from plural angles, we can understand it in novel and deeper ways.” (p.2)

This aligns with our understanding of democracy as an ongoing practice across all layers of social existence, rather than a static and stable institutional arrangement. For us, democratic space can therefore be understood as any socially and symbolically constructed (produced) arena in which participation, deliberation, and contestation over collective life are enacted. Our relational understanding of democratic space discusses communication (Habermas), contestation (Fraser), power and capital (Bourdieu), and the social production of space (Lefebvre), as sketched out below. Simultaneously, our work explores critical models of democracy that foreground networks of care (Tronto), embodies play (Harper), and alternative temporalities (Freeman), as will be discussed in section 3.2.

Our chosen perspective examines the work required to create, maintain, and participate in such spaces, which are actively constituted, negotiated, and stratified through power relations, material conditions, and discursive practices; and actualised through social norms, cultural behaviours, and affective human networks. In the following, we elaborate on the thinking underlying this conceptualization by offering quick sketches of the complementary democratic models and perspectives we draw from.

Jürgen Habermas’s (1962) concept of the *public sphere* provides an initial framework for understanding democratic space as a communicative domain where citizens engage in rational-critical debate about matters of common concern. From this perspective, democratic space can be seen as an *aspirational* sphere of communicative inclusion, always threatened by commodification and bureaucratization.

Nancy Fraser (1990) extends and critiques Habermas by emphasizing that the public sphere has never been universally accessible. She argues that marginalized groups have historically been excluded from dominant arenas of deliberation, leading to the emergence of *subaltern counterpublics* — alternative spaces where subordinated social groups formulate oppositional

interpretations and discourses. For Fraser, democratic space is inherently *plural* and *agonistic*, characterized by struggles over legitimacy and representation. Thus, democracy depends not only on access to existing public spheres but also on the capacity to create new ones that challenge dominant norms and hierarchies.

Pierre Bourdieu's (1990, 1991, 2010) concept of *symbolic power* highlights how domination can persist even in ostensibly egalitarian contexts, as certain ways of speaking, acting, or knowing are valorised over others. This draws attention to how democratic participation is not only institutionally but also culturally conditioned and dependent on group-belonging (Bourdieu and Wacquant 2013). This suggests that democratic space must be understood as both material and symbolic; simultaneously constituted through architecture and spatial organization, as well as embodied practices of e.g. gathering, conflict-resolutions, and performance. The spatial production of democracy requires not only the freedom to deliberate, but also the capacity to occupy and transform physical and social spaces.

Henri Lefebvre (1974/1991) complicates this analysis by insisting that space itself is socially produced, or rather continuously in a producing process. He argues that space is not a neutral container but an outcome of social practices, relations, and representations. A democratic space is a social space connected to and interacting with multitude of other social spaces. It is therefore not possible to analyse one specific space without understanding the societal context around it. Lefebvre guides us to ask whether a social space is reproducing power-relations of the current society, or if it is producing new social reality.

Democracy, in this view, is not located in a fixed institution or territory but enacted across multiple, overlapping spaces that continually reproduce and challenge existing power relations. 'Democratic' is therefore not a binary state, but an aspiration and a claim – performed, resisted, and negotiated across multiple spatial and social dimensions. In the following section, we reflect on the relations of some fundamental democratic models; place physical and metaphorical spaces in the context of democratic practice and *the public sphere*; explore the inclusion of radical perspectives of care and intimacy; and offer theoretical contextualisation of the playful nature of our research topic.

3.2. Deliberation, Care, and the Playful Temporary

3.2.1 Models of democracy and the public sphere

The traditional *participatory model* (e.g. Rousseau, Mill, Dewey) of democracy centres an individual-focused ideal where citizens can live in harmony with each other. In this view, democracy works best when citizens are highly informed, actively engaged, and directly involved in political decision-making. In this model, democratic legitimacy is produced through broad and equal participation with public discourse ideally leading to harmony.

Habermas builds on this idea of public discourse, arguing that legitimacy is rooted not so much in a competition between different interests and voting, but in public reasoning. Presenting arguments, making claims, and justifying them are key to a democratic *public sphere*. Habermas updates the traditional understanding of the centrality of formal decision-making to how democracies work, with

the importance of social and cultural processes. His concept of the public sphere becomes the foundation of the *deliberative democracy model*, whose core idea is that legitimate democracy depends on rational, inclusive deliberation where citizens and representatives justify their views publicly.

The traditional participatory models and its deliberative specification are idealised models of democracy. There are numerous other models that are a step or two closer to practice and criticize or at least complicate the picture painted by including considerations of for instance economic systems.

The *critical or Marxist model* understands democracy as embedded in societal structures that describes conflict and power struggles. Marx views democracy under capitalism as constrained and dependent upon the material resources of classes (economic groups), where the capitalist state serves dominant economic classes. A continuous development of a democracy, as well as a fair society, hinges on the battle between the classes for a more just distribution of power and resources. Other models in this vein include the *pluralist model*, which forefronts how power in democracy is dispersed among many competing interest groups (unions, business associations, NGOs, religious groups, etc.); the *resource & mobilization model*, which assumes that participation in democracy depends on individual and group resources (time, money, education, networks) and mobilization by parties or movements; and the *social capital model* (Putnam 1995), which focuses on how civic engagement and trust (“social capital”) strengthen democracy.

Other critical takes on idealized democratic models underline how there isn’t really a single public sphere, but several overlapping ones. Not all publics are heard and valued in a similar fashion, and these barriers to being heard and appreciated tend to go on gendered, racialized, and class-based lines. These alternatives to the hegemonic public spheres are discussed often under the name of *counterpublics* (Fraser 1990) which can be temporary, informal and like social movements, Jung 2010).

Feminist ethics have also questioned the foundations of the democratic models (e.g. Butler 1988; 2004; 2021). The central idea in *democratic politics of care* is that democracy should not only be about voting, deliberation, or competition, but also about mutual care, solidarity, and attention to vulnerability. Within this approach, democracy can even be viewed as a work of caring, in line with Tronto’s (2013) conceptualization of care as “[e]verything we do to maintain, continue, and repair our world so that we can live in it as well as possible”.

3.2.2. The Cultural Public Sphere

Jürgen Habermas came to update his conception of the public sphere, if not necessarily in direct response to the central critiques, then at least in a manner that accommodates them. In 1992, Citing Bakhtin’s (1968) work on the carnival as the source of his intellectual breakthrough, Habermas (1992, quoted in McGuigan 2011) conceded that he had previously misunderstood “the inner dynamics of a plebian culture”, which should be understood as a “periodically recurring violent revolt of a counterproject to the hierarchical world of domination. (...) Only a stereoscopic view of this sort reveals how a mechanism of exclusion that locks out and represses at the same time calls

forth countereffects that cannot be neutralized". He observed that none of the major contemporary political movements (e.g. nuclear disarmament, global justice, anti-racism, women's rights, and environmentalism) had broached the public thank to the state apparatus or established organizations and systems. Instead, they were broached in the "outermost periphery" of civil society before catalyzing social movements and subcultures (Habermas 1996, quoted in McGuigan 2011)

In his updated view, the closer connection of civil society with the spheres of private life enabled it to perceive problems excluded from the political mainstream.

Complementary modes of discourse – "the whole range of media and popular culture" – have been described by Jim McGuigan (2005, p. 427) as the *cultural public sphere*: an articulation of contested terrains of public and personal politics through affective communication modes for which the cognitively oriented political public sphere has had little patience. He is particularly considering the "various channels of mass popular culture and entertainment" (McGuigan 2011), including physical events such as festivals.

McGuigan is writing at a time when the internet and social media have not yet fully challenged and colonised mass culture, supercharging the role of affective communication in ways that have arguably undermined the rational public sphere entirely, as well as splintering the cultural sphere. Even so, he argues that the concept should not be applied naïvely. Cultural expression, especially if it is public and collective or reliant for its production and distribution on elite gatekeepers, is often a direct expression of political power or indirectly of its agendas. At the same time, the very ubiquity of mass-mediated narratives also creates a space for less-monitored expression of marginalised positions (McGuigan 2011), a dynamic that the explosive growth in media production and the democratisation of its distribution would subsequently only strengthen. This is not to say that all expressions represent constructive participation in the cultural public sphere. McGuigan (2011) observes: "The fact that something engages popular attention does not in itself qualify it as the site of a critical disquisition".

3.2.3 Deliberation theory and its criticism

Normative theories of deliberative democracy (e.g., Jürgen Habermas, John Rawls) that emphasize reason-giving, mutual justification, and legitimacy eventually produced a contemporary sense of 'deliberation' as citizens engaging in reasoned discussion and argumentation about collective issues.

This political theory understanding of deliberation as a normative ideal was critiqued and developed from social science perspectives, promoting a shift from "deliberation as ideal" to "deliberation as empirically situated." Ryfe (2007) argues that deliberative practice is embedded in social fields and lacks the stability of an autonomous field of its own. In sociological practice, as the abstracted citizen becomes embodied, new kinds of questions are unlocked. How does deliberation play out in social contexts? What social conditions, power dynamics, and cultural logics enable or constrain deliberation?

The study of deliberative democracy methods and interventions as democratic innovation embraces this critique. Interventions such as the 'deliberative poll' and 'mini-publics' (for an introductory overview, see Escobar & Elstub 2017) share the intention of bringing citizens closer to the political

process, by designing possibilities for increased democratic participation through deliberation. Deliberation has in recent years dominated the “social imaginary” of the study of democratic participation (Poulsen 2022).

While deliberation has been widely researched, praised, and practiced, it has also been criticized for reinforcing unequal access to participation (Rosanvallon, 2008, p. 298) and for remaining too focused on the role of reason and rational discourse (della Porta, 2013). However, within the field, curiosity towards alternative forms of speech and “creative, playful, emotional, sometimes carnivalesque forms of claim making” (Curato & Parry, 2018) is growing. It has also moved from abstract discussions of the efficacy of democratic methods in producing democratic outcomes within the local systems of governance to measuring specific outcomes and impacts. Iterative testing and evaluation in specific circumstances has deepened the understanding of the dynamics of deliberation. For example, in a systematic review (Caluwaerts et al. 2023) a key finding was that design choices such as group composition, facilitation, an interaction mode matter for the outcomes.

Asenbaum (2025) argues for combining the normative grounding of deliberative democracy with innovation and a multi-perspective diversity of conceptions of democratic space. Drawing on participatory, deliberative, agonistic, feminist, and transformative democratic theory, as well as empirical studies he makes concrete recommendations for designers of democratic innovations.

Especially relevant for the Larpocracy project is the proposal to approach democratic spaces as ludic and playful (Shepard 2006; Harper 2020; Harper 2022); e.g. develop *democratic playgrounds* which “have a particularly strong capacity to unfold the agentic potential of participants [as] play goes beyond discursive expression” (Asenbaum & Hanusch, 2021, p.7). Poulsen (2022) refers to this suggestion in his research of the “junk playground” (2022), strengthening the argument that such playgrounds could cultivate a kind of “democratic serendipity” and more open-ended explorations of “alternative, more democratic futures” (Asenbaum & Hanusch, 2021, p. 9, see also Munoz 1996; Hutching and Giardino 2016).

Within the wider Larpocracy research project, these approaches speak directly to the Work Packages exploring the use of larp and larp methods in deliberative democracy contexts (see Bowman et al 2025). They also inform our analysis of larp festivals as democratic spaces, as these events are shaped and influenced by larps and larp production environments which seem to precisely fulfil the promise of such ‘playgrounds’ – but also as an approach for bridging systems-oriented and social/embodyed understandings of democracy.

3.2.4 Care and democratic spaces

Approaching democracy through feminist ethics (Pettersen 2021, see also Ahmed 2004; Gilligan 1982), centring care, intimacy, and affect, challenges the liberal, individualist conception of politics. Instead of viewing democratic processes as interactions between autonomous, rational subjects, it emphasizes a relational understanding – an understanding of dependency as a universal human condition (Tronto 2013). Democracy is hence explained as interdependent relations, and always embedded in networks of care, vulnerability, and affect. In this tradition democracy is produced through affective and emotional dimensions – intimacy, trust, and shared vulnerability are political

resources, not private matters. Recent theories of democracy show how the concept of *care* enables democratic spaces amongst different empowered people. (Endo 2024)

As mentioned above, Tronto (2013) argues that democracy itself is a form of care, because it relies on how societies attend to interdependence and vulnerability.

On the most general level, we suggest that caring be viewed as a species activity that includes everything that we do to maintain, continue, and repair our 'world' so that we can live in it as well as possible. That world includes our bodies, ourselves, and our environment, all of which we seek to interweave in a complex, life-sustaining web. (Tronto 1993, 103)

From this perspective a democratic space is not only a deliberative arena but also a network of care relations. Tronto sees justice and participation as inseparable from the practices of attending to others — listening, responding, maintaining, and repairing. It follows, then, that exclusion, domination, and neglect are failures of care, not just procedural flaws. Understanding democracy as caring relations implies that democratic spaces are affective and porous and could be encountered anywhere. Democratic space is situated and embodied — it happens between people in their everyday interactions where openness, care, and vulnerability are constitutive, not optional (Tronto 2013, see also Rosa 2023, Endo 2024).

Another model of democracy, part of the same discourse of community and care, is the *affect and emotional model* (Rosa 2023 about e.g. Chantal Mouffe, Martha Nussbaum). The core idea is that participation in democratic processes is not only rational and interest-driven, but also shaped by emotions, empathy, trust, and care. Emotions and intimate relations build solidarity across difference, making democratic life more inclusive. This way of thinking has also made its way into deliberative democracy research (Asenbaum 2021; 2025)

A third model involves rethinking connection and relationality and is presented as a necessary alternative when democracy is *not* working (Rosa 2023). To this end, *radical intimacy theory* (Laureen Berlant, Nikolas Kompridis) reimagines democratic space not as a neutral forum of rational debate, but as a web of embodied, emotional, and affective encounters. The core idea is that democracy is strengthened by practices of closeness, vulnerability, and affective connection, as an alternative to distanced, impersonal procedures. This is "radical" in the sense that intimacy is not merely a private quality, but as a public, political resource for solidarity and transformation. It can also involve new forms of building (non-capitalistic) networks of romance, families, and sexual connections (Rosa 2023).

In this understanding of democracy, a democratic space depends on how we relate — how we touch, listen, and stay with differences that exists or emerge — not merely on procedures. Traditional models of democracy tend to assume autonomous, rational individuals, and focus on outputs, outcomes and impact (Weiss 1995; Rosenberg 1969) of democratic spaces. Care and intimacy-based theories argue instead for interdependence, vulnerability, and affect as essential democratic resources.

3.2.5 Playful and temporal spaces as democratic spaces

The specific context of larp and larp festivals also directs our perspectives. The events we study tend to be *temporally contained* and are deeply connected both to play and care.

Sophie Rosa's (2023) theory of radical intimacy reframes democratic space as a web of embodied, affective encounters, and Chikako Endo (2024) argues that democracy requires enabling others to "be part of the story". This is particularly resonant for larp contexts, where participants are entangled in shared narratives and collective worldmaking. In larp festivals, democratic participation often takes the form of supporting others' capacity to act, feel safe, and remain engaged over time —highlighting care as a precondition for participation rather than its outcome.¹⁹

Playfulness, improvisation, subcultural events, and aesthetic experimentation create temporary worlds in which different relations and rhythms become possible (Poulsen 2022), which is an important part of sustaining and building democracy, and to give space for resistance and new imaginaries. Without a space to think differently political imagination withers (see Graeber & Wengrow 2018). These alternative temporalities allow participants to step outside productivity-oriented rhythms and imagine and embody different forms of social and political relations (Gouveia 2019; Harper 2020; Poulsen 2022). Playful practices are generative precisely because they interrupt habitual orientations, producing moments of disorientation (Ahmed 2006; Stone 2018) that redistribute the capacity to appear, to affect, and to participate. In this sense, larp festivals enact democratic space not by producing policy outcomes or consensus, but by reorienting how bodies, affects, and narratives meet in time/space (see also Jones 2009; Juvonen 2022).

In connection to models of democracy, play has been discussed as disruption against capitalist norms by the Situationist International in France (Ko 2008) and theorised as frivolous or a "protest against the order of the ordained world" (Sutton-Smith p 306). An understanding as play as resistance (Gouveia 2019, Harper 2022) and as a concept of the ludic counterpublic has emerged (Shepard 2006, Kurashige 2019, Xie et al. 2021). Gouveia writes:

Play and games can serve as forms of social resistance and have a profound impact on the narrative construction of playful identities. [...] they can also serve to unite people — they have an ethical and transgressive dimension, and they can promote inclusion through disruptive techniques, damaging all forms of fundamentalism. (Gouveia 2019 pp 52-53)

Describing playful publics as resistance to Chinese authorities, Xie, Foxman and Xu argue that play is what is lacking in Habermas model of democracy:

When contemplating play, these three key ludological features – that it is autotelic, contextual, and appropriative – fill in gaps in Habermas' model, which usually portrays the public sphere as overly formalist, deliberative, and rational. Put simply, play is absent from his paradigm. (Xie et al. 2021)

¹⁹ Play and temporality are central to this argument. Drawing on queer theories of time and space (Freeman 2010; Halberstam 2005; Ahmed 2006; Steele 2013), we may conceptualize larp festivals as heterotopia (Foucault 1986, Hutchings and Giardino 2016) and queer temporal and corporal spaces (Jones 2009; Juvonen 2022) that suspend or reconfigure normative, linear time.

Play can enable creativity, and the two have been connected in research for at least a century (Stenros 2015). Sustained play requires time, space, and opportunity, but can enable creative reimagining of real-life dynamics and situations. Poulsen (2022) has argued that play design can contribute to expanding the participatory repertoire within deliberative democracies by offering sites for public freedom and happiness. Tapping into queer and play temporalities can expand the democratic imagination (Grasmo, Sihvonen and Stenros 2026, Gouveia 2019, Hutching and Giardino 2016) and offer practical, situated, and larp-relevant models for liveable, yet temporary democratic spaces (for examples see Johansson et al, 2025).

Play, and specifically embodied role-play like larp, is also directly connected to questions of equality in public participation. Habermas (Fraser 1990) states that people meet in the public sphere “as if they were social equals”. The key observation is that people are *not* social equals: Haberman’s vision is behaving as though that was not the case. This is not always possible, which is why critical approaches and counterpublics are needed. The conception of public spheres as acting “as if” also opens them to the criticism of merely being theatre (Muñoz 2009, see also Fraser 1990). From the perspective of performance studies, play studies, and game studies, such a critique is reductive.

Behaving “as if” is at the heart of all performance, all pretend play, and all role-play. In many contexts (e.g. wedding rituals, jury duty) the performance of temporary roles and actions is culturally inscribed with real-world consequences. Some sociologists even see roles as a key element of organizing our social situations in everyday life (see Goffman 1959). Playful pretence is embraced in serious arenas ranging from education to artistic practice. If anything, the playful qualities inherent in pretence, and in the temporary social behaviours and situations of alternative temporalities, are central to their impact. Embracing these facts may offer ways of addressing their implications.

From a queer feminist perspective, inspired by Sara Ahmed, temporal space and democratic space are entwined through the politics of orientation, affect, and embodiment. Democracy is not only a question of institutional access or deliberation, but of how bodies inhabit time and space together – how alternative tempos, gestures, and affects can make room for otherwise excluded ways of living and imagining the collective. Ahmed (2010) explores how orientation (both spatial and temporal) structures experience and belonging and demonstrates how heteronormative and racialized orientations organize the spaces we inhabit and the futures we can imagine.

Artistic and playful practices are generative precisely because they *queer* temporal spaces: they interrupt linear progress, open spaces of encounter, and allow democracy to be felt and performed differently. They open for new possibilities, for thinking differently, for approaching social interaction from unusual angles, and viewing the everyday world from a removed position. They produce what Ahmed (2010) might call “moments of disorientation” – ruptures that unsettle the taken-for-granted direction of political life. These moments can be profoundly democratic: they invite participation without predefinition; value openness and emergence over closure and control and redistribute the capacity to appear and to affect.

Queer-feminist theory tends to emphasise disruption and resistance (Fraser 1990) such as e.g. affective activism (Juvonen 2022, Jones 2009; Ahmed 2004). Theories rooted in game and play studies tend to foreground co-creative imagination (Grasmo, Sihvonen, Stenros 2026), reflexivity and preparedness for uncertain futures (Harper 2022), embodied playfulness as inherently democratic

(Poulsen 2022) and even creating affective social counterpublics (Morris 2021). These approaches are complementary, helping to identify the challenges while keeping an eye on the opportunities created by playing together.

Art, performance, and play can all be read as *embodied experiments in temporal space* – practices that suspend or reconfigure normative time. Playfulness, improvisation, and aesthetic experimentation create temporary worlds where different relations and rhythms become possible. In this sense, artistic and playful practices enact democratic spaces not because they produce deliberation or decision-making, but because they reorient how bodies and affect meet in time.

The functions of traditional spaces transforming individual agency, collective dynamics, and the political imaginary have in the last century been colonised by capitalist and individualist dynamics, like commodification of Pride marches (Taylor 2014) Where they still flourish – often “underground” – they may attempt to remain disconnected from the institutional systems of the public sphere. While protecting the integrity of their participant communities in the short term, this may paradoxically also make them largely irrelevant – carnival as a pressure valve within an authoritarian system rather than as laboratory for imagined change. Habermas’s imagined from the private, temporary, playful or not-real peripheries into the political mainstream requires as its bridging infrastructure a functioning cultural public sphere, e.g. through the non-profit, volunteer-based civil-sector cultural organisations exemplified in our research.

We concede that the functioning of this bridging cultural public sphere is particularly challenged at this moment of hyper-capitalism and accelerating AI adoption. Not just has the shared traditional media environment been largely destroyed; the usefulness of the internet and social media for their originally envisioned democratising purposes is also rapidly declining. Further reflection on such aspects of changing mediatisation will be required throughout this project.

We however expect these wider societal dynamics to be largely irrelevant in the immediate context of research in 2026-2027 on members of real-world communities in physical spaces at event types that have remained essentially unchanged across almost a century of technological and social change.

The ongoing democratic backsliding, and the rapid diminishment of democratic space on the societal scale that follows, are also likely to shift citizen attention toward civil society, local community, and the spaces of everyday life, which in practice are the arenas in which the repairing work of a democracy of care is carried out.

3.2.6. Democratic Space in the Context of Our Research

Integrating the perspectives discussed in this chapter, *democratic space* emerges as a relational and contested field, produced through struggles for inclusion and recognition, communicative practices, distributions of symbolic capital, and the spatial organization of social life; a field that is actively made, unmade, and remade. Conceptualising democratic space not merely as a physical or institutional domain, but as a socially produced field of power relations where claims to participation, representation, and equality are continuously negotiated means that studying it will

involve unpacking how power, participation, and material as well as social structures shape how democracy is enacted.

A critical sociological understanding guides us to treat democratic space not as a predetermined domain but as an ongoing process of negotiation shaped by the tension between idealized notions of equality and the persistent realities of structural domination. A contemporary, multiperspectival democratic theory approach guides us to engage with the physical spaces and gatherings we study both as instances of a cultural public sphere, and as spaces engaging with and expanding the political imaginary. Critical democratic innovation theory perspectives remind us not to overlook these spaces or the governance and decision-making process internal to them as potential sources of democratic innovation.

Combining this conceptualisation with design research, which studies how things and social processes create agency, community, and meaning, is particularly fertile. The envisioning, construction, maintenance, and development of democracy are ongoing processes of making and doing; of imagining, designing and testing societies, cultures, norms, spaces of negotiation, as well as the processes through which they can continue to be made anew.

In our ongoing work, we will continue to fine-tune the understanding of democratic spaces discussed in this chapter, which is also the framework for our work in the field. Approaching the analysis stage, we also expect further theoretical reflection of the role of participation and democratic skills in these contexts to be required. The continuing analysis supports our work towards a model for thinking of larp festivals as democratic spaces.

The following two sections are a summary of our current understanding of larp festivals and conventions as democratic spaces (3.3), and a brief discussion of how this connects to the development of a practical model of democratic space, in the sense of a framework supporting decision-making in event design processes (3.4).

3.3. Larp festivals as democratic spaces: Preliminary Descriptions

3.3.1. Festivals as playful counterpublics

Festivals are studied as temporary democratic spaces (Delanty, Giorgi & Sassatelli 2011); e.g. as “playful transgression of authority and the symbolic inversion of social hierarchies” (Taylor 2014), as well as similar to activist tactics of social movements, creating spatial imagination, “playful performance and an aesthetic-political heightened energy.” (Jamieson and Todd 2021). The cultural sphere of festivals can be particularly suited to “collectively build a critical space of their own” since they allow regulars and devotees time to gather and discuss before and after the show (Fabiani 2011).

There are studies in which festivals have been conceptualized as counterpublics (Rosanvallon 2008, see also Fraser 1990), especially where hegemonic norms are contested (Taylor 2014; Jamieson & Todd 2021; Siročić 2025) and alternative political imaginaries can emerge. Festivals as democratic space has been studied as playful and artistic counterpublics (Shepard 2006; Morris 2021; Gouveia 2019), as counterpublics of affect (and larp in itself as a socio-cultural technology for creating heterotopia (Grasmo, Sihvonen, & Stenros in press). *Heterotopia* (Foucault 1986) is a temporary

space that is neither utopia nor dystopia, but “somewhere else”. This understanding aligns with utopian theories and speculative worldbuilding (Muñoz 1996; 2009).

Larp festivals as a distinctive form of counterpublic space are shaped by embodied role-play, radical – or at least democratic – intimacies (Rosa 2023). Queer performance theory challenges the understanding of the temporal performance, for instance in a festival, of “acting as if” social equality exists as merely theatrical. Muñoz (2009) argues that playful pretense and role-taking are not politically empty, but central to how social realities are organized and transformed (see also Sutton-Smith 1997). Participatory creation, as larp does, can form a critically utopic perspective, affective engagement and commitment to disruptive and radical play (Martin and Licona 2018). In larp festivals, behaving “as if” different relations were possible enables participants to create democratic capacities such as reflexivity, adaptability, and resilience (Harper 2022), which may be poorly supported by more rigid democratic formats.

3.3.2 Studying larp festivals as democratic spaces

How “democraticness” is expressed in the context of larp festivals and conventions varies, depending e.g. on their production context and on which aspects of them are the focus of our study at any given time. As discussed in chapter two, these events and their participants are connected to underlying communities and organizations. They may be organised as or by democratic associations, small businesses, or informal social groups, and the events may be for-profit or non-profit, depending for their existence on e.g. public funds, customer retention, or volunteer labour. All these parameters directly affect the structure of the events, the experiences of their participants, and the ways in which they can be democratic.

Many larp festivals and conventions have been intentionally structured – in whole or in part, from the beginning or over time – to align with explicitly democratic ideals, but what this means varies too. The representative democracy of a national interest organisation and the spontaneous and self-organising *do-ocracy model* (Chen 2009) of an art collective may share similar values but embody and operationalise them through entirely different means and prioritise different concerns.

Engaging with larp festivals and conventions as ‘democratic spaces’, we are therefore thinking about them simultaneously as systems and concretely as humans interacting with each other – considering on the one hand theories concerned with power, process, outcomes, and effects, and on the other the practice of understanding and modelling humans making, being in and doing in these spaces. Both approaches can be applied on a scale ranging from the macro – model systems of democracy – via the meta and meso – accounts of what people theoretically need for a system to function – to micro, the consideration of specific people in actual rooms.

We may study *how larp festivals and conventions function within systems of democratic governance, cultural life, or social communities*, including how their existence and production is supported or hindered by those structures. Another way of phrasing this that we can study *how the events are made*. On the one hand, this involves analysing *how they are produced by the dynamics and circumstances of their surrounding societies and structures*; on the other, *how they are produced in terms of organisation and labour*. These two approaches will be expanded on separately in the next two subsections (3.3.2. and 3.3.3).

We could also study studying *whether, how, and by whom individual agency and democratic practices are created and operating* in the context of the events. In other words, how the events themselves (as well as their production processes) are experienced in terms of co-creation, agency, and belonging. This approach will be discussed in subsection 3.3.4.

Finally, one might study *how the existence of these spaces and the interactions of participants within them may support, challenge, or reimagine the wider democratic structures and cultures within which they exist*. That is, study them as arenas for public discourse and the political imaginary, whether as instances of a cultural public sphere or as catalysts of personal, cultural, and political transformation. This approach is discussed in subsection 3.3.5.

These preliminary descriptions of larp festivals as democratic spaces from these perspectives are followed in the next section by a discussion of how we are prioritising our research within the limited time frame of this three-year project.

3.3.3. Larp festivals and conventions in society

Larp festivals and conventions are both part of and interacting with democratic institutions and systems. Larp festivals and conventions are cultural events and sometimes cultural institutions. As sites for creating, experiencing, critiquing, and debating the societal meanings of works of art they are part of the cultural public sphere (McGuigan 2011). This is also true for these events as nodes for publication and media production. As shared public-private spaces of conversation and laughter, they are in the sociological sense third places (Oldenburg 2023 [1989]). As playful volunteer-run events, they provide non-commercial, collectively oriented, secular spaces for recreation and education. In their juxtaposition of their loci with potential, temporary and fictional worlds, they may function as heterotopias (Foucault 1986), providing sites where imagining and inhabiting differently is possible – and that are necessary to produce “reality”.

Larp festivals and conventions are meeting places gathering people of different ages, from different regions and cultures, and to a varied but lesser degree from varied socioeconomic backgrounds.

In a playful and co-creative environment, where shared interests as well as responsibilities are assumed, participants engage with works on serious and existential topics, as well as seriously on frivolous topics, and work side by side on practical tasks. Within the larps that they play or discuss, participants maintain, negotiate, and recreate the shared norms of their temporary society. Outside the fictions or programme items, the same process is applied to the event itself. Arguably therefore, role-playing, resting, or reflecting, civic skills are exercised and perhaps developed.

Many of these events, including those specifically included in our study, are non-profit and organized, produced, and run by communities of volunteers. Specifically in the Nordic context, this tends to mean that the events are formally organised by democratic non-profit associations (some operational implications of this will be discussed in the next subsection). This is an organisational form historically encouraged by the state in the Nordic countries, as belonging to or participating in the running of democratic association explicitly trains civic skills.

The precise requirements for associations vary between countries, as do sources of available funding (public funds, lottery money, private foundations), and how support for the civil sector is organised, e.g. which kinds of support are handled on state, regional or local levels; whether game-cultural

events can receive cultural funding (e.g. Norwegian cultural funds including larp in “amateur theatrics”); or how youth-culture and youth organisations are defined (e.g. in Sweden a youth organisation is one where over half of the members are 26 or under).

Since it is typical for the events and organisations in our study to be entirely volunteer-run – even an event like the Finnish Ropecon with over 10.000 participants and over 1600 staff – the main cost is the venue, and scales with the participants. In practice, on the level of the individual event, event operations are often functionally independent from public support and therefore from potential influence via that channel.

Local clubs, associations and game communities do however benefit from regular meeting places. Free or affordable access to venues like culture houses, youth houses, and libraries is an indirect form of public support made increasingly necessary by an overall decline in non-commercial meeting places. The ability to rent a permanent space typically relies on public money, which in turn is often contingent on high levels of organised activity and a stable or growing membership. This is a kind of public-sector influence, mitigated in the cultural sector by arm’s length policies. In the context of youth work the necessity for the activities to genuinely appeal to the co-creating membership may provide a counterweight to attempts of influencing their content or direction.

In Denmark and Sweden, where national umbrella organisations organise and represent local clubs, these do have some salaried staff. Sverok, for instance, distributes government funds to its 1000 member organisations, which requires a high level of operational continuity and predictability. Sverok has maintained its historical policies of pushing funding out to local associations (who would, for instance, organise conventions; Brodén 2009). Centrally run initiatives in recent years have included e.g. developing a Code of Conduct for Swedish esports (Englin 2024) and a multi-year project for active inclusion of neurodivergent youth in gaming culture (Hilding et al 2025). Sverok has a vibrant system of representative democracy throughout its internal structures and can be considered a success story from the perspective of national investment in democratic skills; in return it has become a credible representative for the gaming hobbies that is legible to the state. Its elected chairperson is also considered in the media as a natural representative to speak for the hobbies it organises.

In Finland, by contrast, no equivalent structure exists, and gaming clubs and game-cultural associations interact with public systems on local level. The responsibility for speaking in the media and other public contexts for the hobbies it organises has however to some degree been taken up by Ropecon ry, the non-profit association that produces Ropecon (and, every fourth year, the Nordic larp convention Solmukohta/Knutepunkt). This role is not enabled by a relationship to the public sector but by the event’s systematic media work over decades and what it is understood to represent. The same could be said of Sverok.

These macro perspectives are only peripherally relevant to our promised deliverables. They do however offer promising topics for future work or research partnerships. Particularly interesting directions could include:

- Differences in game-cultural organisations across the Nordics should be documented and comparatively studied. What differences are related to how game-cultural fields are defined? To what degree is “games” understood as youth culture?
- What incentives and limitations do different rules and regulations of non-profit associations produce? How, if at all, is this reflected in operational practice or the kinds of events and communities made possible? Are such differences in game-cultural practice reflecting or challenging current understandings of changing membership structures and participatory models in civil sector organisations?
- Local or comparative results can also be analysed in relation to evolving civil society research. Understanding these contexts in relation to democratic culture and civic skill-building is central to questions about democratic event design. Larps and larp-cultural events however also seem to engender an unusual amount of trust between their participants. This may prove relevant and fruitful to the evolving understanding of the role of trust in stable democracies.
- How does non-profit organising contribute to the production of cultural legitimacy and legibility in democratic systems?

3.3.4. Larp festivals and conventions as volunteer productions

In preliminary summary, the Nordic events we study are produced non-profit, typically entirely by teams of volunteers. While their organising teams can range in formality from a friend group to a project group selected in an association meeting through some democratic process. In most cases, the formal organisation backing the events is a registered non-profit association, an organisational form allowing groups of private citizens to collectively assume responsibility for e.g. bank accounts, contracts, and leases²⁰.

Large associations, especially any interacting with authorities or organising young people, are often conscientiously run. In such contexts, places on the board or as chair are campaigned for, and showing up to vote on propositions is viewed as important among the most actively volunteering members. Most are probably in between, with formal processes or roles involving administrative responsibilities understood to be a necessary if not enjoyable part of the work of volunteering.

If human resources are limited, attention and efforts seem to be directed away from the formalities toward the operational level. For associations not receiving funding in proportion to their membership anyway, a possible solution is to limit the association membership (and therefore its formal leadership) to some core group of volunteers, perhaps as few as five or ten people. The actual organising teams can of course still be much bigger, and the participant communities committed to the events themselves larger still. In such cases, an annual meeting may be a fifteen-minute affair to ensure someone among the active members can still sign for the association, and the required democratic processes treated as bureaucratic formalities that need to be fulfilled only on paper.

We have not asked about compliance specifically, and our sample is too small to generalise from regardless, but in the light of the wider research it seems likely that small game-cultural

²⁰ The Nordic cultures are not particularly litigious, and healthcare is essentially free, making insurance a relatively insignificant financial burden in the context of events.

organisations may be taking liberties regarding their own bylaws, e.g. perhaps having general meetings as needed for significant decisions rather than every year. While legal requirements vary across countries, such flexibility can in the long term potentially undermine the democratic legitimacy of the associations by making it harder to e.g. stand for election. This is also the case when association membership is very limited: this naturally makes joining harder, management less transparent, and the continuing work of the organisation less resilient to changes in the lives of its formal members.

How democratic the organising *associations* are does not however seem to be in direct proportion to whether the organising teams of the events themselves can be considered democratic. A core team or committee for the next event is typically gathered by calling a meeting for everyone potentially interested in producing it and finding most people who would like to join in some suitable task or areas of responsibility. It is more common to be short on people than having to pick between applicants. Nevertheless, people are also turned down; why and how this happens and how it is experienced will likely be further explored in our research.

On-site tasks – the staff of the event – is typically a larger group than the organising committee. A proportion recurring in a few different contexts so far is about one event participant in six volunteering in some capacity. Volunteer management is an area of research in its own right and could provide complementing frames for exploring how volunteering at larp-cultural events is structured – and how that structure is experienced. Finally, at co-creative events, even participants who may not be formally volunteering are likely to perform physical and/or emotional labour.

Our fieldwork and ongoing design-related research studies whether, how, and how intentionally circumstances for the co-creative participation and sense of agency of the event participants is designed. We had not originally considered asking the same questions about the co-creative participation of team members and staff (on-site volunteers) but will be guided by the interviews and fieldwork.

Particularly interesting directions for research could include:

- Is the level of formal organisational and democratic structure in a non-profit association reflected in the formality on democratic structure of their organising committees?
- What kinds of trade-offs can be identified when it comes to e.g. hierarchy, formality, decision-making, and production managements processes in these volunteer environments? E.g., will extra work potentially caused by disorganised or ineffective committees be performed by the participants in a co-creative structure, and if so, how is it negotiated? How do event organisations weigh the benefits smaller, experienced, specialised and therefore selective event committees against their need to attract and train new volunteers?
- How are expectation-setting and culture-building around volunteer labour expressed in event communications and onsite behaviours?

3.3.5. Larp festivals and conventions as experienced

Our fieldwork at larp festivals and conventions has two goals: to document and attempt to understand the experience of the participant from the perspective of their perceived agency and sense of belonging at or being invited to participate in activities at the event as well as in the community and culture of the event as a whole; and to gain an understanding of how the physical

and social environment as constructed produce these outcomes. Many of the questions connected to the latter are connected to the design of the festivals, i.e. the intentions and skills of their organising teams, which will be discussed in the next chapter, and are the focus of an ongoing interview study. As our fieldwork at the events is also continuing, this subsection will sketch out some areas of interest in that work.

Larp festival vary significantly in their structure, foci, cultures, target audiences, and organisational structures. They are also different in what may be preliminarily described as their level of completeness. This quality describes how much content, labour, problem-solving, and space for creativity is intentionally left to the participants (rather than smoothly delivered to them, as a consumer experience would); but also to what degree the volunteer team and volunteer on-site staff seem to have been able to achieve what they have intended – in effect, how much labour, problem-solving, and good cheer may be required from the participants for the event to come off at all. Ambitions as to the level of productions vary, as do the “professionalism” of the team and staff²¹.

As discussed in Chapter 2, larp festivals and conventions (likely as a class, and certainly in the cases we study) do not have customers, but participants. The nature of this distinction and how, if at all, it is communicated to the prospective audience is an area of our study. Preliminarily we have observed that this quality of these events is not consistently made explicit on e.g. a webpage or in other communications, although it may be indirectly signalled, and many of these events do have codes of conduct that may cover aspects of this expectation.

Nevertheless, we have observed a joint will and a practical assumption amongst both organizers and participants that larp festivals and conventions – like larp – are created together. Participants arrive with an expectation of to what degree this is the case, and that original level-setting is corrected on site. A typical baseline for an acculturated participant could be to assist with small practical tasks like carrying chairs; to take responsibility for one’s own experience proactively; to actively contribute to the shared culture of the event and the positive experience of other participants; and to be prepared step in with more effort if an unexpected need arises. Whether high or low, the level of effort required is typically accepted if it is intentional but may be grumbled at if perceived as resulting from poor organisation. If a promise or agreement from the organising team relating to the event or its management is broken, however, participant reactions may be as strong as it would be in a consumer situation.

Team members have the highest decision-making power, and on-site volunteers wield authority based on their assumed knowledge about the procedures of the event. Participants will however also step in to solve problems, help with tasks, or care for each other, assuming a higher degree of civic responsibility than they might in other contexts. If the event organisation has a process in place, however, they are unlikely to interfere even if it is inefficient. How participants determine what level of co-creation is expected or appropriate at any given event is not yet clear; nor indeed how first-time participants pick up on such cultural expectations at all. Part of the answer in the case of the

²¹ Words like “professionalism” are uncomfortable in the volunteer and non-profit environment, but we are using it here to indicate that what is intended is not e.g. competence. A competent volunteer in a poorly conceived process will produce an underwhelming result, unless the team on the task has the agency to change the process.

events we have studied may relate to Nordic cultural norms around volunteering and collective work; others we hope to identify through participant observation and studying event websites.

As larp festivals and conventions always have numerous simultaneous events, be they larps, talks, workshops, social program, or something else, the joint attention of everyone participating is concentrated only rarely. It appears that the most important sites for establishing joint rules and norms are the website, an opening ceremony or welcome talk, and possibly an ending talk or a party. The verbal sources usually repeat established information, making event websites a valuable source for studying these processes. Many websites do have a section explaining how to be at the festival (often under headers like “community guideline”, “code of conduct”, or “practical”). Spelling out assumptions about shared responsibility explicitly is by no means the norm, although democratic or civic values do tend to be reflected.

In our initial discussion of larp festivals and conventions (Chapter 2), we have referred to “events and their communities” as intimately connected but not precisely overlapping entities. Many larp festivals and conventions will produce a sense of the specific participant community of that event, although this is not necessarily the case for those with a drop-in structure, where people come and go. Recurring events also have implied or actual communities of people who more or less regularly attend, as well as a smaller community of participants most invested in the continuation of the event, who are also most likely to volunteer to make it happen. At any of these levels, however, some sense of ownership will follow from the event’s co-created nature and the shared experiences it provides.

This community nature contributes to a sense of belonging, which may be palpable even to new participants. On the other hand, it also raises expectations of being or feeling included, which may intensify disappointment and alienation if that is not the case. Many of the events we study, and their communities, take an active interest in inclusion, and specific decisions, policies, or interventions are created to ensure different backgrounds, ages, identities, and experiences can feel that they belong. In practice, however, there is always a tension between a strong culture specific to the event, and the ability for any first-time participant to find their way into that bubble. Some events put a great deal of effort into onboarding newcomers and creating shared moments and experiences to ritualise the feeling of being on a shared journey. At their best, larp festivals and conventions are sites of care and recognition, offering places to contribute and to share in play; to do so as much or as little as one would like; and to be seen as a worthy and valuable community member.

In practice, of course, this does not always succeed. Even when interventions are successful and cultures constructive, social hierarchies, intersectional identities, and individual differences cannot be fully negated. Cultural differences between international participants, and the general difficulty of communicating unspoken norms, can create conflicts that flat, small, volunteer organisations have no procedures for handling. An event can also have as its target audience an existing or implied community (e.g. people of a particular style of larp; anyone who is a larp designer). If some members of that community cannot participate or do not feel welcome (for e.g. financial or social reasons), and the event is a significant locus for that community’s shared culture, public debate, or even decision-making, not having access may feel undemocratic.

In our interviews with organisers of festival-type events, their organisers have placed very different emphases on whose experiences they centre. Some conceive of their event as a space where new creators can present their larps with top-notch technical support; or offer those contributing new larps coaching through the design process. Some festivals want to ensure that a participant has full control over which specific larp they will play at the festival, where others think about the participant groups as a collective and design for their shared enjoyment of the time together. Sometimes festival organizers remember to mention a third group, the organizers themselves – and how important it is for them to support each other to make the unpaid labour sustainable.

Particularly interesting directions for research could include:

- How do people become excluded or are actively included? For example, many larp festivals have information about the physical accessibility of the spaces where their events take place, even as language about the accessibility of the larps on the programme may be severely lacking.
- How do events conceive of their communities and communities of their events? Can mapping a sense of ownership help us understand dynamics of belonging, inclusion, and co-creation?
- Does the event serve or address an existing community, and does it in that case serve some groups within that community more than others?
- If the event creates its own community, does it work to include relevant members of marginalized populations? Has that been successful?
- What kind of space, from the point of view of democratic values, does the festival website promise? How are these rules enacted and taught at the festival? Do the agreed-upon rules play out equally to all participants?
- What degree of co-creation does the convention or festival allow for or expect? How is this communicated and what kind of scaffolding is in place to enable it?
- Is the sphere of inclusion and belonging one that participants feel empowered to contribute to or intervene in? If so, how?

3.3.6. Larp festivals and conventions as arenas of democratic imagination

In preliminary summary, larp festivals and conventions are a site for thinking and playing about democracy, its values and institutions, by creating a platform for different voices and creative expressions. Participation in these events and particularly their organization can produce lived experiences democratic agency and shared civic responsibility, as well as forming critical counterpublics and democratic intimacies. Each festival allows a multitude of playful (cultural) publics to co-exist, as every larp engages participants in imaginative and co-creative worldbuilding.

As discussed in 3.2.5, playfulness, improvisation, subcultural events, and aesthetic experimentation can all create temporary worlds and communities, in which other or new kinds of time, norms, behaviours and relationships are possible. These kinds of spaces have been described as vitally important for building, sustaining, and renewing democracy by theorists and scholars approaching the issue from a range of academic disciplines and political perspectives (e.g. Graeber & Wengrow

2018; Ahmed 2006; Gouveia 2019; Harper 2020). Playful practices have the capacity to produce generative moments of disorientation (Ahmed 2006; Stone 2018), to offer sites for public freedom and happiness (Poulsen 2022), and to transform the democratic capacity of individuals and communities.

Larps specifically can become a site for expanding democratic imaginaries (Grasmo, Sihvonen and Stenros 2026, Gouveia 2019; Hutching and Giardino 2016), as every larp arguably provides at least in some sense a space in which the meeting of bodies, affects, and narratives in time and space is reoriented – a space for thinking differently (see Graeber & Wengrow 2018). Larp has also been used to concretely model societal systems or democratic processes (for examples see Johansson et al, 2025).

It follows that larp festivals and conventions are sites for expanding the democratic imagination: as sites of larps being played; of experiences of larps being processed and analysed; of other larps being imagined; as sites where the power dynamics, rules, and norms of hypothetical societies are proposed, and how they are produced by actions or can be modelled in interactions discussed. But also as alternative worlds in their own right, both as temporary but typically recurring sites with their own range of playful practices; and as communities that may exist in part or in whole, or as ideas, even when the event is not physically happening. Finally, these events and their communities have their own cultures, traditions, rules, structures, and norms, which are communally created, and in whose development and maintenance any participant can at least in theory play a part. Whether participants also experience this to be true remains to be seen.

Particularly interesting directions for research could include:

- How does it impact a participant to realize that with social experience design it is possible to change how human interaction works and how shared meaning is assigned?
- Do the mechanics for doing things different slip out of the larps and into the larp festival? Are they sometimes carried into other places, practices, and communities?
- What kinds of alternative worlds, heterotopias, liminal spaces, festival bubbles, etc. resonate strongest with participants? Why?
- How do participants speak of the step apart festivals offer? What does it mean to them?

3.3.7. Larp festivals and conventions as conduits of the democratic imagination

As it can be argued that the transformative dynamics discussed in 3.3.6. would primarily affect the perceived agency, sense of belonging, or capacity for democratic imagination of individuals or at best limited, local communities. The complexities of that question in relation to individual growth or cultural change can be sidestepped entirely by focusing instead on the direct transmission of ideas. If we accept that in democratic systems, some kind of role is played by a public sphere, and that ideas, concerns, and arguments can move from social and cultural peripheries to the centre of public discourse, we might ask how individual experiences and perspectives first become topics of common concern and reflection.

In the process of private conversations becoming collective concerns, cultural expression and meeting-places play a central role. The pamphlet and public coffeehouse of one era, may be the novel and internet platform of another. In any age, sites of particular interest in this process would be those where marginalised voices are speaking, or where concerns and reason-giving are

expressed in way that are not legible to establishment discourse, whether because of the tone or format, of unfamiliar cultural modes, or of the ideas themselves seeming absurd to their contemporary mainstream. For peripheral ideas to gain legitimacy and enter even the cultural public sphere, sites and communities capable of cultural translation are a necessary conduit.

In preliminary summary, larp festivals, as well as and both larp and literary sci-fi conventions, are such sites for the cultural expressions they engage with.

In addition to the direct experiences of temporary society created by the events themselves, as discussed above, conventions and festivals are also a cultural infrastructure for engaging seriously with alternative worlds – whether utopian or dystopian, playful or serious. Additionally, the larp-cultural events are distinct from those of sci-fi fandom in the experimental potential of the larp medium for collectively testing possible worlds as dynamic, inhabited systems.

In relation to marginalised genres and cultural expressions, festivals/conventions and their communities provide arenas for audience engagement, and provide paths to cultural legitimacy through nurturing artists, aesthetic theory, knowledge, and academic and professional frameworks. In this sense they have provided spaces of resistance against cultural homogenisation and way for more voices to gain legitimacy. The non-profit nature of many larp design and sci-fi fandom communities has allowed the world-imagining and society-simulating medium to become broadly available to non-professionals; to remain relatively unhindered by commercial appeal in selecting topics and artistic approaches; and to spread into societies where authoritarian elements or economic restrictions may control access to more public cultural forms (in the case of larp e.g. Palestine; see Anderson et al 2015).

In relation to an individual artwork, they are a site of translation where portrayals of hypothetical worlds, cultures, and social orders can enter the cultural public sphere, and the transformative, challenging, or even revolutionary ideas of a single author or a group of artists can be considered, analysed, and brought forward. This spread can occur through gradual cultural transmission via e.g. criticism or academic writing, or through direct organising around specific causes within fandom, gaming associations, or other communities related to the events.

- The processes described above straddle multiple fields. A systematic literature review charting how they have been approached within e.g. English literature, fandom studies (including fan activism), civil society research, and cultural and critical theory is required to shape an understanding of whether these approaches are directly applicable to our work or promising a direction of study.
- A better historical understanding of the role of embodied play practices in early sci-fi fandom (1920s-1970s) and early role-playing culture (1970s) would be a useful stepping stone toward worldbuilding-related leisure communities as sites of democratic ideation.

3.4. Towards a systematic model of democratic space

In this chapter, we have attempted to situate our work on larp festivals and conventions in relation to existing discourses on democratic spaces. The work we do, while mostly situated in game studies and design research, also needs to be firmly rooted in the fields where democratic engagement has

long been studied. The following is offered to further explicate our position and priorities connected to our continuing research.

Valuable contributions to the research directions suggested above can be found in academic fields including e.g. psychology, education, game studies, management studies, human-computer interaction, and festival and event studies. Highly relevant empirical work exists on an enormous range of co-creative social situations, e.g. democratic innovation spaces, village festivals, LAN parties, participatory design processes, artistic work, and non-profit volunteering.

Of our specific area of study, *larp festivals and conventions*, has on the other hand hardly been studied at all; there is not much research on analogue game conventions, and even fandom conventions are understudied. The *design of participation* is present implicitly in work across many academic disciplines. As will be discussed in Chapter 4, it exists in professional and artistic practice but has not yet been theorised as a field.

Finally, our research is conducted in the context of game studies, an interdisciplinary field that does not predetermine any approach. The nature of the project necessitates the democratic theory grounding, while the sociological, textual, and design approaches emerge from the background and training of these specific researchers.

Carefully focusing the research priorities to align with the goals, duration, and available resources of the project is obviously a practical necessity. We are triangulating the academic foci from three very different perspectives:

- 1) Working inward from democratic theories to identify which lenses are most relevant and practically useful given our contexts of playful temporary spaces; civil sector non-profit organising; artistic work; communities of practice; and the ongoing work of democracy.
- 2) Working forwards from scoping observations, field observation, and interviews
- 3) Working to document, analyse, and make legible approaches within Nordic Larp design discourse to the design of co-creative, participatory events.

Our fieldwork involves the study of people in rooms, of the design of the rooms, dynamics, and practices, and of how the interactions within them are facilitated. To understand this data, we must map out understudied or previously undocumented cultural, social, and historical aspects of both, and theorise the types of events as well as their functions. In the case of the events themselves, our research is moving from practice to theory – from existing events toward a model. In the case of the design research, we are moving from abstraction to practice, as we explore whether the design discourse espoused within the communities we study is operationalised in the design and production of the events.

Central to the structure of the Larpocracy project is the output of evidence-based and research-informed democratic design recommendations for organisers of game-cultural events. Contingent on the research supporting their generalisability or transferability, guidance for the application of these recommendations in other contexts, such as participatory democracy spaces, may also be produced. As we prioritise and delimit the research, the need to support practically useful recommendations must be kept front and centre.

Separately, our work will also contribute to policy recommendations. From the perspective of maximising societal impact, prioritising research in potentially significant directions can also be argued for.

The field and directions sketched out in section 3.3. are in part beyond the scope of our remit, and the rest far exceeds our resources. Our academic publications during and after the project do offer an opportunity to lay groundwork also for research in areas mapped out above but not possible to prioritise within the scope of this project. Even so, we have selected to include as much as possible of our thinking here, both to place it in the public record and in the interest of inviting academic collaboration.

The next stage of our research plan involves further developing and then systematising the model of democratic space whose foundations have been described in this chapter. As the results of the first phase of the fieldwork are analysed, and our understanding of democratic space iterated on, we will also proceed into the work of contextualising our work in the field of design theory. To us, the usefulness of a model for describing or analysing larp-cultural events as democratic spaces depends on whether it can guide a design process for making them more so.

In chapters 2 and 3 we have shown that “larp convention”, “larp festival”, and “democratic space” are dynamic concepts. Even assuming a single universal norm for fully democratic spaces was possible, our grounding in Nordic larp-based approaches to the design of experiences and participation (discussed in Chapter 4) suggests that the path to achieving it would be entirely contextual.

We do not believe that a normative approach would serve our purposes, nor indeed be useful to address democratic challenges, which themselves are highly context specific. Our ambition for our model of democratic space is to provide a conceptual framework in support of analysing existing spaces and/or goal setting for new or changed ones. To reduce complexity, it will be focused on the scale of humans in rooms, and on the qualities, aspects, and dilemmas connected to creating these spaces and interacting in them that our research has identified as especially important.

The next chapter discusses the *bespoke design* approach of Nordic Larp; how it applies to the design of experiences in general; and the way this discourse community conceptualises enabling participation and co-creation. While we have hypothesised that this community’s holistic approach to creating experiences is systematic enough to provide the basis for a design language of human participation, constructing one in the next year is obviously not feasible. What we hope to achieve is a model for understanding the key design choices involved in the creation of a participatory democratic space; and vice versa, to show what kinds of democratic spaces are enabled or undermined by specific choices in an event’s design.

It does not seem at this time that this process would necessitate significant further research into the cultural and democratic functions of the kinds of events we study; nor are we likely to be able to produce deep work on the civil society aspects of non-profit volunteer gathering places of this nature. Our preliminary results, sketched out in section 3.3. above, do however suggest that these research directions might provide a basis for important and specifically actionable policy recommendations. We will accommodate as much of that work as we can into the scope of this project.

4. Designing Larp Festivals as Democratic Spaces

4.1 Larp design as bespoke experience design

4.1.1. Events, experiences, and social interactions as objects of design

The term “experience design” has long been used as shorthand for “user experience design” (UX), the design of interfaces and services with an active awareness of the users’ interactions with and behaviours relative to these systems. Another influential usage was suggested by designer Tim Brown (2008), describing a market for sophisticated, “emotionally satisfying and meaningful” experiences, “complex combinations of products, services, spaces, and information”. In his book on design thinking (Brown & Katz 2009), he would ultimately also position experience design “as a stage in a design thinking research and prototyping practice” (Burickson 2023, 16).

In parallel with these, an entirely separate meaning of experience design has emerged in the last two decades among practitioners across a variety of disciplines involved in different ways with creating events and human encounters. Those describing themselves as experience designers work in shaping and curating a great variety of things, some of which, like artistic performances or immersive media, fit easily into an everyday sense of what a designed experience might be. But the new conceptualisation of experience design extends to include every kind of space somehow involving relational presence and the direction of sensory attention: from museum exhibits to restaurants; from theme parks to healthcare appointments; from marketing events for major brands to in-person education in the elementary school classroom.

In *Experience Design. A Participatory Manifesto*, Abraham Burickson’s (2023) useful guide to this design approach, he describes how these differing practices relate to each other: “Their discoveries speak to each other, together developing a practice whose tools are at once very new and as old as humanity. This practice is experience design. It connects these disciplines, and erodes the lines between them” (ibid, xiv). Furthermore, he explains how an experiential outcome is the starting point of the design process:

Experience design comprehends the things we make, the systems we develop, the communities we facilitate as vessels for experience. Experience designers begin with the experience they wish to create and work backward from there. (Burickson 2023, xiii).

Burickson specifically positions experience design as something fundamentally different from the trivial interactivity or symbolic participation that are also commonly employed in contemporary contexts such as marketing, immersive entertainment, and relational art. The central goal is not to impress a receiver with intense sensory stimuli, or a temporary upending of the traditional roles and power structures within a medium, but to design for the participation and potentially the transformation of the participant. This requires humility with respect for the participants’ backgrounds and specific current situation, and an understanding of the value of their own contributions to their experience – potentially in advance as co-designers, and inevitably during their embodied participation.

For this reason, both Burickson’s manifesto and the many designers whose work he is citing, require the experience designer to centre their projects and processes around empathy, relational

engagement, and inclusion. (Burickson 2023) Burickson does not fully define his usage of “inclusion”, but across the book it can be summarised as extending or focusing the relevance of one’s work to people somehow different from oneself, sometimes expressed as deep listening, at other times as co-design. The work of inclusion may also include the continuing effort to relate to the participant of an experience, or the user of a system, product, or service, as co-equal in status and artistic capability to the designer.

4.1.2. Nordic Larp as a design discourse

In the formalised documentation and teaching larp design that has grown out of the Nordic larp design community (exemplified for instance in the textbook *Larp Design*, Koljonen et al 2019), each larp is understood as an independent, original work. This means that all aspects of the larp (e.g. form, content, participation patterns) are made in service of the work’s *artistic vision*, which may be conceptualised as *design goals*. Nordic larps are discussed as *bespoke design*, in the sense that design choices are made specifically with that particular larp in mind. This is contrasted to larp *traditions*, which may strive e.g. towards a generic rule set that can be used in any larp regardless of the setting, theme, goals; produce larps set in a single recurring world; or iterate on earlier larps within a shared frame of locally acceptable aesthetics.

The Nordic larp design tradition is also a tradition, in the sense that it has some shared values, assumptions, and narratives about itself, as well as typical and customary ways-of-doing and solutions to known challenges. However, in this tradition, each larp is considered an individual work, whose creators are free to determine all its formal qualities. Earlier work is a key influence, but the participant-audience communities in question generally expect at least some aspects of each larp to be novel and are also open to the intentionally experimental.

Nordic larp emerged when the region’s nascent avant-garde larp communities in the 1990s attempted to break out of the larp mainstream (see Stenros & Montola 2010; Johansson et al 2025). Larp was understood at the time as a kind of play culture developed from the commercial entertainment medium of tabletop role-playing games, or at best as a kind of participatory folk art. Participant communities preferring specific genres or specific interaction styles (e.g. combat) felt the form to be inherently suitable only for those. Some proportion of larp makers and their players saw another potential, and in the Nordics, early internet penetration as well as the existing infrastructure of non-profit organisation enabled local collectives interested in developing the medium to coalesce into a movement (Johansson et al 2025). Its international nature and the vast geographic distances of the Nordics necessitated a great deal of written interaction, specifically in English, in media ranging from fanzines and online fora to the Knutepunkt convention’s book-length anthologies of theoretical, para-academic and academic writing (Torner 2018). Similar artistic developments having taken place elsewhere, many of those larp communities and design collectives would eventually find their way into the “Nordic” communities and join the rapidly internationalising discourse on larp making.

Early Nordic larp discourse had as its starting assumption that larp was a valid cultural expression suited to any topic just as literature or film can be, but the question of whether it should be considered an art form has not been resolved. It seems likely that this orientation towards participatory art and the growing numbers of larp makers with art school backgrounds supported the continuing expectation of originality and openness to experimentation within the larp community.

Larp work was produced in museum contexts very early (Stenros 2010), but there was also a tension between larpmakers and the institutional structures of contemporary art. Larpmakers often operated from a counter-cultural, DIY position (see Johansson et al 2025), while the artworld of the late 1990s was only cautiously starting to engage with game art in the digital sphere. The Nordic larp discourse community would eventually attract a great number of artistic practitioners who saw its approach as fruitful for relational art practice, as well as producing larpmakers who collaborate with contemporary artists (see e.g, Wilk 2024, Pogačar & Rosenbluth 2024, McKinnon-Little 2019, Tank 2019). That this has been normalised over time is reflected e.g. in recent or ongoing artistic research involving or focused exclusively on larp at Nordic universities (e.g. Lipsyc 2024, Rydberg, n.d).

Easier for larpmakers to agree on was the conceptualisation of creating bespoke larps as a process of *larp design*. Game design was one obvious influence, especially as this was the conceptualization of the dominant online community for serious role-playing at this time, *The Forge* (see White 2020). A third wave of academic game studies emerging at this time, and particularly strong in the Nordics (Stenros & Kultima 2018), would also connect early larp theorists with an intellectual tradition at that time very invested in digital games and similar, mechanically oriented disciplines. Just as many larp designers and players brought with them experiences from art schools, however, others at this time ended up working for tech startups, in service design, business strategy, urban planning, or other fields strongly affected by the boom in design thinking approaches at the start of the millennium. In the first decade of the millennium, as the individually experimental but collectively systematic approaches of Nordic Larp practitioners were documented and theorised, it was perhaps inevitable that they should be conceptualised in terms of *design choices*.

An important step in the formalization of this understanding was *The Mixing Desk of Larp* (Andresen & Nielsen 2013; Stenros, Andresen, & Nielsen 2016), a design tool and a thing-to-think-with originally developed for the Larpwriter Summer School in 2012. The Mixing Desk Model illustrates a selection of the design opportunities available to a larp designer. These are depicted as moving “faders” on a mixing desk with the ends of each scale representing mutually exclusive theoretical positions, e.g. between a larp’s interaction style being fully verbal or fully physical, or its scenography being entirely realistic or entirely symbolic. Most larps will fall somewhere in between for each choice.

The purpose of the Mixing Desk was to help teach design vocabulary, and to support designers in making conscious choices (Andresen & Nielsen 2013). Its starting point is that all choices are valid but serve different purposes and may have different consequences not just for the play experience but also elsewhere on the Mixing Desk. Central to its development was reflecting not just on existing Nordic larps, but also on how larps in other traditions could be described and understood.

While the specific faders of the Mixing Desk reflect the artistic concerns of its time, and it was never intended to be used in practical larp design processes, it was pedagogically effective. In addition to the approximately 280 larp design students, teachers, and community volunteers engaged with the summer school directly (M. Nielsen, personal communication 27 Jan 2026), it was presented in convention contexts, published in a Knutepunkt book, and likely catalysed or at least contributed to a practice of approaching larp design analytically.

In the following decade, the same need to be able to teach larp design more efficiently than through the combination of informal apprenticeships (i.e., volunteering on projects) and trial and error has

led to a gradual systematisation of design documentation within the discourse. Any larp designer engaging with the discourse can have access not just to case studies but to conceptual tools helping make sense of them. There is a shared toolbox of mechanics and design elements to choose from, which can be understood as a design language.

By 2024, artists and larp designers Andrea Lindwall and Gabriel Widing could plausibly claim that viewing larp-making as a design practice was a hegemonic position within larp discourse. In what was admittedly an intentional provocation, their Knutepunkt convention book article described the development in exaggerated terms as a rhetorical device to make some very well-observed critiques. Interaction design is intended to smooth out disagreement, while culture and artforms develop “through cultural and subcultural clashes.” Focusing overly on design risks making larps easily digestible rather than open for multiple interpretations and produces work that is “predictable and shallow”. Instead, larp discourse should reflect that larps can be created in many ways, including artistic processes, and “bring back dialectics” (Nordwall & Widing 2024)²².

Although we view Nordwall & Widing’s imagery of the outcomes of an over-reliance on design thinking as primarily rhetorical than as descriptions of actual larp project existing in the world, they are correct that design processes as taught to e.g. interaction designers – optimised for efficiency at all levels – would likely not produce very interesting larps. That is however not how larp designers operate.

Describing and theorising the relationship between art, craft, and design in larp-making is relevant to our continuing research. While we do not expect to have finished that work within this project, some first thoughts about what is designed in the design of a co-created experience, and how that connects to the issues of democratic space, are sketched out below.

4.1.3. Larp design as the design of participation

Larps regularly take place in magic schools, on spaceships, in different historical eras, and all kinds of alternative worlds. Participants may embody characters who can turn invisible or do telepathy, are part of traditional four-person marriages, worship new gods, serve on vampire councils, or inhabit worlds where queerphobia or even the concept of sexual violence just do not exist.

Creating and participating in larps demonstrates, in a particularly practical manner, that not only is reality socially constructed: changing ‘reality’ through socially constructing it in a different manner is surprisingly easy (see Searle 1995; Montola 2012; Stenros 2015). In this understanding, the object of larp design is not creating “a game” or “a role-play experience” but creating a framework within which a specific fictional and temporary social reality can be collectively brought into being by the participating players.

All game design operates in this way in relation to the game-as-played. Katie Salen and Eric Zimmerman (2004, 327) have discussed the idea of *second order design*, that a “game designer only *indirectly* designs the player’s experience, by *directly* designing the rules.” This would arguably be

²² Of the authors of this report, Tampere University researchers Johanna Koljonen, Jaakko Stenros, and Hanne Grasmø have all been involved in establishing larp design within the Nordic larp discourse, and one phrase of Koljonen’s is directly referenced in Nordwall & Widing’s essay “Against Design”. It should therefore be clarified that interactions around the text were friendly, playful, and immediately fruitful; and that the ensuing conversations were a step toward clarifying our current thinking about the design of participation.

true of any process or object that only acquires meaning and function through active use, larps being no exception. In complexity, and likely in kind, larp design is however subtly different from game design overall.

As with any game with a strong narrative component, game design (of dynamics, interactions, and rules) and writing (creating the setting, arena, situations, characters, and central plot points) is included in the creation of a larp. In comparison with e.g. a digital game, the participant in a larp usually has significantly more room for interpretation (e.g. of the character they play), improvisation (e.g. of their lines and actions) and active co-creation of the world through e.g. collaboratively fleshing out details of the fiction or guiding emerging storylines in preferred directions. The artistic outcomes of a larp depend not just on the aesthetic qualities enabled by that second-order participatory framework, but also on its *playability*.

'Playability' has several meanings in game studies (these will not be covered here). Its use within Nordic larp discourse has not been specifically defined but can usefully be understood as a combination of two aspects. The minimum playability requirement is that it is physically and socially *possible* to embody and enact the potential world inherent in the work, as well as all aspects of the character specifically required by the design for the larp to function as intended.

Once this functional playability is achieved, playability in a larp would also mean that the design supports participant co-creation. "Supporting co-creation" is our headline for a category of qualities related to playability including at least the following: establishing or communicating a shared artistic vision; providing relevant creative restrictions; ensuring that the repertoire of actions available to the player in the game, and/or to their character in the fiction, provide appropriate agency to meaningfully impact the experience and the story; while simultaneously ensuring this agency is not undermined by design choices negatively affecting the state of the individual participant or trust within the participant group.

In practice this means that in the Nordic tradition, "larp design" extends beyond designing the runtime of the larp, to designing the circumstances in which it is played: the preparatory processes of the participant; collective onboarding, workshops, briefing of information, or rehearsals of necessary skills or routines; tools for fluid consent negotiations and communicating boundaries; processes for handling participant dissatisfaction, social chafing, or strong emotional reactions; transitions in and out of the temporary world and of the embodied characters; collective and individual processes for narrativizing the experience – both as lived and as played – and for meaning-making around them; and sometimes to support the translation and integration of new social relationships and communities from the temporary sphere of the player ensemble into the everyday sphere of daily life.

The design of the full participant experience in this manner cannot be reduced merely to a user journey. In service design tradition centring consumers, a good user experience may be one reducing friction and predictably inviting or manipulating them to spend money. In a co-creative setting, each player journey should support the agency and informed consent of all participants. Within the agreed-upon frame and artistic vision, it should also leave a significant proportion of the work undetermined, to be filled in by the participants through co-created play.

We would argue that in the context of a larp, then, “designing the experience” is shorthand for “designing the ability to, and appropriate circumstances for, participating in this specific co-creative experience”, or just *designing participation*. Specifically, that participation is designed not in service of a process of agreement and assimilation, but in service of co-creation, with a contextual focus on agency, consent, and navigating conflicting participant goals and circumstances. The attention paid in this practice to the circumstances of the individual participant within the collective situation is fundamentally contrary to the understanding of design as optimisation that underlies the critique by Nordwall and Widing (2024) discussed in the previous section. On the contrary, nurturing or supporting participation through careful choices is a way of making a space of ambiguities, tensions, and artistic exploration possible and accessible to more people.

4.1.4. ‘Experience design’ within Nordic larp discourse

In Nordic larp design discourse, the term ‘experience design’ has become increasingly common in the last decade. It is used within the discourse in reference to all aspects of creating and producing a larp that are not directly concerned with the fiction, game mechanics, or embodied portrayal of roles during the larp’s runtime. It is also used by many larp designers outside the larp design context to describe the skillset they have acquired through larpmaking. The latter maps precisely onto the kind of understanding of experience design of which e.g. Burickson (2023) is a proponent. The validity of this skillset in other professional settings related to experiences in co-creative places has been confirmed by their direct usefulness in fields such as the design of theme parks (Jahromi 2022), museums (Rodley 2025), and immersive entertainment such as theatre performances and escape rooms (e.g. Law 2022).

The Nordic larp discourse’s internal understanding of experience design is however subtly different, in that it is typically viewed as only a supporting – although central – element of larp design. To many larp designers and participant players, the appeal of a specific larp springs largely from the specifics of its temporary fiction, which are the product of other specialties such as world-building, the writing of dynamic situations and compelling characters, and the design of elegant rules systems for e.g. plot negotiation and combat simulation. Talking about experience design became more common as out-of-character elements considered necessary for the role-playing itself to be successful, such as workshops and onboarding processes, increased in complexity. But as practice, experience design (whether in its usage among other experience designers, or the more participation-enabling sense used by larp designers), is in larpmaking often taken for granted.

If all elements of the larp are aligned with the same goals, the full experience will be well-designed. Everyone on a larp’s team should have the skillset to some degree, but it is only noticed in its absence. In most larp cultures, including many participating in Nordic larp discourse, experience design is therefore either integrated into the larp’s game design, communication, and practical production roles, or not explicitly engaged with. The latter is especially typical for larp designers working within strong traditions, where players have similar expectations, and where the format, style, and practical aspects of the events are not expected to differ widely even when the content does. In such contexts, a well-functioning experience design can be reproduced with only minimal changes across events.

When experience design is discussed, however, it is understood through the lense of bespoke larp design. It is assumed that every aspect of a larp’s form and content, as well as its material and social

aspects, will impact their play experience and its connected meaning-making. Therefore, they should all – at least theoretically – be the product of an intentional process. The function, necessity, and consequences of all elements in play during the runtime of the larp should be considered.

Through a game design lens, a list of such elements would include things like larp mechanics, player characters, and pacing. In the complex physical and social environments of larp, however, the playability of an embodied situation is also affected by seemingly incidental factors. Has the player eaten enough? Does the lighting of the main space lend itself to reading or to hiding? Is it too cold to be wearing a summer dress? How are the acoustics? These kinds of questions are not specific to larp, and could be asked e.g. of the design of a wedding party. In a participatory and co-creative medium, however, they directly impact the outcomes. A wedding will typically result in a marriage even if guests are cold and hungry, but if players are miserable, or indeed physically unable to perform actions required for the larp's plot events to progress, the work will fail or not meaningfully exist. These aspects of the larp experience become the responsibility of the designer because they are directly impacted through design choices such as story elements, meal schedules, and cultural traditions of the fictional culture.

It gets even more complicated, as larp designers have found that the state of the participant and their ability to meaningfully participate may also be affected by events outside the runtime (when characters are being portrayed). If the larp is not what some participants they expected and prepared for, this cannot be solved by changing the larp. Instead, communications and interactions in advance of the event should have been designed differently. Wider social, societal, and cultural dynamics will also affect the play experience. E.g. if younger or underprivileged audience members cannot afford to participate, but player diversity is important to the play experience, a progressive pricing structure and different outreach strategies may be designed.

Through testing, Nordic larp has established that all of these elements are addressable through design, an approach often phrased as *everything is a designable surface* (Koljonen 2020). That anything and everything connected to an experience can be approached as design is not a call to try to control every aspect. It is literally impossible – and would perhaps risk creating a counterproductively polished experience.

Instead, elegance in the design of an experience is about enabling the desired interaction outcomes and processes through as few choices, elements, and rules as possible. Neither is the start of the process in practice infinite possible choices, as the best possible circumstances for that specific act of co-creation must be achieved in a way that is feasible within the budget, the time of the organising team, the physical constraints of the venue, and the realistically available preparation time of the potential participants, as well as the preferences and abilities of the specific ticket-holders.

4.2. Studying the design of larp festivals and conventions

4.2.1 Studying larp design for participation

The starting point for this research project was our hypothesis that the previously discussed approaches to the design of events and experiences may be particularly fruitful in the context of e.g. democratic innovation processes, where multiple perspectives being heard and accommodated was

a concern. Evaluating that assumption in the context of the larps themselves was however not deemed feasible.

Larps layer temporary circumstances and social roles – some of them fictional – atop each other, making it irresolvably complex to extricate which behaviours are produced by the participation structures and which contributed by the players in response to a fictional prompt, to some personal yearning rationalised through the character’s goals, or even to a perceived weakness in the underlying design. Additionally, larps can generally not be meaningfully studied from the outside. Studying participants is challenging because of how narratives are retroactively constructed around fragments of lived experience, while studying the larp by participating in them comes with its own methodological problems (for both aspects, see Brind 2022).

Given that the use of larp-design skills in unrelated professional contexts has been widely reported, we have however further hypothesised that qualities of larp and larp design may be shaping or colouring how its practitioners design other kinds of experiences in non-larp contexts. We identified conventions and festivals as a promising field of study, especially in the Nordic larp tradition, in which convention organisers are often larp designers, and the design discourse is explicitly and broadly engaged with.

Additionally, conventions and festivals are similar to larp in that they are contained, temporary experiences; approached by participants with specific expectations; with codes of conduct and other rules; in which participants are not only users but co-creators of an experience in which norms, values, behaviours, and social roles may differ from daily life. Studying conventions and festivals means we can study the same designers, as well as the same, playful communities, but in out-of-character interactions, in situations that are special, without being understood as fictional.

In the next phase of our work, we will venture to recontextualise and translate our sector-specific understanding of larp design from both practitioner and game studies perspectives into the conceptual languages of design research and design theory. That work is yet to begin, but below we are mapping out some of our core questions and approaches.

4.2.2 “Conrunning” as tradition, craft, or design?

It is clearly *possible* to approaching the creation of a larp festival, larp convention, or other larp-cultural event as a design process, given that entire professional fields (e.g. event design; wedding planning; immersive brand-activations) are doing very similar things. It is also clear that putting together a festival or convention does not *require* that type of creative structure, any more than a birthday party or a professional conference would. Most people participate in events occasionally, and some will have helped with making or hosting them. Recreating a familiar and suitable format from experience and observation with as few changes as possible is a very reasonable approach. It is how most people learn to make events, and indeed how expertise in the field is most commonly accrued.

From the perspective of larp design practice, we have previously argued that *design is the opposite of tradition* (see eg. Kangas et al 2024, p. 8). We want to be very clear that approaching event production from a design perspective is not a qualitatively “better” way than working within a tradition; it is a different way. We understand the distinction in terms of the approach to the goals and process, i.e. what categories of elements of an event can be changed, and what is the process by

which the vision is identified and its constitutive elements chosen. Working in a tradition does not preclude gradual iteration or even the (re)designing of elements when circumstances require it. In a traditional process, the goal is producing the best feasible version of a familiar and shared ideal type, while a design approach involves a willingness to reconsider form and traditional practices entirely in the service of a better outcome or even a better process.

The distinction is also not about skill. A craftsman who has come by their experience within a tradition may have the skills and ability to perform the steps of a design process, or to masterfully implement the decisions – just not the inclination, if doing so is not meaningful, necessary, or relevant to them and their audiences.

Within existing traditions, where events are (re)created and produced by copying tried-and-true approaches in the ways expected by the participants, innovation tends to be opportunistic and incremental. The creators will have a fairly uniform idea of the goal of the event, and their audiences may be unwilling to engage with any changes. Individual elements are then typically improved within the existing paradigm, e.g. by identifying best practices. In these contexts, innovation mostly happens when a significant cultural change gives rise to new expectations or possibilities – or when production reality shifts (for example, the traditional venue space is no longer available).

On the other hand, working in a strong tradition speeds up many processes, as significantly fewer choices need to be considered. The design space shrinks, as a much narrower scope of possible choices are considered, or even legible. Much less communication is needed within teams, and events and their participants, if most things are recognizable and familiar.

The processes and outcomes of e.g. organising an event can appear very similar regardless of whether design or tradition is the underlying principle. This is especially the case for very experienced organisers, as much of the knowledge involved is tacit, and decisions may be experienced as intuitive or automatic. Part of our research concerns itself with exploring processes of *reflective practice* (Schön 1992) and *designerly knowing* (Cross 2001) in convention organising practice.

Knowing how to do something and being able to explain it or reflect on it in words are not the same thing. Conceptual tools, like having words for the different actions, decisions, and observations involved in a skill, make it possible to learn from the experiences of others without working side by side. At the same time, conceptual frameworks inevitable frame understanding.

We are interested in comparing and contrasting this to how knowledge is conceptualised in traditional expressions, such as crafts, as the ways of accruing the relevant skills have until relatively recently been similarly practice-oriented in larp design too. Perhaps the distinctions between experience design in tech-oriented discourse and in larp-cultural contexts could be better understood by e.g. approaching human participation as a material.

Within convention organising specifically, a significant traditionally oriented expert community offers fascinating comparative opportunities. Organised sci-fi fandom has documented the craft of ‘conrunning’ (planning, producing and organising fandom conventions) for a very long time. SMOFcon, a training event for convention organisers, has been organised annually since 1984. The conrunning community is extremely invested in developing their craft and sharing best practices, but

participating audiences of both local and international events tend to be formally conservative. Innovation is instead directed toward areas like accessibility and inclusion²³.

At this point in time, with our fieldwork and analysis still ongoing, it is unclear how conscious the design of larp festivals and conventions as experiences actually is, and whether indeed they are mostly produced in a tradition. Prior to the beginning of the Larpocracy project we had noticed instances of larp conventions implementing designed interventions or applying interaction tools previously used in larps in order to make participation easier, facilitate a feeling of community, or smooth communal interactions. It is yet too early to say whether this is a question of larp design elements slipping into the community that surrounds them through unreflected cultural transmission, or the product of systematic experience design for participation. It is also uncertain whether any design interventions that may be intentional are having the intended effect.

Whether the events in our fieldwork are systematically designed or recreated within a tradition, and whether or not the way they are organised produced the intended participant experiences, the fieldwork will help us understand non-profit volunteer organizing of participatory and playful spaces.

And regardless of whether concepts from Nordic larp discourse are engaged with in the design of these events, we are already finding it useful in *describing* them. The conceptual language of larp design, developed to help designers verbalise their tacit knowledge, benefit from the experience of others, and use their own skills with intention, includes a great many approaches applicable to the design of any event. Being able to describe the choices involved in event-planning and event production processes is a necessity for being able at the end of this project to give any evidence-based recommendations at all.

In the next sections, we discuss the distinction between a design language and a language describing design, and the next steps toward systematising a model for the design of democratic spaces.

4.3. Towards a Design Language for larp-cultural events

4.3.1 Event Design conceptualised as choices and consequences

As discussed in chapter 2, many very different kinds of events that are recognised as larp festivals and conventions, and variety within the same type of events is significant²⁴. Every event (or event type) can be understood as clusters of culturally conventional design elements. This means that there are essential qualities necessary for making it identifiable the same event or event type within a particular context. Whether an event is produced to an existing model or designed from scratch, a necessary step exists of identifying or selecting and agreeing on non-negotiable elements of the design vision, base assumptions, and/or design values.

It follows that conventions and festivals can be locally defined as a field expressed as design choices within which the event is still recognisable as belonging to that category. Recognizing which

²³ These general comments are based on observations and conversations at SMOFcon in Stockholm on 5-6 Dec 2025.

²⁴ There are even examples where the same event can change significantly year to year. A notable example is Knutepunkt, which travels the Nordic countries. While some organisers recur every fourth year, in practice a new group of experience designers takes on the project yearly.

elements can be changed and which cannot while remaining a member of a type of event helps map the limits of the design space. Naming the different aspect that can be changed helps in explicating possibilities within the design space. This is the foundation of a design language.

Our preliminary work demonstrates that in the context of designing a larp festival or convention, the designable surfaces are all those choices that are, at least in theory, addressable by the organising team affecting the outcome.

Choices that cannot be made and choices that do not affect the outcome are not part of the practical design space. Not making a choice, intentionally following a traditional or otherwise shared assumption, or making a choice because of a practical circumstance are also choices. As was discussed in the previous section, although in experience design everything is theoretically a designable surface, the practical process cannot be infinite. Offering useful advice to organisers of events will likely require providing a process for intentionally defining and prioritising choices without compromising on the democratic design goals.

Beginning to chart this design space and build a design language, we will be tapping into a long tradition. It starts with Christopher Alexander's *A Timeless Way of Building* (1979), which explored draft a pattern language for architecture. The book has been extremely influential not just in architecture, but much more widely. The several endeavours in game studies to develop design languages for game design most centrally include *Patterns in Game Design* (Björk & Holopainen 2005), directly building on Alexander. Other takes on charting the space of game design that may prove helpful to our approach include *A Game Design Vocabulary* (Anthropy & Clark 2014) and *The Art of Game Design: A Book of Lenses* (Schell 2008).

4.3.2. Slicing “everything” into “designable surfaces”

In practice, identifying which kinds of elements, choices, circumstances, or materials to be intentional about and to internally align, is typically an iterative process that experienced practitioners may experience as intuitive or automatic. To describe, formalise, or teach it, however, structured perspectives are a helpful lens. Below, we offer examples of three such lenses, with examples of such “designable surfaces”: those common to most physical events; those considering an event as separate a temporary reality with shared culture for participants to step into together; and aspects of the design in service of participation.

Most designable surfaces would be shared by any physical event. On a timeline of the participant experience, stretching from the moment they find out about it until long after it is over, these may include all aspects of e.g.

- Participant Selection and self-selection
 - Announcement and communication
 - Content, tone, timing, channels, targeting
 - Expectation management
 - Stating, implying, and suggesting the event's nature (including e.g. structure, level of formality, comfort levels) and intended culture (e.g. expectations on participants, hierarchies)
 - Ticketing

- What kinds of tickets are available, how, when, and at what prices; how are they allocated if demand surpasses supply?
- The physical event
 - Venue, logistics, transportation, accessibility, arriving and leaving, layout, decor
 - The temporal structure of the event
 - beginning/end, schedule slots, planning of human movement during event, temporal zoning
- Procedures for management, staffing, and running of the event
- What happens afterwards
 - Outcomes, feedback
 - Processes for striking the event (packing down, logistics, cleaning)

Another design level can be understood as creating the framework and necessary circumstances for the event as a shared experience: considering what is required for participants to co-create and experience the same temporary world. Before this work can be done, some kind of unifying design framework – e.g. *vision*, *aesthetic*, *narrative*, or *design goal* – has been arrived at.

Essentially, this 'vision' is any set of design goals simply expressed design goals answering a question along the lines of “what kind of experience will the participants have?”: e.g. “a magical wedding, that all guests will remember for the rest of their lives”, or “every participant will feel they have been heard, and that they have contributed meaningfully to local democracy”. It is then used as the selective criteria. The choices made in the event’s design, production, and facilitation should on the one hand *enable this experience for all participants*; on the other their consequences and dynamic relationship should be evaluated to ensure that choices or circumstances do not *unintentionally counteract it*.

Shared or intended/strived-for culture:

- Explicit *and implicit* values and norms
 - Code of conduct
 - Rules
- Attitudes to and practices related to hierarchies
 - Pricing
 - Organisation of labour; distribution of responsibilities
 - Dynamics of power and agency between organizers and participants
 - Shared expectations
 - Local cultural expressions or practices
- Boundaries of the event as a shared experience (magic circle)
 - Moments and procedures entering and exiting the experience
 - Sense of welcome, of understanding what to do and where to go
 - Symbols or actions signalling belonging
- Content
 - Curation of programme
 - Design of playful experiences and smaller temporal experiences (e.g. larps, meals, parties) inside the event
- Afterlife (shaping the memory, narrative, and community produced by the event)

- Post-event communications
- Ways of reflecting on the experience, whether to reminisce or celebrate, or to learn, critique, process, rectify
- Ways of maintaining relationships

A third level of design is that of design elements enabling participation: considering what state they would need to be in to co-create that experience for themselves and each other. Considering these aspects is of particular importance in co-creative, educational, and playful contexts. Play, learning, problem-solving, shared creativity, and arguably even interacting with new people, implies a certain amount of cognitive effort and social risk.

Tolerances for these risks vary individually and contextually, as do the available energy and executive capacity. On a group level, however, these dynamics are relatively predictable: e.g. hungry participants are less cognitively capable; a physical layout or lighting scheme that makes people feel exposed makes them less likely to fill the dancefloor.

On the structural level, these issues can be considered in the planning stages, when one is still designing for a hypothetical audience. At the point the participants are specific individuals, choices can further be fine-tuned. A separate design process can be identified for handling resource-intensive outlier needs on an individual basis, but having e.g. an accessibility plan does not negate the need for considering the physical, social, and emotional effects of participation in an event on the participant group as a collective.

In practice, this also requires the event design and the design of the shared experience to be in place, as making choices requires knowing what is being participated in. In co-creative contexts, however, the design processes of those too levels can also be participatory; in that case, those processes themselves will naturally first be designed.

Enabling participation is a useful filter for reflecting on unintended consequences of choices made on the other levels. Below are some very few examples:

- Curation
 - Are themes and content types balanced between those likely to give energy and those likely to cost energy?
 - Are participants able to self-select between programmes and activities for pacing and still have the meaningful, full experience?
 - Are there time slots or areas that remained undesigned or aspects of the event that are uncurated, to enable spontaneous creativity?
- Spatial
 - Is there a variety of spaces available for different modes of engagement and sensory input?
 - Do layouts and decor in core spaces support the practicalities of participation (e.g. is it possible for everyone to hear each other?), as well as the affective experience of existing in them (e.g. does the room make people feel small?)
- Cultural onboarding and belonging
 - How do new participants learn how things are done at the event+

- Are participants, including newcomers, to opt into and out of activities that may feel uncomfortable, without loss of social stature?
- Facilitating interactions
 - Cultures, procedures, or rituals making collaboration or interacting with strangers easier
 - Methods of facilitating reflective conversations
 - How are limited resources like participation in larps or conference sessions distributed?

After slicing the design space of larp festivals into understandable and designable parts, the next step is to use this dismantling as a basis for starting to build a model that aids design. We turn to that next.

4.3.3. Gathering the building blocks of democratic event design

The purpose of our models and resources for democratic event design would be to help organisers prioritise between the theoretically infinite design choices by providing guidance to which of them are most impactful, and support in analysing the consequences of their decisions. Achieving the first requires a useful and accessible model of what democratic space means in the context of these events; for the second, an accessible model of how interactions in spaces are shaped by their physical and social design is needed. As the results of our fieldwork emerge, we will proceed to iterate on our modelling. Other sources of both conceptual input and validation will be the existing literature on e.g. experience design and the design of democratic innovation.

Our preliminary understanding is that some of the experience design approaches within the practitioner communities shaping Nordic larp discourse are unusual. If that proves to be the case, our process may contribute to design theory overall. Novel design insights are however not a goal in themselves. Our proposed toolkit may well prove to be a new pedagogical approach to upskilling event organisers through making lessons from existing design research accessible and applicable. This would be a very positive outcome, as the principles would be thoroughly validated.

As we begin to move forwards, we need to combine the vocabulary of the design language of larp festivals that we are creating with an understanding of democratic spaces (developed in chapter 2). If democracy-related goals, such as supporting democratic engagement or building democratic skills, are included as a goal in the vision level of design – as is in the interests of the Larpocracy project – then that integration needs to be thorough. This practical model, that is built around creating larp-cultural events that function as democratic spaces, needs to support decision making in event design processes.

One possible way of presenting this is to follow in the footsteps of the mixing desk of larp and to identify a limited number of key design choices that are in tension, to help people make intentional decisions about it. While a limited number of choices on scales is hardly enough to capture the whole design space, they can be used to highlight areas proved central to democratic engagement. However, such a model will not be a tool for identifying “correct” choices or to even rank choices, but to show the trade-offs inherent in making design choices. Any decision that is made renders certain things possible while other ones as impossible. This is why we need values and a vision to guide the process.

For examples, there is a tension between a space being inclusive of everyone and having a nurturing shared community culture. The former implies that there should be as low as possible a threshold for new participants to peek in and take part – but this makes it harder to transform a participant group into an ensemble, a temporary community of people who share high trust and feel safe enough to participate even in challenging processes. These tensions, or choices, will come up repeatedly in a design process. Should the event be in the centre of a city where more people can pop in and out, or should it be on an isolated island so that everyone can concentrate on the shared journey of the joint event? Obviously, both approaches can be good choices but serve different goals.

This example design choice, which could be characterized as choice between open and contained, or between public and magical, is but one of many that we see as relating to the creation of larp-cultural events. Other such choices can be found between, say, focused and inter-disciplinary, between customized and standardized, or between cost and access.²⁵ What our practical experience in this kind of design tells us is that these choices are not binary: every choice will affect agency, participation, power, and belonging across the entire design space.

Creating a design language involves naming these choices. Organising them into a model informed by research into democratic spaces helps make the choices and their consequences visible, legible, and actionable for a designer. This is what we turn our attention to next in Larpocracy.

4.4 Coda

In this document we have been working towards a model of participatory cultural events and its related design language that functions as a tool for people who create such events. Importantly, the model should be useful in strengthening democratic cultures and democracy-related skills.

To lay the foundations for this, we have concentrated on larp festivals and conventions, as a specific type of cultural event that we believe often to be consciously designed. We have explored the emergence and history of larp festivals and argued that they should be viewed as cultural institutions and as part of a cultural public sphere. We have also discussed the concept of a ‘democratic space’ and bridged how that relates to the larp festival. Finally, we have discussed how larp festivals and other experiences where participation is a key element can be approached from the point of view of design.

The next step is to develop model and design language for larp festivals and conventions – and to discuss how democratic goals can be integrated and supported. Aspects of the model should be generalizable in a manner allowing it to also be used in cultural events that are not larp-related, and perhaps in the context of democratic innovation.

²⁵ Designing for democratic engagement requires that event creators are aware of both the democratic values that this particular event is seeking to implement and understand how these goals can be achieved at the event planning level. The toolkit for understanding design of participatory events with democratic aspirations will make the process easier to navigate. Such a toolbox may, additionally, be useful in evaluating retrospectively, for example from the perspective of the event participant, how well the goals were achieved. However, that is not the main focus of the tool.

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Appendix A: List of Larp Festivals

The following list has been compiled during 2025 and is being updated regularly until the end of the Larpocracy project. The database is found online at the address:

https://1drv.ms/x/c/74807ba04adc80a8/EQeaLN9NMSxMqS_qEH6foeMBdMei1KM0xffX1k3EcCoy4Q?e=9lxY2q

Table of larp festivals

This is a list of the larp festivals organised during the calendar year 2025, in chronological order from the earliest to the most recent. The goal has been to capture all larp festival and conventions in Europe, but some events from other parts of the world have also been included. For more information on the festivals, please check out the online database.

name	country	city	homepage
The Smoke	UK	London	https://thesmoke.org/
der Larp Conference	Germany	Wiesbaden	https://derlarp.de/
Black Box Copenhagen	Denmark	Copenhagen	https://blackbox-cph.dk/
Carbon	Poland	Katowice	https://www.facebook.com/events/katowice/carbon-2025-edycja-iii/301408326041270/?_rdr
Stoori	Finland	Helsinki	https://stooriorg.wordpress.com
What's Your Game Larp Kit Fair	UK	Gloucester	https://www.facebook.com/events/1443486236244813/
KoLa Larp Conference	Poland	Krakow	https://konferencja.larpowa.pl/
Prolog	Sweden	Trollhättan	https://lajvkonvent.se
International Larp Festival Online	online	online	https://chaosleague.org/international-larp-festival-online/
Intercon X	USA	Warwick	https://x.interconlarp.org
Intercon W	USA	Warwick	https://w.interconlarp.org/
Laagland Festival	Netherlands	Utrecht	https://www.laaglandlarp.com/
LarpCon	UK	Coalville	https://larpcon.co.uk/
Knutepunkt	Noway	Oslo	https://knutepunkt.org
Baltic LARP UNcon	Lithuania	Vilnius	https://www.facebook.com/events/s/baltic-larp-uncon-2025/1531177114176762/
Tapestries	USA	San Francisco	https://2025.tapestrieslarp.org
Fastaval	Denmark	Hobro	https://www.fastaval.dk/en/
A Larp Festival 2025	USA	Cambridge, MA	https://alarpfestival-2025.concentral.net/

Festival du Jeu de Rôle	France	Kaysersberg	https://www.festivaldujeuderole.fr/
Phoenix LARP Convention	New Zealand	Christchurch	https://www.facebook.com/events/s/phoenix-larp-convention-2025/942605717922288/
Larpart	Poland	Glińo Wielkie	https://www.larpart.pl
Eternal Convention	Germany	Bacharach	https://eternal-con.de/en/home
Voidspace Live	UK	London	https://voidspacezine.com/voidspace-live-2025-open-call/
Summer Larpin	USA	Boxborough, MA	https://summerlarpin2025.concentral.net/
Kaltenberger Ritterturnier	Germany	Kaltenberg	https://www.ritterturnier.de/en/
Orkon	Poland	Niegowa	http://www.orkon.org/
GamesCon	Czech Republic	Pardubice	https://gamecon.cz/
Ropecon	Finland	Helsinki	https://ropecon.fi/en/front/
Continuum	UK	Cranfield	https://continuumconvention.co.uk
Larp Fort	Poland	Czyżowice	https://www.5zywiolow.com/strefaprzygody/pl/w/larp-fort
Fornost	Poland	Czatachowa	https://fornost.pl/
Labo-GN	France	Montauban-de-Bretagne	https://www.labogn.org/
Make a Scene	USA	Minneapolis	https://makeascenemn.org/en/
BlackBox Summer Week	Poland	Glińo Wielkie	https://bb3c.pl/blackbox/blackbox-summer-week-2025/
Ziemie Jałowe	Poland	Gliwice	http://ziemiejalowe.pl/
LARP Zomer Festival	Netherlands	Otterlo	https://www.larp-platform.nl/zomer-festival/
Castlefest	Netherlands	Lisse	https://castlefest.nl/en
Immersion Larp Festival	Finland	Turku	http://www.nordicrpg.fi/immersion/
Bristol Freeform Games Day	UK	Bristol	https://bristol.freeforming.uk/events/2025/
Flamberg	Poland	Czatachowa	https://flamberg.pl
BeCon	USA	Elk Grove Village (Chicago)	https://2025.beconlarp.com
Festival Mediaval	Germany	Selb	https://www.festival-mediaval.com/
Jornadas Oniria	Spain	Segovia	https://vilynoc.com/
Cidre & Dragon - Le festival de la Fantasy	France	Merville-Franceville-Plage	https://www.cidreetdragon.eu/

Spillerom	Norway	Stavangers	https://www.spillerom.org/
Portal Larp Convention	Slovenia	Ljubljana	https://www.facebook.com/portallarpconvention
Forum	Denmark	Vissenbjerg	https://forumbifrost.dk/praktisk/
BEta LARP	Belgium	Charleroi	http://beta.larp.be/
The Overkill Festival	Netherlands	Enschede	https://theoverkill.nl/
Consequences	UK	Chichester	https://r.consequences.org.uk/
Stockholm Scenario Festival	Sweden	Stockholm	https://scenariofestival.se
Krak-ON	Poland	Krakow	https://krak-on.info/
Liminal-con 2025	Denmark	Aarhus	https://www.facebook.com/events/1203812627595129/?acontext=%7B%22ref%22%3A%2252%22%2C%22action_history%22%3A%22[%7B%5C%22surface%5C%22%3A%5C%22share_link%5C%22%2C%5C%22mechanism%5C%22%3A%5C%22share_link%5C%22%2C%5C%22extra_data%5C%22%3A%7B%5C%22invite_link_id%5C%22%3A687194020944476%7D%7D]%22%7D
Кабинетко уикенд - "Kabinetka Weekend"	Russia	Nizhnyi Novgorod	https://vk.com/festival_ky
Italian Larp Festival	Italy	Porta Bologna	https://chaosleague.org/italian-larp-festival/
Midwinter Fair	Netherlands	Alphen aan den Rijn	https://archeon.eu/midwinterfair/

Appendix B: Overview of the Fieldwork and Study Visits to Larp Festivals

During the calendar year 2025 we visited eleven larp festivals and conventions. These visits are here presented in chronological order from the earliest to the latest. The visits are divided into two categories, study visits and field work. Field work refers to visits where researchers from academic partners have conducted participatory observation. Study visits refer to visits by practitioner partners visiting festivals and conventions to learn about their workings, and to visits by academic partners to festivals and conventions that does not count as field work, but background mapping.

Blackbox CPH

Annual larp festival in Copenhagen, Denmark.

Organized since 2012, Blackbox CPH is one of the oldest Nordic larp festival that concentrates specially on blackbox larps. "The larps will apply theatrical lighting and sound for controlling the play and several of them will be experimenting with other theatrical techniques. This creates a unique form of role play that has come to be known as black box larp.

Date & place: January 16-18, 2025, Copenhagen, Denmark.

Website: <https://blackbox-cph.dk/en/welcome/>

Participants: While majority of the participants are Danish, the festival is international, bringing in both players and designers from numerous countries, mostly from Europe.

Organizers: The festival has a 16-member organizing team according to the website. All are volunteers. At Blackbox CPH the technical aspects of blackbox larps, the support that light and sound can give, is central. Many of the organizer tasks relate to managing and operating this technology. This role is more prominent at Blackbox CPH than at many other larp festivals.

Programme: The festival features 16 larps (or larp-adjacent experiences) during three days. The larps played were *Above Your Station* by Laurie Penny, *Baboon Moon* by Karete Jacobsen Meland, *Created through love (but no longer needed)* by Nina Runa Essendrop, *Dawn of Europe* by Jan Gebert and Ondřej Provazník, *Estranged* by Maya B. Hindsberg, *If stars are lit* by Maryia Karachun, Zhenja Karachun, Volha Rudak, and Nastassia Sinitsyna, *inSanity* by Alexander Bakkensen and Sydney Mikosch, *Into The Unknown* by Halfdan Keller Justesen and Sagalinn Leo Tangen, *Once Upon a Time in Space* by Tjalfe Chessni and Martin Andreas Dahl Sinding, *Panopticon* by Nór Hernø, *Root and Branch* by Alex Brown, *The Language of Plants* by Omi-peah Ryding and Roman Schramm, *The Last Hour of Sunlight* by Charlie Andersen, *The Last Moot* by Mikkel Brunberg, *Trümmer Träume (Debris Dreams)* by Ari Adamski and Sophie Allerding, and *Where The Wild Things Are* by Karete Jacobsen Meland, Martin Nielsen, and Nina Lund Westerdahl.

Study visit: Jaakko Stenros, Johanna Koljonen, and Piotrek Warzyszynski participated at the festival to gather background information on larp festivals and their design before actual field work could begin. This visit was geared towards identifying questions relating to the form and organization of larp festivals. The three representatives of Larpocarcy played in larps, participated in the social program, and chatted with festival organizers.

Stoori

One day annual larp festival in Helsinki, Finland.

Started in 2023, Stoori is a single day “freeform festival” in Helsinki. The event offers old and new short form larps and freeform scenarios that can be played without special equipment.

Date & place: 1.2.2025, Helsinki, Finland.

Website: <https://stooriorg.wordpress.com/>

Participants: The latest edition had 60-70 participants mostly from the greater Helsinki region – although there were also people from other parts of Finland and a few from abroad. The Stoori crowd tends to be middle aged and white. All experiences are played in English.

Organizers: The event has 2-3 main organizers plus a few additional people handling support functions. The organizers are volunteers and the event does not receive public funding.

Programme: The festival had five experiences running simultaneously, and two four-hour slots for them to run in, meaning that there were ten larps or freeform scenarios presented. The presented works were: *7 Years and 1 Day* by Jokim Garcia, *Sexcraft* by Frida Sofie Jansen & Tor Kjetil Edland, *Dirty laundry* by Holger Pick and Mo Holkar, *Unicorn Season* by Pihla Lehtinen, *We Are Not Vampires* by Lizzie Stark & Jason Morningstar, *The 24th Hour* by Niina Niskanen, *Blood of the Vikings* by Jukka Oksanen, *Players Guide to Flirting* by Jukka Oksanen, *The Last Movie* by Simon Larsson and Björn Thálen, and *Wonderworks* by Lauri Lukka.

Study visit: The event was attended by Jaakko Stenros, who was there continuing background mapping for larp festivals.

KoLa Konferencja Larpowa

Annual, Polish larp conference.

Organized since 2012, in 2025 KoLa took place in Krakow. The convention rotates every year among different cities in Poland. It is organized by larp-related entities (mostly NGOs). In 2025 KoLa was coordinated by the Students Society of Technical University of Krakow (Larp AGH) and for the first time produced an academic publication.

Date & place: 21-23.02.2025, Faculty of Humanities AGH, Czarnowiejska 36, Kraków

Web site: <https://www.agh.edu.pl/wydarzenia/detail/s/konferencja-larpowa-kola>, mostly active on Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/events/822179946518282>

Participants: 120-140 participants, Polish larpers and larp organizers coming from all around the country. All participants were 18+ with majority being in the age of 30-40. Language of conference was Polish.

Program: Program items were provided by the community but curated and selected by the organizers. The event featured presentations, talks and discussions and workshops (eg. Impro workshop). No larps were played during the event. Topics of the program items differed with some

being an introduction to larp (eg. „Novice at Larp”) to very advanced and specific topics (eg. Case study of using larp to reconstruct medieval theater).

Study visit: Learning through participating (Marcin Słowikowski, Piotr Warzyszynski) during talks and pane discussions, The study visit included also a 45-minute presentation of Larpocracy project and 90-minutes discussion about democratic practices during larp events (~20 participants).

Knutepunkt

Annual international larp festival that travels between Nordic countries.

Knutepunkt has been organized since 1997. The event travels between Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland – and its name also changes to match the local language (Knutepunkt, Knutpunkt, Knudepunkt, Solmukohta). The event hosts various Programme relating to larps, mainly lectures, workshops, discussions, and larps, but there is also quite a bit of social program. The event usually runs from Thursday to Sunday and preceded by a festival around the host city that starts on preceding Sunday or Monday. The event itself is usually held at a hotel or other venue that allows participants to lodge on site.

Date & place: 13-16.3.2025, Oslo, Norway

Website: <https://knutepunkt.org> (The site no longer works.)

Participants: While the event started out as a Nordic one, very rapidly it expanded to be much more international. Nowadays it is common to have participants from over twenty countries.

Organizers: Knutepunkt travels between four countries and each country has their own way of deciding who organizes the event. Some have sustained organization that handle the event every four years, other build an organization whenever one is needed. There is no general overseeing body. The organizing is mostly done on a volunteer basis, although in some countries organizations with a few permanent employees may be involved. The event has received public funding on some years. In Norway in 2025 all participants were required to do “hero shifts” and help with the organization of the event.

Programme: Approximately ten different larps were played during the event, with additional larps staged during the preceding Week in Oslo. In addition, there were lectures, panel discussions, open discussions, social program, workshops, and other Programme items.

Study visit: Many Larpocracy members were present at Knutepunkt, and presented on Larpocracy. This is a well-known event for many members and represent a key starting-point for Larpocracy. The study visit aspect mostly related to noticing if anything significant had changed.

Ropecon

Largest independent role-playing convention in Europe.

Ropecon has been organized annually since 1994. It brings together player of tabletop role-playing games, miniature wargames, collectible card gamers, board gamers, larpers, cosplayers, as well as other people interested in game cultures. The event lasts three days and is preceded by an academic conference. Since 2016 the event has been organized in the Helsinki Expo and Convention Centre.

Date & place: 25-27.7.2025, Helsinki, Finland.

Website: <https://ropecon.fi/>

Participants: The event keep growing and in 2025 for the first time there were more than 10,000 participants. The event attracts visitors of all ages, from toddlers to senior citizens. A significant minority of participants dress up for the event.

Organizers: Ropecon organization has a few dozen of people working around the year, with most of the work concentrating on the six months leading up to the event. A significant portion of the participants contribute work towards the event (from holding Programme and running games, to manning the clock room and selling merch at the convention store desk), and anyone who does two work shifts can attend for free.

Programme: The Programme is very varied, with numerous game tournaments and competitions, possibilities to play hundreds of games, lectures, discussions, workshops, but also historical dances, galas and parties, as well as a big vendor area. Larps were available to be played in Finnish, English, and Swedish.

Fieldwork: Larpocracy fieldwork started at Ropecon after the ethical evaluation of the study was cleared. Jaakko Stenros did field work at the event, doing participant observation and interviews. In addition, Piotrek Warzyszynski was present doing a study visit.

Immersion

Annual larp festival in Turku, Finland.

Immersion is a relatively new festival, having been organized only twice. It takes place in a building complex that hosts several theatres next to the River Aura. The festival features both new works and older larps form over the decades.

Date & place: 8-9.8.2025, Turku, Finland.

Website: <https://www.nordicrpg.fi/immersion/>

Participants: While most festival participants come from southern Finland, Immersion is quite international, drawing in a significant number of players from abroad. The festival is held in English.

Organizers: There are three main organizers behind the festival, with 15 other people pitching in both before and during the festival. The festival has received monetary support from an arts foundation.

Programme: 24 larps in total were played over the two days, divided into three slots. *Panopticon* by Nór Hernø, *Rap Superstar* by Lauri Lukka, *Beyond the Barricades* by Eva Wei and Rosalind Göthberg, *Farewell to Earth* by Maarit Neuvonen, *10 Birch Street* by Kaisa Mikkola and Aino Haavisto, *Dirty Laundry* by Holger Pick and Mo Holkar, *Those Were Dark Times and Hare Paid the Price* by Matko Radić, *inside:outside* by Emir Zeik (Eirik Fatland & Mike Pohjola), *Westwind* by Mo Holkar, *Superconductivity* by Thomas Steinfeldt Nielsen and Kalle Hunnerup Jacobsen, *Debris Dreams* by Ari Adamski & Sophie Allering, *Estranged* by Maya Hindsberg, *Fridge Poetry* by Usva Inei and Hazel Anneke Dixon, *Horga Dance* by Eva Wei and Rosalind Göthberg, *Glow* by Niina Niskanen, Hanna

Erkinjuntti, and Tiia Seeve, *Unicorn Season* by Pihla Lehtinen, *Faerie* by Halfdan Keller Justesen, *Tiny Steps in Heaven* by Tamara Nassar, *Mobilized* by Nea Landin, Gabriel Widing, and Scott Cazan, *Women in Finland* by Aino Haavisto, *Heart of Darkness* by Tuukka Tenhunen, *The Memoratorium: A Pleasant Place* by Monica Hjort Traxl & Morten Greis Fakkelskov, *Mind over Sight* by Leland Masek, Daniel Fernández Galeote, Zoi Asterataki, and Edward Rupper, and *Finding Tom* by Vili Myrsky Nissinen, Nina Mutik.

Fieldwork: Jaakko Stenros conducted fieldwork at the festival.

Make a Scene Festival

Annual, larp scenario festival in Twin Cities, Minnesota.

Organized since 2019, Make a Scene is “a weekend-long exploration and celebration of in-person narrative games (...) guided by three main principles that inspire us to cultivate a compassionate and creative community: Bringing People Together, Bringing Stories to Life, Bringing Hearts to Mind”

Date & place: 22-24 Aug 2025, Center For Performing Arts, 3754 Pleasant Ave, Minneapolis, MN 55409

Web site: <http://makeascenemn.org/en/>

Participants: 40-50 participants from Twin Cities and other cities from the USA, some attending the whole event, other - particular scenarios. Both larpers and participants new to larp. One of the goals was inclusion in several ways: scenarios centered in accessible play, sliding-scale admission price, code of conduct centered on safety, support, and equity, wheelchair-accessible location, quiet room for sensory overload, amenities for parents.

Organizers: 8-person group of active larpers, larp enthusiasts and designers from Twin Cities, partnering with Larp House – inclusive and member-powered collective supporting the festival with volunteers; and Metropolitan Regional Arts Council granting the project from the arts and cultural heritage fund.

Programme: Make a Scene 2025 theme Under the Surface. The Programme featured 8 curated premiere larp scenarios: *Actors* by Tom Fendt, *Echo Caprese in The Silver Moon Directive* by Jae Krehbiel, *Face It* by Melissa Song Loong, *Mozog Station is Falling Down* by Espionage Party (Sarah Barringer, Rey Miranti, Kyle Kissell), *Roots Underground* by Shawn Roske, *The City the Rats Kept* by Peter Haggmann, *The Language of Bones* by July Pilowsky, *Thunder Only Happens When It's Raining* by Soft Chaos, played in four Programme slots: Friday 17:00-22:00, Saturday 9:30-14:00 and 15:30-20:00, Sunday 9:30-14:00, communal meals at the venue, party with tier cake and blanket fort on Saturday evening.

Study visit: Learning about the event through participation (Marcin Słowikowski) at larps, social program, and other informal social interactions. Interviews with two organizers and three participants. The study visit included also a nonformal 30 minutes “ask me anything” about Larpocracy (ca 10 participants).

Portal Larp Convention

Annual Convention

Organized for thirteenth time, in 2025 Portal was organized in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The convention rotates every year among host countries mostly on the Balkan (it has also been in Poland and Ukraine). Focus of Portal in 2025: "Regional connections, larp deepdive on connection & community, edu-larp for sustainability".

Date & place: 26-28.09.2025, Četrtni center Golovec, Pesarska 14, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Web site: <https://www.facebook.com/portallarpconvention>

Participants: 30-40 participants, mostly from Slovenian larp community, with a organized group representing Terrible Creations from Slovenia and 5-8 international guests. All participants were 18+. Most of the members of the Slovenian larp community were between 20-30 years old while the international participants, connected to Portal for longer time were between 40 and 50 years old.

Programme: Programme was fully prepared by the members of the larp community; it was a mix of discussions, talks and workshops. Also, two larps were played throughout the weekend. Topics of the Programme idems were focused on edu-larp and general game design. Planned game-jam activity did not happen, due to the low number of participants. Social Programme was focused on introducing the Slovenian larp community to international participants.

Study visit: Learning through participating (Marcin Słowikowski, Piotr Warzyszynski) during talks and pane discussions, social Programme and other informal social interactions. Qualitative interviews with two participants. The fieldwork included also a 45-minute presentation of Larpocracy project and discussion of assumption for My Po!nt Festival with potential target group (6 participants).

Spillerom

Annual, national larp festival and convention in Norway.

Organized since 2014 in Trondheim. Later in Bergen 2015, Stavanger 2016, Marnadal 2017, Oslo 2018, Trondheim 2019, Bergen 2020, Haugesund 2021 (Canceled) and Skien 2024. Next year: Drammen.

Date & place: 26.9-28.9.2025, at Forus Scandic Hotel in Stavanger, Norway.

Web site (changes with each festival): [Spillerom – Norges laivfestival](https://www.facebook.com/Spillerom), also uses Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/Spillerom/about> (650 followers) and Discord.

Participants: 50-70 participants from all over larp Norway, some for the whole weekend, other for a day or a short visit. All ages are allowed, but underaged (under 18) need a chaperon. Both participants new to larp, families with kids, old-timers (started larping 20-30 years ago) and larp designers of international larps were present.

Organizers: A team of six adults aged 30 – 50, originated from SLIK (Stavanger larp organisers). Three of them was on the Spillerom team from 2016.

Programme: Participants themselves send in electronic forms with what they would like to organize or present. A mix of short (2-4 hours) larps, both 18+ and children's larps, discussions panels (e.g. vampire larp, how to use language at larps), workshops (e.g. historical dances, patinating, play conflict, how to talk in front of crowds, pitch a new larp), larp café (including history of larping in

Stavanger, “my first larp” and presentation of upcoming larps), an aera with bord games (run by a board game association) and a big party dinner Saturday night.

Fieldwork: Participatory observation (Hanne Grasmø) at larps, workshops and informal social interactions. Qualitative interviews with two organizers and three participants. The fieldwork included also a democracy workshop (5 participants), a 45 minutes “ask me anything” about Larpocracy (ca 10 participants), and a 5 minutes presentation at the Larp café about Larpocracy and our own larp festivals (about 40 participants).

Beta-larp

Annual, national larp festival and convention in Belgium.

Organized for 10 years, first just for French speaking larpers, since a few years also for international, English speaking larpers. “It’s a weekend dedicated to the news about the Belgian larp, but that’s not all! Conferences and round tables are led by motivated volunteers, in parallel with workshops (confections, thematic and practical topics...), other kinds of animations or short format role-playing games.”

Date & place: 14-16 Nov 2025 in Auberge de Jeunesse de Charleroi , [Rue du Bastion d’Egmont 3 6000 Charleroi,gium](#)

Web site: <http://beta.larp.be>, but more active on Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/events/1139938413972289?active_tab=about

Participants: 60-80 participants, majority representing French speaking Belgian community, group of international, English-speaking participants, organized group of 8 persons from Palestine, representing Seen Youth Network. Most or majority of participants were over 18, they mostly knew each other as the event was directed to the well-integrated Belgian larp community

Organizers: BE LARP - Fédération Belge du jeu de rôles grandeur naturem (Belgian Larp Federation, institutionalized association, address: Rue Nanon, 98 - 5002 Namur). the team of 4 Adults (aged from 20 to 40 years old), supported by older organizers of previous editions of BEta Larp, who were there and were ready to spontaneously take over some tasks if needed.

Programme: Programme was mostly focused on integration of Belgian larp community and giving recognition to events organized by the community (Speed Dating, Larp Museum featuring larp related artifacts brought by the community, annual larp awards). The Programme featured mostly presentations, discussions, and workshops. There was one larp played. Most of the Programme was in French with one item in each time slot in English.

Study visit: Learning through participation (Piotr Warzyszynski) during English speaking Programme items, social Programme and other informal social interactions. Interviews with two organizers and participant from Palestine are planned. The study visit included also nonformal talks about Larpocracy project, especially the assumptions of WP5 (ca 15 participants).

Grenselandet

Annual, international chamber larp festival in Norway.

Organized ([Grenslandet - Oslo chamber larp festival](#)) since 2010. "Grenslandet is an annual festival for chamberlarp organized in Oslo since 2010. We aim to have a programme of high quality scenarios within the genres of blackbox, freeform and other chamberlarps. The larps are run by their authors. The festival is organized on non-profit basis through the organization Fantasiforbundet (org no 994 704 346)." ([grenslandet.net/about](#))

Date & place: 5.-6.12.25, at Hausmania and Rikscenen/Øvingshotellet/Deichman Library Schous. Oslo, Norway. Informal Sunday brunch at Café Sarah.

Web site: <http://www.grenslandet.net/>, but active at Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/Grenslandet/> and by email.

Participants: 60-80 international participants (e.g from Sweden, Denmark, Finland, UK, France, Germany, Spain, Poland, and other cities in Norway). Some participants are internationals (e.g. Belarus, Russia, Ukraine and others) living in Norway. Normally 18+ years, but this year two big youth delegations from Norway (Ludo) and Denmark (Bifrost) with youth down to 14 yo. New adult participants who have never played larps, as well.

Organizers: Fantasiforbundet is the formal organizer, Martin Nilsen is the visible organizer and communication centre. There is a team of volunteers, but no names on web sites or during the larp festival. Grenslandet 2025 was founded by Kulturrådet. (Grenslandet is normally founded by Norwegian governmental bodies, there will often also be part of the funding to pay for larpers from countries where Fantasiforbundet has run democracy larp-projects, like Palestine, Baltic countries and Belarus.)

Programme: Around 15 larps from different larp designers who have pitched them themselves. Play from 1-3 larps: Friday: 17:00-21:00, Saturday: 11:00-15:00, Saturday: 17:00-21:00. This year there ways Lounge party Friday night and big party with dancing, midnight ritual and full bar Saturday night. Hangout at Hausmania Friday 16:00-01:00, Saturday 10:00-03:00 (bar from 20:30-03:00). It is possible to just attend the social parts. No common accommodation nor food.

Fieldwork: Participatory observation (Hanne Grasmø) at larps, introduction, parties and other informal social interaction. The fieldwork included a 5-minute presentation at the beginning of the festival (about 50 participants).

About the Authors

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